

Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 3548–3644

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Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Technical Report 0033

Cover photo

Mosaic of target Tapirapeco. MAHLI focus merge products showing a stratified and fractured rock outcrop in the Marker Band valley. The images, illuminated by sunlight from the upper left, were acquired and merged on Sol 3605.

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7.1 Definitions and conventions

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Acknowledgements

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Note that pages are not numbered in this document because all of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, and *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* were inserted separately after creation using a word processing tool that differs from the one used for the text.

Abstract

Covering the time between Curiosity’s 3548th and 3644th Martian days (sols) of operations in northern Gale crater, Mars, this document is a compilation of the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Team’s notes and information about MAHLI images and activities conducted during that period. The report includes brief sol-by-sol notes—written as the mission unfolded—regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used and significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation. The document, further, contains information regarding range and scale (camera working distance and scale of in-focus elements of an image); the parent images, range, and scale information associated with each MAHLI focus merge product created onboard the instrument; and a description of the purpose and intent behind acquisition of each MAHLI image and creation of each onboard focus merge product. The MSL science team and rover engineers routinely used the information contained in this report during the course of the mission for tactical planning, strategic planning, and scientific analysis.

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction and purpose

This document is a compilation of the Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Team’s notes and information about MAHLI images and activities that occurred during the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) mission between Sols 3548 and 3644.

MAHLI is a 2-megapixel color camera with a focusable macro lens mounted on the turret at the end of a robotic arm aboard NASA’s MSL rover, Curiosity (Edgett *et al.* 2012). The rover landed and began operation in northern Gale crater, Mars, on 6 August 2012 (Vasavada *et al.* 2014).

Each *Curiosity’s Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator’s Notebook* covers a specific period corresponding to a release of MAHLI data to the NASA Planetary Data System (PDS) Imaging Node (<http://pds-imaging.jpl.nasa.gov/>). As some MAHLI data can arrive from Mars months or years after a given release period, the publication of these reports typically lags behind the PDS release schedule by a period that varies from one occasion to the next, depending largely on when data acquired during that period arrive on Earth and when we have time to complete the *Principal Investigator’s Notebook* report.

This report, *Curiosity’s Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator’s Notebook: Sols 3548–3644*, corresponds to MAHLI data Release 32 in the NASA PDS archives. These are data acquired 30 July 2022 through 06 November 2022.

1.2 Versions and change log

The enclosed materials were compiled as the MSL mission unfolded. That being the case, we might sometimes have made errors. The reader should be aware that this report might be corrected via release of a new version in the future.

A new version would also be created if new data from this report’s period (Martian sols) are received from the instrument after an earlier version has been made available. This can occur because MAHLI can store data onboard the instrument for an indefinite period of time after acquisition. As a result, images are archived with the NASA PDS on the basis of when they are received on Earth, not when they are acquired on Mars.

Covering the Sol 3548 through 3644 period, this document is Version 1.

If this were a later version, this section would document the changes made relative to the previous.

2 Instrument activities for this period

This section captures day-by-day or sol-by-sol notes written by the MAHLI Team, as the mission unfolded, regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used or significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 3548 – 3644						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Heading through Paratepuy Pass	02 Aug 22	3551	4	40	4	MAHLI imaged the target Karisparo, which included a 3x1 mosaic. The focus stack images were also merged.
	04 Aug 22	3553	5	42	4	MAHLI imaged the target Arorouta and acquired a 2x1 mosaic on the target Yakontipu. The focus stack images were also merged.
	07 Aug 22	3555	7	54	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Sloth_Island and Aponguaou.
	07 Aug 22	3556	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 3555 were merged.
	09 Aug 22/ 10 Aug 22	3558	9	75	7	MAHLI imaged the targets Sao_Marcos, Essequibo and Kumu_Falls. The focus stack images were also merged.
	12 Aug 22	3560	7	58	5	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Annai and the target Mirizal. The focus stack images were also merged. MAHLI images that correspond to CDPIDs 1 through 3313 (data from Sols 3362–3481) were deleted from the MAHLI DEA non-volatile memory storage.
	14 Aug 22	3562	6	50	4	MAHLI imaged the targets El_Silencio and Orinduik and the focus stack images were merged.
	16 Aug 22	3564	6	46	4	MAHLI imaged the targets Sand_Creek and Nascente and the focus stack images were merged.
	18 Aug 22	3566	4	27	0	MAHLI imaged the REMS UV Sensor and the target Yupukari.
	19 Aug 22	3567	0	0	2	Focus stack images from Sol 3566 were merged.
	20 Aug 22	3568	11	70	0	MAHLI imaged the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets as well as the target Fortaleza and the DRT-brushed target Massara.
	22 Aug 22	3570	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 3568 were merged.
	23 Aug 22	3571	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the target Raimundo and the focus stack images were merged.
Traversing through Marker Band alley towards the Canaima Drill Site	25 Aug 22	3573	10	60	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Kanuku and Wadakapiapue.
	26 Aug 22	3574	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 3573 were merged.
	27 Aug 22	3575	11	86	8	MAHLI imaged the targets Los_Rosos, Nova_Estrela and Enamuna and the focus stack images were merged.
	30 Aug 22	3578	9	79	7	MAHLI imaged the target Jacamim and the DRT-brushed target Micobie. The focus stack images were also merged.
Traversing through Marker Band valley towards the Canaima Drill Site	04 Sep 22	3583	7	54	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Marie_Island, Branco and Machado.
	11 Sep 22	3590	0	5	10	Focus stack images from Sol 3583 were merged.
	13 Sep 22	3592	3	22	2	MAHLI imaged the target Piabas and the focus stack images were merged.
	15 Sep 22/ 16 Sep 22	3594	6	52	5	MAHLI imaged the targets Tiger_Pond and La_Mata. The focus stack images were also merged.
	18 Sep 22	3596	10	72	6	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed targets Marshall_Falls and Corona_Falls and the focus stack images were merged.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 3548 – 3644						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Traversing through Marker Band valley towards the Canaima Drill Site	21 Sep 22	3599	11	94	9	MAHLI imaged the targets El Triunfo, Nova Cintra and Pirara. The focus stack images were also merged.
	23 Sep 22	3601	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Cauarane and the focus stack images were merged.
	25 Sep 22	3603	9	66	6	MAHLI imaged the targets Tapirapeco, Lagoa do Velame and Lagoa do Macaco. The focus stack images were also merged.
	27 Sep 22	3605	6	60	6	MAHLI acquired a 6x1 mosaic on Tapirapeco and the focus stack images were merged.
	29 Sep 22	3607	6	12	0	MAHLI imaged the targets El Pao De La Fortuna and Espirito Santo.
At the Canaima Drill Site	01 Oct 22	3609	8	48	4	MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Canaima before and after DRT, and after a drill bit preload test; then the focus stack images were merged.
	04 Oct 22	3612	1	2	0	Drill preparation activities at the planned Canaima sample extraction site. MAHLI imaged the intended site for the Canaima sample discard pile.
	16 Oct 22/ 17 Oct 22	3624	3	14	1	MAHLI imaged the Canaima drill hole and cuttings. The focus stack images were also merged.
	18 Oct 22	3626	4	24	2	MAHLI imaged the target Bacabal and the Canaima drill cuttings. The focus stack images were also merged.
Traversing through Marker Band valley towards Gediz Vallis ridge	20 Oct 22/ 21 Oct 22	3628	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the target Pacu and the focus stack images were merged.
	23 Oct 22	3630	6	44	0	MAHLI images that correspond to CDPIDs 3314 through 4854 (data from Sols 3482–3560) were deleted from the MAHLI DEA non-volatile memory storage. MAHLI imaged the targets Vista Alegre and Santa Silvia.
	23 Oct 22	3631	0	0	4	Focus stack images from Sol 3630 were merged.
	26 Oct 22	3633	4	24	2	MAHLI imaged the target Balata and the focus stack images were merged. The REMS UV Sensor was imaged as well.
	28 Oct 22	3635	5	36	3	MAHLI imaged the targets Mau and Univini and the focus stack images were merged.
	30 Oct 22	3637	7	57	5	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Catrimani and the target Marari. The focus stack images were also merged.
Traversing through Marker Band valley towards Gediz Vallis ridge	01 Nov 22	3639	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the target Nicara and the focus stack images were merged.
At the edge of the Marker Band	03 Nov 22	3641	14	108	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed targets Mel and Mamupi and the target Iracema.
	04 Nov 22	3642	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 3641 were merged.
	06 Nov 22	3644	20	192	0	MAHLI imaged the target Mixiguana, which includes a 6x2 mosaic, and the target Mocra.

The NASA PDS archives include documentation that describes the MAHLI image ID and file naming scheme and the nature of the archived Experiment Data Record (EDR) and Reduced Data Record (RDR) products (Malin *et al.*, 2013).

The EDR products, the raw data product, have the following file name scheme:

- 1 **[Image ID]_XXXX** – these are always 8-bit images except for the 16-bit products (type A) returned from MAHLI for calibration purposes.

The RDR products are of the following nature:

- 2 **[Image ID]_DRXX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated color images,
- 3 **[Image ID]_DRLX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated and geometric calibrated color images,
- 4 **[Image ID]_DRCX** – 8-bit relative radiometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied, and
- 5 **[Image ID]_DRCL** – 8-bit relative radiometric and geometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied.

The following table describes the variety of image types (raw, lossless, JPEG, focus merge, thumbnail, *etc.*). Malin *et al.* (2013) described these in greater detail.

product type	product format
A	raster 16-bit image
B	raster 8-bit image
C	lossless compressed image
D	JPEG grayscale image
E	JPEG 4:2:2 color image
F	JPEG 4:4:4 color image
G	raster thumbnail of parent image
H	JPEG gray thumbnail of parent image
I	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of parent image
J	raster 8-bit video frame
K	lossless compressed video frame
L	JPEG grayscale video frame
M	JPEG 4:2:2 color video frame
N	JPEG 4:4:4 color video frame
O	raster 8-bit thumbnail of video frame
P	JPEG gray thumbnail of video frame
Q	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of video frame
R	focus merge best focus image product
S	focus merge range map product
T	focus merge best focus thumbnail
U	focus merge range map thumbnail

Types R and T are JPEG 4:4:4; S and U are JPEG grayscale products.

3.3 MAHLI LED positions

The MAHLI camera head has two groups of two white light LEDs (Edgett *et al.* 2012), called Group 1 and Group 2. For reference, the figure below shows their location on the camera head and how these locations translate to positions relative to pixel 0,0 (column 0, row 0) on the MAHLI CCD. In addition, MAHLI has two 365 nm ultraviolet (UV) LEDs, also shown in the figure. Each group of two LEDs (Group 1, Group 2, and UV) can be operated together or independently with each of the other two groups. When the LEDs are used, which group was operated is reported in the RATIONALE_DESC description of the image intent and purpose (Section 6).

MAHLI image TVC_MH0809080020000032B00, left, shows the violet and white reflections of the UV and Group 1 and Group 2 white light LEDs, indicating their location in relation to the CCD's pixel at column 0, row 0. The photograph on the right shows the camera head with its dust cover open and LEDs labeled.

4 Camera range and scale information

4.1 Purpose and description

MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* (or “Distance and Scale Information Sheets”) describe **(a)** the distance between the MAHLI camera and an imaged target, and **(b)** the scale of in-focus features in the image, based on knowledge of that distance. Usually, these are determined using the camera’s stepper motor count focus position (Edgett *et al.* 2015).

These information sheets were created only for cases in which there was a need. Cases for which they are not usually created include those when the only MAHLI image(s) acquired on a given sol are **(a)** views of the landscape, focused at infinity; **(b)** intended to make a rover self-portrait mosaic; **(c)** sky flat field calibration data; or **(d)** routinely-acquired images of the rover wheels for inspection purposes.

For the Sol 3548–3644 period, *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were created for the following **Sols: 3551, 3553, 3555, 3558, 3560, 3562, 3564, 3566, 3568, 3571, 3573, 3575, 3578, 3583, 3592, 3594, 3596, 3599, 3601, 3603, 3605, 3607, 3609, 3612, 3624, 3626, 3628, 3630, 3633, 3635, 3637, 3639, 3641, 3644.**

The origin of the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was in the need for a rapid, tactical response from the MAHLI team to the Curiosity Rover Planners—the engineers tasked with operating the rover’s mobility and robotic arm systems—for range-finding and image scale information derived from MAHLI’s autofocus and focus merge capabilities. As described by Minitti *et al.* (2013), during the rover’s first sample extraction campaign, conducted at the Rocknest eolian sand deposit in October–November 2012, the engineers elected to use MAHLI autofocus sub-frames to confirm their estimates of the range to the sand surface for subsequent scoop placement (Anderson *et al.* 2015). These *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were borne of that effort to provide the information almost as soon as the data arrived on Earth.

Presented in this section are the latest versions of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, for the above stated sols, as of the date of this *MAHLI Technical Report* publication. Most of these sheets were actively used during the MSL mission for tactical and strategic planning, as well as for the scientific analyses. Note that some of the sheets exhibit slightly different formatting from each other, as the formatting and content evolved over time.

The image IDs presented in these Information Sheets are the identifiers of the best, least-compressed version of the image received from Mars for a given camera position for the stated purpose (autofocus, imaging, range-finding, etc.). In cases for which only a thumbnail version of the image was received, the image ID is colored orange.

4.2 Formulae

4.2.1 Working distance

The working distance (d_w , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was computed from the empirical relationship between working distance and motor count for the flight unit MAHLI when the dust cover is open (m_{open}) described by Edgett *et al.* (2015):

$$d_w = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For the dust cover closed case (m_{closed}), Edgett *et al.* (2015) found that m_{closed} is related to m_{open} as follows:

$$m_{closed} = 17075 - m_{open}. \quad (2)$$

4.2.2 Standoff distance (RP distance; MAHLI toolframe +X distance)

The standoff distance (d_s , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* is 1.9 cm less than the MAHLI working distance (Edgett *et al.* 2015). Note that “standoff distance” is equivalent to “RP distance” and “MAHLI toolframe +X distance”; see **Section 7.1**). It is determined by subtracting 1.9 cm from the working distance (d_w) computed from motor count:

$$d_s = d_w - 1.9 \text{ cm} \quad (3)$$

4.2.3 Distance or range uncertainty estimate

Estimation approach applied to the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

For the Sol 0–945 period (except Sol 687), the uncertainty in distance (whether expressed as d_w or d_s) was estimated using an early version of our team’s understanding (Edgett *et al.* 2013) of the flight unit MAHLI depth of field (DOF; d_{old_DOF} , in centimeters) as a function of working distance (d_w).

The method for estimating the far range of the DOF, d_{old_far} , was:

$$d_{old_far} = ad_w^5 - bd_w^4 + cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 + ed_w - f \quad (4)$$

in which $a = 2.067963396 \times 10^{-10}$, $b = 5.81503025785 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 1.55563715379086 \times 10^{-5}$, $d = 1.78558768966003 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 7.87243271888297 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 3.57047935299353 \times 10^{-2}$.

The method for estimating the near range of the DOF, d_{old_near} , was:

$$d_{old_near} = -(ad_w^5 + bd_w^4 - cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 - ed_w + f) \quad (5)$$

in which $a = -9.6497783 \times 10^{-12}$, $b = 1.06050131902 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 5.8615047292452 \times 10^{-6}$, $d = 2.42284468424977 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 4.28714139095939 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 7.534391000189 \times 10^{-4}$.

The MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* added the absolute values of the near and far DOF, then divided by two, to provide an overall uncertainty, $\pm d_{old_DOF}$, in centimeters:

$$\pm d_{old_DOF} = ((-d_{old_near}) + d_{old_far})/2 \quad (6)$$

The $\pm d_{old_DOF}$ estimate was sufficient for using MAHLI as a range finder for subsequent scoop placement during the Rocknest sample extraction campaign (Minitti *et al.* 2013; Anderson *et al.* 2015).

Improved estimation method, used for Sol 687 and after Sol 945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

Later analysis refined our DOF estimate (Edgett *et al.* 2015), but these results arrived too late to be incorporated into most of the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*. That said, for small working distances (e.g., < 20 cm), the results are about the same. As a function of dust cover open focus motor count (m_{open}), the near (d_{near}) and far (d_{far}) depth of field can be expressed, in centimeters, as:

$$d_{near} \text{ or } d_{far} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (7)$$

in which, for d_{near} , $a = 1.03565$, $b = -11.9083$, $c = 2.82403 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.29003 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.34332 \times 10^{-12}$; and, for d_{far} , $a = 1.03438$, $b = -11.4118$, $c = 2.69297 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.17752 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.02494 \times 10^{-12}$.

4.2.4 Pixel scale

The estimated pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel) is based on working distance (d_w) and applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. We estimate the scale from the working distance (d_w) as described by Edgett *et al.* (2012):

$$p = 6.9001 + 3.5201d_w. \quad (8)$$

4.2.5 Pixel scale uncertainty estimate

No estimation applied to the Sol 0–998 range and scale information sheets

No estimate of pixel scale uncertainty was applied to the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* until Sol 999.

Estimation approach

Pixel scale uncertainty (p_{far} , p_{near} , $\pm p_{uncertainty}$, in μm per pixel) can be estimated based on the depth of field (d_{far} , d_{near} , in centimeters; **Equation 7**) and pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel, **Equation 8**) as determined from working distance (d_w , in centimeters; **Equation 1**). The uncertainty applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. The uncertainty can be estimated as follows (please round $\pm p_{uncertainty}$ to the nearest 0.1 μm per pixel):

$$p_{far} = (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{far})) - p, \quad (9)$$

$$p_{near} = p - (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{near})), \text{ and} \quad (10)$$

$$\pm p_{uncertainty} = (p_{far} + p_{near})/2. \quad (11)$$

4.2.6 Image dimensions estimate

The image dimension estimates described in the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* are computed by multiplying the estimated pixel scale (p) by the number of horizontal (columns) and vertical (rows) covered by the image. This simplistic approach, of course, assumes that the target is a plane parallel to the CCD.

last update: 03_August_2022

Sol 3551 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Karisparo - a 3 x 1 mosaic from 5 cm standoff													
mhl00359	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3551MH0003590011204537C00	4537	13031	25.7	23.8	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	1608	1198	15.7	11.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3551MH0001530001204582R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3551MH0001530001204583S00					
mhl00363	position 1 of 3		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3551MH0003630011204547C00	4547	14170	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3551MH0001530001204580R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3551MH0001530001204581S00					
mhl00363	position 2 of 3		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3551MH0003630011204557C00	4557	14170	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3551MH0001530001204578R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3551MH0001530001204579S00					
mhl00363	position 3 of 3		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3551MH0003630011204567C00	4567	14119	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3551MH0001530001204576R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3551MH0001530001204577S00					

Sol 3553 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Arorouta

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3553MH0001900011204585C00	4585	13036	25.4	23.5	-1.6	1.8	96.3	6.1	1608	1198	15.5	11.5	
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3553MH0001820011204587C00	4587	14225	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3553MH0001530001204632R00				range map product:					3553MH0001530001204633S00
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3553MH0001820011204597C00	4597	14227	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3553MH0001530001204630R00				range map product:					3553MH0001530001204631S00

target named Yakontipu - a 2 x 1 mosaic

mhl00854	position 1 of 2	intended standoff - 20 cm												
	3553MH0008540011204607C00	4607	13117	21.5	19.6	-1.2	1.3	82.5	4.4	1608	1198	13.3	9.9	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3553MH0001530001204628R00				range map product:					3553MH0001530001204629S00
mhl00854	position 2 of 2	intended standoff - 20 cm												
	3553MH0008540011204617C00	4617	13076	23.3	21.4	-1.4	1.5	89.0	5.1	1608	1198	14.3	10.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3553MH0001530001204626R00				range map product:					3553MH0001530001204627S00

Sol 3555 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Sloth_Island

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3555MH0001900011204635C00	4635	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1	
mhli00299	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3555MH0002990011204637C00	4637	14032	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3556MH0002270001004696R00				range map product:					3556MH0002270001004697S00
mhli00299	medium-r resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3555MH0002990011204647C00	4647	14029	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3556MH0002270001004694R00				range map product:					3556MH0002270001004695S00
mhli00335	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm												
	3555MH0003350011204657C00	4657	14756	3.6	1.7	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.2	1608	1198	3.2	2.4	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3556MH0002270001104692R00				range map product:					3556MH0002270001104693S00

target named Aponguao

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3555MH0001900011104667C00	4667	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhli00182	medium-r resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3555MH0001820011104669C00	4669	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3556MH0002270001104690R00				range map product:					3556MH0002270001104691S00
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3555MH0001820011104679C00	4679	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3556MH0002270001104688R00				range map product:					3556MH0002270001104689S00

Sol 3558 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Sao_Marcos

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3558MH0001900011004699C00	4699	13042	25.1	23.2	-1.6	1.8	95.2	5.9	1608	1198	15.3	11.4	
mhli00308	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3558MH0003080011004701C00	4701	14328	5.1	3.2	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	1608	1198	4.0	3.0	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3558MH0001710000704785R00				range map product:					3558MH0001710000704786S00
mhli00308	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3558MH0003080011004711C00	4711	14370	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3558MH0001710000704783R00				range map product:					3558MH0001710000704784S00

target named Essequibo

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3558MH0001900011004721C00	4721	13040	25.2	23.3	-1.6	1.8	95.6	6.0	1608	1198	15.4	11.4	
mhli00673	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3558MH0006730011004723C00	4723	14431	4.7	2.8	-0.1	0.1	23.4	0.3	1608	1198	3.8	2.8	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3558MH0001710000704781R00				range map product:					3558MH0001710000704782S00
mhli00673	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3558MH0006730011004733C00	4733	14441	4.6	2.7	-0.1	0.1	23.2	0.3	1608	1198	3.7	2.8	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3558MH0001710000704779R00				range map product:					3558MH0001710000704780S00

target named Kumu_Falls

mhli00678	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3558MH0006780010804743C00	4743	13037	25.4	23.5	-1.6	1.8	96.2	6.1	1608	1198	15.5	11.5		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3558MH0001710000704777R00				range map product:					3558MH0001710000704778S00	
mhli00166	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3558MH0001660010804754C00	4754	14292	5.3	3.4	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	1608	1198	4.1	3.0		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3558MH0001710000704775R00				range map product:					3558MH0001710000704776S00	
mhli00166	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3558MH0001660010704764C00	4764	14303	5.2	3.3	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	1608	1198	4.1	3.0		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3558MH0001710000704773R00				range map product:					3558MH0001710000704774S00	

Sol 3560 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Annai** - after DRT

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3560MH0007060010704788C00	4788	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhli00763	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3560MH0007630010704791C00	4791	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3560MH0002270000504853R00					range map product:							3560MH0002270000504854S00
mhli00763	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3560MH0007630010704802C00	4802	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3560MH0002270000504851R00					range map product:							3560MH0002270000504852S00
mhli00835	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm													
	3560MH0008350010704813C00	4813	15124	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3560MH0002270000604849R00					range map product:							3560MH0002270000504850S00

target named **Mirizal**

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3560MH0001900010704824C00	4824	13031	25.7	23.8	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	1608	1198	15.7	11.7		
mhli00224	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3560MH0002240010704826C00	4826	14138	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.4		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3560MH0002270000604847R00					range map product:							3560MH0002270000604848S00
mhli00224	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3560MH0002240010604836C00	4836	14141	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.4		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3560MH0002270000604845R00					range map product:							3560MH0002270000604846S00

Sol 3562 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named El_Silencio															
mhli00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3562MH0007060011300027C00	2	13032	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6		
mhli00721	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3562MH0007210011300005C00	5	14181	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3562MH0007070001300057R00				range map product:					3562MH0007070001300058S00
mhli00721	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3562MH0007210011300016C00	16	14183	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3562MH0007070001300055R00				range map product:					3562MH0007070001300056S00

target named Orinduik															
mhli00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3562MH0007060011300027C00	27	13035	25.5	23.6	-1.6	1.8	96.5	6.1	1608	1198	15.5	11.6		
mhli00763	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3562MH0007630011300030C00	30	14203	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3562MH0007070001300053R00				range map product:					3562MH0007070001300054S00
mhli00763	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3562MH0007630011300041C00	41	14205	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3562MH0007070001300051R00				range map product:					3562MH0007070001300052S00

Sol 3564 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Sand_Creek															
mhli00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3564MH000706001130006C00	60	13033	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	96.9	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6		
mhli00714	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3564MH0007140011300063C00	63	14229	5.5	3.6	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3564MH0008060001300111R00				range map product:					3564MH0008060001300112S00	

target named Nascente															
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3564MH0001900011300074C00	74	13001	27.5	25.6	-1.9	2.2	103.8	7.2	1608	1198	16.7	12.4		
mhli00299	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3564MH0002990011300076C00	76	13908	7.5	5.6	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	4.0		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3564MH0008060001300109R00				range map product:					3564MH0008060001300110S00	
mhli00299	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3564MH0002990011300086C00	86	13913	7.5	5.6	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	4.0		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3564MH0008060001300107R00				range map product:					3564MH0008060001300108S00	
mhli00337	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm												
	3564MH0003370011300096C00	96	14477	4.5	2.6	-0.1	0.1	22.8	0.3	1608	1198	3.7	2.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3564MH0008060001300105R00				range map product:					3564MH0008060001300106S00	

last update: 19_August_2022

Sol 3566 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

REMS UV sensor

mhli00095	standard viewing position	intended standoff: ~15 cm											
	3566MH0000950011300114C00	114	13264	16.6	14.7	-0.7	0.8	65.3	2.6	1608	1198	10.5	7.8

target named *Yupukari*

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3566MH0007060011300116C00	116	13040	25.2	23.3	-1.6	1.8	95.6	6.0	1608	1198	15.4	11.4		
mhli00709	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3566MH0007090011300119C00	119	14252	5.4	3.5	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.1		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3567MH0007030001300142R00				range map product:						3567MH0007030001300143S00	
mhli00709	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3566MH0007090011300130C00	130	14254	5.4	3.5	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.1		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3567MH0007030001300140R00				range map product:						3567MH0007030001300141S00	

Sol 3568 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

*Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

MAHLI calibration target

Note: one can also use features in these images to determine scale; the scale information presented here is based on motor count, not analysis of the images.

mhli00371	bar target - 5 cm working distance												
	3568MH0003710011300145C00	145	14383	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.0	0.3	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
mhli00372	cent target - 5 cm working distance												
	3568MH0003720011300147C00	147	14377	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.1	0.3	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
mhli00374	calibration target + front left wheel + surface - 30 cm working distance												
	autofocus on calibration target												
	3568MH0003740011300149C00	149	12965	30.1	28.2	-2.3	2.6	112.7	8.6	1608	1198	18.1	13.5
	manual infinity focus												
	3568MH0003740021300150C00	150	12552	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	1608	1198	(infinity)	(infinity)

APXS calibration target

Note: one can also use features in the image(s) to determine scale; the scale information presented here is based on motor count, not analysis of the image(s).

mhli00373	6.9 cm working distance												
	3568MH0003730011300152C00	152	13955	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.8

target named Fortaleza

mhli00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3568MH0007060011300154C00	154	13034	25.5	23.6	-1.6	1.8	96.7	6.1	1608	1198	15.6	11.6
mhli00714	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3568MH0007140011300157C00	157	14223	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3570MH0002270001300222R00		range map product:		3570MH0002270001300223S00			
mhli00714	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3568MH0007140011300168C00	168	14240	5.5	3.6	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.1
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3570MH0002270001300220R00		range map product:		3570MH0002270001300221S00			

target named Massara - after DRT

mhli00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3568MH0007060011300179C00	179	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00834	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3568MH0008340011300182C00	182	13969	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3570MH0002270001300218R00		range map product:		3570MH0002270001300219S00			
mhli00834	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3568MH0008340011300193C00	193	13959	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3570MH0002270001300216R00		range map product:		3570MH0002270001300217S00			
mhli00785	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm										
	3568MH0007850011300204C00	204	14987	3.1	1.2	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3570MH0002270001300214R00		range map product:		3570MH0002270001300215S00			

last update: 24_August_2022

Sol 3571 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Raimundo													
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3571MH0001900011300225C00	225	13012	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.3	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1
mhl00224	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3571MH0002240011300227C00	227	13966	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3571MH0001930001300260R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3571MH0001930001300261S00						
mhl00224	medium-r resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3571MH0002240011300237C00	237	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3571MH0001930001300258R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3571MH0001930001300259S00						
mhl00307	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm										
	3571MH0003070011300247C00	247	14629	4.0	2.1	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3571MH0001930001300256R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3571MH0001930001300257S00						

Sol 3573 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Kanuku - quantitative relief model (QRM) data

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3573MH0001900011300263C00	263	13005	27.3	25.4	-1.9	2.1	102.9	7.0	1608	1198	16.5	12.3		
mhli00297	med res - stereo-1 & relief model position 1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3573MH0002970011300265C00	265	13808	8.3	6.4	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	1608	1198	5.8	4.3		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3574MH0002270001300330R00				range map product:					3574MH0002270001300331S00	
mhli00297	med res - stereo-2 & relief model position 2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3573MH0002970011300275C00	275	13810	8.3	6.4	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	1608	1198	5.8	4.3		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3574MH0002270001300328R00				range map product:					3574MH0002270001300329S00	
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 3	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3573MH0007050011300285C00	285	13797	8.4	6.5	-0.2	0.2	36.5	0.8	1608	1198	5.9	4.4		
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 4	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3573MH0007050011300287C00	287	13811	8.3	6.4	-0.2	0.2	36.0	0.8	1608	1198	5.8	4.3		
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 5	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3573MH0007050011300289C00	289	13813	8.3	6.4	-0.2	0.2	36.0	0.7	1608	1198	5.8	4.3		
mhli00311	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm													
	3573MH0003110011300291C00	291	14266	5.4	3.5	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.1		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3574MH0002270001300326R00				range map product:					3574MH0002270001300327S00	

target named Wadakapiapue

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3573MH0001900011300301C00	301	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1	
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3573MH0001820011300303C00	303	13955	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.8	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3574MH0002270001300324R00				range map product:					3574MH0002270001300325S00
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3573MH0001820011300313C00	313	13964	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3574MH0002270001300322R00				range map product:					3574MH0002270001300323S00

Sol 3575 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Los_Rosos

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3575MH0001900011300333C00	333	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 1														
	3575MH0001730011300335C00	335	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3575MH0001700001300432R00				range map product:						3575MH0001700001300433S00	
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 1														
	3575MH0001730011300345C00	345	14001	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3575MH0001700001300430R00				range map product:						3575MH0001700001300431S00	
mhl00173	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3575MH0001730011300355C00	355	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3575MH0001700001300428R00				range map product:						3575MH0001700001300429S00	

target named Nova_Estrela

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3575MH0001900011300365C00	365	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3575MH0001730011300367C00	367	14014	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3575MH0001700001300426R00				range map product:						3575MH0001700001300427S00
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3575MH0001730011300377C00	377	14016	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3575MH0001700001300424R00				range map product:						3575MH0001700001300425S00
mhl00302	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm													
	3575MH0003020011300387C00	387	14720	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	1608	1198	3.2	2.4		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3575MH0001700001300422R00				range map product:						3575MH0001700001300423S00

target named Enamuna

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3575MH0001900011300397C00	397	13040	25.2	23.3	-1.6	1.8	95.6	6.0	1608	1198	15.4	11.4		
mhl00306	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3575MH0003060011300399C00	399	14252	5.4	3.5	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.1		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3575MH0001700001300420R00				range map product:						3575MH0001700001300421S00
mhl00306	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3575MH0003060011300409C00	409	14277	5.3	3.4	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.1	3.1		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3575MH0001700001300418R00				range map product:						3575MH0001700001300419S00

Sol 3578 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Jacamim

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3578MH0001900011300435C00	435	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhli00168	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3578MH0001680011300437C00	437	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3578MH0001710001300525R00				range map product:					3578MH0001710001300526S00
mhli00168	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3578MH0001680011300447C00	447	14013	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3578MH0001710001300523R00				range map product:					3578MH0001710001300524S00
mhli00426	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm												
	3578MH0004260011300457C00	457	15139	2.8	0.9	0.0	0.1	16.6	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3578MH0001710001300521R00				range map product:					3578MH0001710001300522S00

target named Micobie - after DRT

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3578MH0007060011300467C00	467	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhli00834	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3578MH0008340011300470C00	470	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3578MH0001710001300519R00				range map product:					3578MH0001710001300520S00	
mhli00834	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3578MH0008340011300481C00	481	14026	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3578MH0001710001300517R00				range map product:					3578MH0001710001300518S00	
mhli00835	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3578MH0008350011300492C00	492	15161	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.5	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3578MH0001710001300515R00				range map product:					3578MH0001710001300516S00	
mhli00834	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 1														
	3578MH0008340011300503C00	503	14012	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3578MH0001710001300513R00				range map product:					3578MH0001710001300514S00	

Sol 3583 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
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 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Marie_Island

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
context view		intended standoff - 25 cm											
mhli00855	3583MH0008550011300528C00	528	13006	27.2	25.3	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	1608	1198	16.5	12.3
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3590MH0002270001300589R00				<i>range map product:</i>		3590MH0002270001300590S00			

target named Branco

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
context view		intended standoff - 25 cm											
mhli00190	3583MH0001900011300538C00	538	13012	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.3	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1
medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm											
mhli00306	3583MH0003060011300540C00	540	13959	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3590MH0002270001300587R00				<i>range map product:</i>		3590MH0002270001300588S00			
medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm											
mhli00306	3583MH0003060011300550C00	550	13978	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3590MH0002270001300585R00				<i>range map product:</i>		3590MH0002270001300586S00			

target named Machado

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
context view		intended standoff - 25 cm											
mhli00190	3583MH0001900011300560C00	560	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0
medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm											
mhli00299	3583MH0002990011300562C00	562	13991	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3590MH0002270001300583R00				<i>range map product:</i>		3590MH0002270001300584S00			
medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm											
mhli00299	3583MH0002990011300572C00	572	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3590MH0002270001300581R00				<i>range map product:</i>		3590MH0002270001300582S00			

last update: 14_September_2022

Sol 3592 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

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 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Piabas													
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3592MH0001900011300592C00	592	13023	26.2	24.3	-1.7	1.9	99.0	6.5	1608	1198	15.9	11.9
mhl00363	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3592MH0003630011300594C00	594	14115	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3592MH0002650001300615R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3592MH0002650001300616S00							
mhl00363	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3592MH0003630011300604C00	604	14410	4.8	2.9	-0.1	0.1	23.7	0.3	1608	1198	3.8	2.8
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3592MH0002650001300613R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3592MH0002650001300614S00							

Sol 3594 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Tiger_Pond

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3594MH0001900011300618C00	618	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhli00673	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3594MH0006730011300620C00	620	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3594MH0002270001300677R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3594MH0002270001300678S00								
mhli00673	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3594MH0006730011300630C00	630	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3594MH0002270001300675R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3594MH0002270001300676S00								

target named La_Mata

mhli00291	intermediate view	intended standoff - 10 cm											
	3594MH0002910011300640C00	640	13547	11.2	9.3	-0.4	0.4	46.2	1.3	1608	1198	7.4	5.5
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3594MH0002270001300673R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3594MH0002270001300674S00								
mhli00308	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3594MH0003080011300650C00	650	14123	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3594MH0002270001300671R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3594MH0002270001300672S00								
mhli00308	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3594MH0003080011300660C00	660	14142	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.4
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3594MH0002270001300669R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3594MH0002270001300670S00								

Sol 3596 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Marshall_Falls - before DRT													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3596MH0001900011300680C00	680	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhli00122	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3596MH0001220011300682C00	682	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7

target named Corona_Falls - after DRT													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3596MH0001900011300684C00	684	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00224	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3596MH0002240011300686C00	686	14024	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3596MH0001630001300761R00				<i>range map product:</i>				3596MH0001630001300762S00
mhli00224	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3596MH0002240011300696C00	696	14028	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3596MH0001630001300759R00				<i>range map product:</i>				3596MH0001630001300760S00
mhli00307	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm										
	3596MH0003070011300706C00	706	14738	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.2	1608	1198	3.2	2.4
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3596MH0001630001300757R00				<i>range map product:</i>				3596MH0001630001300758S00

target named Marshall_Falls - after DRT													
mhli00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3596MH0007060011300716C00	716	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3596MH0006990011300719C00	719	14027	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3596MH0001630001300755R00				<i>range map product:</i>				3596MH0001630001300756S00
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3596MH0006990011300730C00	730	14030	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3596MH0001630001300753R00				<i>range map product:</i>				3596MH0001630001300754S00
mhli00823	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm										
	3596MH0008230011300741C00	741	15178	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.4	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3596MH0001630001300751R00				<i>range map product:</i>				3596MH0001630001300752S00

Sol 3599 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **El_Triunfo**

mhli00855	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3599MH0008550011300764C00	764	13026	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	1608	1198	15.8	11.8
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3599MH0005360001300873R00				range map product:				3599MH0005360001300874S00	
mhli00291	intermediate-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 10 cm											
	3599MH0002910011300774C00	774	13556	11.0	9.1	-0.4	0.3	45.8	1.2	1608	1198	7.4	5.5
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3599MH0005360001300871R00				range map product:				3599MH0005360001300872S00	
mhli00291	intermediate-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 10 cm											
	3599MH0002910011300784C00	784	13571	10.8	8.9	-0.3	0.3	45.1	1.2	1608	1198	7.2	5.4
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3599MH0005360001300869R00				range map product:				3599MH0005360001300870S00	

target named **Nova_Cintra**

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3599MH0001900011300794C00	794	13013	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1
mhli00173	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3599MH0001730011300796C00	796	13973	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3599MH0005360001300867R00				range map product:				3599MH0005360001300868S00	
mhli00173	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3599MH0001730011300806C00	806	13965	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3599MH0005360001300865R00				range map product:				3599MH0005360001300866S00	
mhli00337	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm											
	3599MH0003370011300816C00	816	14639	4.0	2.1	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3599MH0005360001300863R00				range map product:				3599MH0005360001300864S00	

target named **Pirara**

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3599MH0001900011300826C00	826	12999	27.7	25.8	-1.9	2.2	104.3	7.2	1608	1198	16.8	12.5
mhli00299	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3599MH0002990011300828C00	828	13831	8.1	6.2	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	1608	1198	5.7	4.2
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3599MH0005360001300861R00				range map product:				3599MH0005360001300862S00	
mhli00299	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3599MH0002990011300838C00	838	13831	8.1	6.2	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	1608	1198	5.7	4.2
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3599MH0005360001300859R00				range map product:				3599MH0005360001300860S00	
mhli00337	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm											
	3599MH0003370011300848C00	848	14344	5.0	3.1	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.0	2.9
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3599MH0005360001300857R00				range map product:				3599MH0005360001300858S00	

last update: 23_September_2022

Sol 3601 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Cuarane - after DRT													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3601MH0001900011300876C00	876	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3601MH0001820011300878C00	878	13990	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3601MH0001930001300911R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3601MH0001930001300912S00				
mhli00182	medium-r resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3601MH0001820011300888C00	888	13991	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3601MH0001930001300909R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3601MH0001930001300910S00				
mhli00838	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm										
	3601MH0008380011300898C00	898	15072	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3601MH0001930001300907R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3601MH0001930001300908S00				

Sol 3603 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Tapirapeco													
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3603MH0001900011300914C00	914	13034	25.5	23.6	-1.6	1.8	96.7	6.1	1608	1198	15.6	11.6
mhl00224	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3603MH0002240011300916C00	916	14232	5.5	3.6	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.2
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 3603MH0001630001300989R00				range map product: 3603MH0001630001300990S00						
mhl00224	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3603MH0002240011300926C00	926	14236	5.5	3.6	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.2
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 3603MH0001630001300987R00				range map product: 3603MH0001630001300988S00						

target named Lagoa_do_Velame													
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3603MH0001900011300936C00	936	13030	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7
mhl00168	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3603MH0001680011300938C00	938	14164	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 3603MH0001630001300985R00				range map product: 3603MH0001630001300986S00						
mhl00168	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3603MH0001680011300948C00	948	14166	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 3603MH0001630001300983R00				range map product: 3603MH0001630001300984S00						

target named Lagoa_do_Macaco													
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3603MH0001900011300958C00	958	13032	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6
mhl00168	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3603MH0001680011300960C00	960	14186	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 3603MH0001630001300981R00				range map product: 3603MH0001630001300982S00						
mhl00168	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3603MH0001680011300970C00	970	14193	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.2
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 3603MH0001630001300979R00				range map product: 3603MH0001630001300980S00						

last update: 28_September_2022

Sol 3605 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
target named Tapirapeco - a 6 x 1 mosaic													
mhl00841	position 1 of 6	intended standoff - 16 cm											
	3605MH0008410011300992C00	992	13245	17.1	15.2	-0.8	0.8	67.1	2.8	1608	1198	10.8	8.0
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		<i>range map product:</i>				3605MH0001630001301061R00					
mhl00841	position 2 of 6	intended standoff - 16 cm											
	3605MH0008410011301002C00	1002	13242	17.2	15.3	-0.8	0.8	67.4	2.8	1608	1198	10.8	8.1
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		<i>range map product:</i>				3605MH0001630001301059R00					
mhl00841	position 3 of 6	intended standoff - 16 cm											
	3605MH0008410011301012C00	1012	13221	17.8	15.9	-0.8	0.9	69.6	3.0	1608	1198	11.2	8.3
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		<i>range map product:</i>				3605MH0001630001301057R00					
mhl00841	position 4 of 6	intended standoff - 16 cm											
	3605MH0008410011301022C00	1022	13213	18.1	16.2	-0.9	0.9	70.4	3.1	1608	1198	11.3	8.4
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		<i>range map product:</i>				3605MH0001630001301055R00					
mhl00841	position 5 of 6	intended standoff - 16 cm											
	3605MH0008410011301032C00	1032	13218	17.9	16.0	-0.8	0.9	69.9	3.0	1608	1198	11.2	8.4
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		<i>range map product:</i>				3605MH0001630001301053R00					
mhl00841	position 6 of 6	intended standoff - 16 cm											
	3605MH0008410011301042C00	1042	13228	17.6	15.7	-0.8	0.9	68.9	2.9	1608	1198	11.1	8.2
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		<i>range map product:</i>				3605MH0001630001301051R00					

last update: 29_September_2022

Sol 3607 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named El_Pao_De_La_Fortuna

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3607MH0001900011301064C00	1064	13029	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.8	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7
mhli00148	intermediate-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 10 cm											
	3607MH0001480011301066C00	1066	13556	11.0	9.1	-0.4	0.3	45.8	1.2	1608	1198	7.4	5.5
mhli00148	intermediate-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 10 cm											
	3607MH0001480011301068C00	1068	13556	11.0	9.1	-0.4	0.3	45.8	1.2	1608	1198	7.4	5.5

target named Espirito_Santo

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3607MH0001900011301070C00	1070	13027	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.2	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.8
mhli00148	intermediate-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 10 cm											
	3607MH0001480011301072C00	1072	13549	11.1	9.2	-0.4	0.3	46.1	1.2	1608	1198	7.4	5.5
mhli00148	intermediate-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 10 cm											
	3607MH0001480011301074C00	1074	13550	11.1	9.2	-0.4	0.3	46.1	1.2	1608	1198	7.4	5.5

Sol 3609 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

intended drill target named **Canaima** - before DRT

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3609MH0001900011301076C00	1076	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00122	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3609MH0001220011301078C00	1078	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7

intended drill target named **Canaima** - after DRT

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3609MH0001900011301080C00	1080	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhli00173	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3609MH0001730011301082C00	1082	14007	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3609MH0001530001301129R00				range map product:						3609MH0001530001301130S00	
mhli00173	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3609MH0001730011301092C00	1092	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3609MH0001530001301127R00				range map product:						3609MH0001530001301128S00	
mhli00649	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3609MH0006490011301102C00	1102	15131	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3609MH0001530001301125R00				range map product:						3609MH0001530001301126S00	
mhli00173	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 1														
	3609MH0001730011301112C00	1112	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3609MH0001530001301123R00				range map product:						3609MH0001530001301124S00	

intended drill target named **Canaima** - after drill bit pre-load test

mhli00465	context view	intended standoff - 35 cm											
	3609MH0004650011301122C00	1122	12895	36.5	34.6	-3.3	3.9	135.3	12.7	1608	1198	21.8	16.2

last update: 04_October_2022

Sol 3612 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information*

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

intended sample discard site for planned Canaima drill sample

context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
mhi00190	3612MH0001900011301132C00	1132	13012	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.3	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1

last update: 17_October_2022

Sol 3624 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

Canaima drill hole

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00197	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3624MH0001970011301134C00	1134	13025	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.6	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8
mhli00774	intermediate-resolution view		intended standoff - 10 cm										
	3624MH0007740011301136C00	1136	13575	10.8	8.9	-0.3	0.3	44.9	1.2	1608	1198	7.2	5.4

Canaima drill hole cuttings

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00152	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3624MH0001520011301138C00	1138	14218	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>				<i>best focus product:</i>		3624MH0002580001301147R00		<i>range map product:</i>		3624MH0002580001301148S00			

last update: 19_October_2022

Sol 3626 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Bacabal

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3626MH0001900011301150C00	1150	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3626MH0001730011301152C00	1152	14046	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3626MH0002650001301175R00				<i>range map product:</i>		3626MH0002650001301176S00				
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3626MH0001730011301162C00	1162	14048	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3626MH0002650001301173R00				<i>range map product:</i>		3626MH0002650001301174S00				

Canaima drill hole cuttings

mhl00122	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3626MH0001220011301172C00	1172	13947	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9

last update: 21_October_2022

Sol 3628 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Pacu													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3628MH0001900011301178C00	1178	13013	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1
mhli00168	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3628MH0001680011301180C00	1180	13954	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.8
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3628MH0001930001301213R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3628MH0001930001301214S00				
mhli00168	medium-r resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3628MH0001680011301190C00	1190	13961	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3628MH0001930001301211R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3628MH0001930001301212S00				
mhli00386	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm										
	3628MH0003860011301200C00	1200	14963	3.1	1.2	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.1
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3628MH0001930001301209R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3628MH0001930001301210S00				

Sol 3630 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Vista_Alegre

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3630MH0001900011301216C00	1216	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3630MH0001820011301218C00	1218	14011	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3631MH0001530001301265R00					<i>range map product:</i> 3631MH0001530001301266S00					
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3630MH0001820011301228C00	1228	14015	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3631MH0001530001301263R00					<i>range map product:</i> 3631MH0001530001301264S00					

target named Santa_Silvia

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3630MH0001900011301238C00	1238	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3630MH0001820011301240C00	1240	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3631MH0001530001301261R00					<i>range map product:</i> 3631MH0001530001301262S00					
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3630MH0001820011301250C00	1250	14015	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3631MH0001530001301259R00					<i>range map product:</i> 3631MH0001530001301260S00					

last update: 31_October_2022

Sol 3633 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Balata

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3633MH0001900011301268C00	1268	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00168	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3633MH0001680011301270C00	1270	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3633MH0002650001301291R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3633MH0002650001301292S00						
mhli00168	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3633MH0001680011301280C00	1280	14008	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3633MH0002650001301289R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3633MH0002650001301290S00						

REMS UV sensor

mhli00095	standard viewing position	intended standoff: ~15 cm											
	3633MH0000950011301294C00	1294	13264	16.6	14.7	-0.7	0.8	65.3	2.6	1608	1198	10.5	7.8

Sol 3635 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Mau**

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3635MH0001900011301296C00	1296	13011	26.9	25.0	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.2	
mhli00299	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3635MH0002990011301298C00	1298	13990	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3635MH0001930001301335R00				range map product:							3635MH0001930001301336S00
mhli00299	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3635MH0002990011301308C00	1308	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3635MH0001930001301333R00				range map product:							3635MH0001930001301334S00

target named **Univini**

mhli00814	context view	intended standoff - 15 cm												
	3635MH0008140011301318C00	1318	13278	16.2	14.3	-0.7	0.7	64.0	2.5	1608	1198	10.3	7.7	
mhli00699	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3635MH0006990011301321C00	1321	14094	6.3	4.4	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3635MH0001930001301331R00				range map product:							3635MH0001930001301332S00

Sol 3637 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Catrimani - after DRT**

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3637MH0001900011301338C00	1338	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1	
mhli00173	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3637MH0001730011301340C00	1340	13969	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3637MH0002270001301402R00				range map product:					3637MH0002270001301403S00
mhli00173	medium-r resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3637MH0001730011301350C00	1350	13970	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3637MH0002270001301400R00				range map product:					3637MH0002270001301401S00
mhli00716	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm												
	3637MH0007160011301360C00	1360	14980	3.1	1.2	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.1	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3637MH0002270001301398R00				range map product:					3637MH0002270001301399S00

target named **Marari**

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3637MH0007060011301370C00	1370	13046	24.9	23.0	-1.6	1.7	94.4	5.8	1608	1198	15.2	11.3	
mhli00721	medium-r resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3637MH0007210011301373C00	1373	14323	5.1	3.2	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	1608	1198	4.0	3.0	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3637MH0002270001301396R00				range map product:					3637MH0002270001301397S00
mhli00721	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3637MH0007210011301384C00	1384	14301	5.2	3.3	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.1	3.0	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3637MH0002270001301394R00				range map product:					3637MH0002270001301395S00

last update: 01_November_2022

Sol 3639 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Nicara													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3639MH0001900011301405C00	1405	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00173	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3639MH0001730011301407C00	1407	14034	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3639MH0001930001301440R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3639MH0001930001301441S00				
mhli00173	medium-r resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3639MH0001730011301417C00	1417	14034	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3639MH0001930001301438R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3639MH0001930001301439S00				
mhli00386	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm										
	3639MH0003860011301427C00	1427	15210	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3639MH0001930001301436R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3639MH0001930001301437S00				

Sol 3641 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Mel - before DRT													
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3641MH0001900011301443C00	1443	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0
mhl00122	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3641MH0001220011301445C00	1445	13957	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8

target named Mel - after DRT													
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3641MH0001900011301447C00	1447	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00308	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3641MH0003080011301449C00	1449	13965	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3642MH0003690001301568R00		range map product:		3642MH0003690001301569S00			
mhl00308	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3641MH0003080011301459C00	1459	13972	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3642MH0003690001301566R00		range map product:		3642MH0003690001301567S00			
mhl00428	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm										
	3641MH0004280011301469C00	1469	14587	4.1	2.2	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.6
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3642MH0003690001301564R00		range map product:		3642MH0003690001301565S00			

target named Mamupi - after DRT													
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3641MH0001900011301479C00	1479	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00224	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3641MH0002240011301481C00	1481	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3642MH0003690001301562R00		range map product:		3642MH0003690001301563S00			
mhl00224	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3641MH0002240011301491C00	1491	13982	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3642MH0003690001301560R00		range map product:		3642MH0003690001301561S00			
mhl00307	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm										
	3641MH0003070011301501C00	1501	14646	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3642MH0003690001301558R00		range map product:		3642MH0003690001301559S00			

target named Iracema													
mhl00855	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3641MH0008550011301511C00	1511	13013	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3642MH0003690001301566R00		range map product:		3642MH0003690001301557S00			
mhl00299	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3641MH0002990011301521C00	1521	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3642MH0003690001301554R00		range map product:		3642MH0003690001301555S00			
mhl00299	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3641MH0002990011301531C00	1531	14018	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3642MH0003690001301552R00		range map product:		3642MH0003690001301553S00			
mhl00649	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm										
	3641MH0006490011301541C00	1541	15119	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3642MH0003690001301550R00		range map product:		3642MH0003690001301551S00			

Sol 3644 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Mixiguana

mhl00855	context view stereo-1	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3644MH0008560011301571C00	1571	13041	25.1	23.2	-1.6	1.8	95.4	6.0	1608	1198	15.3	11.4
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3645MH0008570001301798R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3645MH0008570001301799S00					
mhl00855	context view stereo-2	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3644MH0008560011301581C00	1581	13032	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3645MH0008570001301796R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3645MH0008570001301797S00					

target named Mixiguana - a 6 x 2 mosaic

mhl00856	position 1 of 12	intended standoff - 15 cm											
	3644MH0008560011301591C00	1591	13373	14.1	12.2	-0.5	0.5	56.4	1.9	1608	1198	9.1	6.8
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3645MH0008570001301794R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3645MH0008570001301795S00					
mhl00856	position 2 of 12	intended standoff - 15 cm											
	3644MH0008560011301601C00	1601	13404	13.5	11.6	-0.5	0.5	54.3	1.8	1608	1198	8.7	6.5
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3645MH0008570001301792R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3645MH0008570001301793S00					
mhl00856	position 3 of 12	intended standoff - 15 cm											
	3644MH0008560011301611C00	1611	13327	15.1	13.2	-0.6	0.6	59.9	2.2	1608	1198	9.6	7.2
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3645MH0008570001301790R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3645MH0008570001301791S00					
mhl00856	position 4 of 12	intended standoff - 15 cm											
	3644MH0008560011301621C00	1621	13326	15.1	13.2	-0.6	0.6	60.0	2.2	1608	1198	9.6	7.2
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3645MH0008570001301788R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3645MH0008570001301789S00					
mhl00856	position 5 of 12	intended standoff - 15 cm											
	3644MH0008560011301631C00	1631	13345	14.7	12.8	-0.6	0.6	58.5	2.1	1608	1198	9.4	7.0
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3645MH0008570001301786R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3645MH0008570001301787S00					
mhl00856	position 6 of 12	intended standoff - 15 cm											
	3644MH0008560011301641C00	1641	13342	14.7	12.8	-0.6	0.6	58.7	2.1	1608	1198	9.4	7.0
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3645MH0008570001301784R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3645MH0008570001301785S00					
mhl00856	position 7 of 12	intended standoff - 15 cm											
	3644MH0008560011301651C00	1651	13313	15.4	13.5	-0.6	0.7	61.0	2.3	1608	1198	9.8	7.3
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3645MH0008570001301782R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3645MH0008570001301783S00					
mhl00856	position 8 of 12	intended standoff - 15 cm											
	3644MH0008560011301661C00	1661	13315	15.3	13.4	-0.6	0.6	60.9	2.3	1608	1198	9.8	7.3
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3645MH0008570001301780R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3645MH0008570001301781S00					
mhl00856	position 9 of 12	intended standoff - 15 cm											
	3644MH0008560011301671C00	1671	13343	14.7	12.8	-0.6	0.6	58.6	2.1	1608	1198	9.4	7.0
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3645MH0008570001301778R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3645MH0008570001301779S00					
mhl00856	position 10 of 12	intended standoff - 15 cm											
	3644MH0008560011301681C00	1681	13359	14.4	12.5	-0.6	0.6	57.4	2.0	1608	1198	9.2	6.9
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3645MH0008570001301776R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3645MH0008570001301777S00					
mhl00856	position 11 of 12	intended standoff - 15 cm											
	3644MH0008560011301691C00	1691	13349	14.6	12.7	-0.6	0.6	58.2	2.0	1608	1198	9.4	7.0
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3645MH0008570001301774R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3645MH0008570001301775S00					
mhl00856	position 12 of 12	intended standoff - 15 cm											
	3644MH0008560011301701C00	1701	13430	13.0	11.1	-0.5	0.5	52.7	1.7	1608	1198	8.5	6.3
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3645MH0008570001301772R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3645MH0008570001301773S00					

target named Mixiguana

mhl00383	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3644MH0003830011301711C00	1711	13977	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3645MH0008570001301770R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3645MH0008570001301771S00					

Continued on Next Page...

target named Mocra															
mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3644MH0001900011301721C00	1721	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
mhli00299	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3644MH0002990011301723C00	1723	13954	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.8		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3645MH0001530001301768R00				range map product:						3645MH0001530001301769S00	
mhli00299	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3644MH0002990011301733C00	1733	13962	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3645MH0001530001301766R00				range map product:						3645MH0001530001301767S00	
mhli00311	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3644MH0003110011301743C00	1743	14600	4.1	2.2	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3645MH0001530001301764R00				range map product:						3645MH0001530001301765S00	
mhli00299	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 1														
	3644MH0002990011301753C00	1753	13947	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3645MH0001530001301762R00				range map product:						3645MH0001530001301763S00	

5 Focus merge product information

5.1 Purpose and description

The MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* provide information about the best focus and range map products created by focus merges performed onboard the MAHLI instrument.

The information includes:

1. thumbnail images representing the appearance of each best focus and range map product;
2. a brief title or description of the image target and purpose;
3. the Sol and date (UTC) that the merged parent images were acquired;
4. the Sol on which the focus merge took place,
5. image IDs for the focus merge products and a corresponding full-frame image;
6. the MAHLI command sequence that acquired the parent images and the command sequence that created the focus merge products;
7. the commanded stack depth; that is, the number of parent images acquired in a given focus stack;
8. the type of focus stack (relative or absolute; see definitions in **Section 7**);
9. a list of the thumbnail image IDs for the parent images acquired in the focus stack (because, in some cases, these are the only versions of the focus stack images that are received on Earth);
10. the focus position (stepper motor count) for each parent image in the focus stack;
11. the range and range uncertainty determined from the focus position (motor count) of each parent image; and
12. the grayscale DN value corresponding to each parent image motor count and range in the focus merge range map product.

Further, for each parent image, the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* state whether any of the full-size images (Individual Focus Stack Images) were received on Earth, listing:

13. the image ID of the full-size parent or child image, if received on Earth;
14. the date on which the full-size image was received (applicable only to *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* for the period between Sol 0 and 946 after that, with the exception of Sol 930, this practice was abandoned as unnecessary);

15. the compression quality of the best version of the image, if received on Earth (this practice was later abandoned as unnecessary); and
16. a statement regarding the fate of parent images not received on Earth; that is, the Sol on which the parent was deleted from the data storage inside the instrument’s digital electronics assembly (DEA).

Each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is identified by the Sol on which the parent images were acquired. The onboard merge, in some cases, might have been performed on a later sol.

The parent images identified in rows that are colored orange, if they have a corresponding DN value in a yellow-colored column, are those that participated in the creation of the focus merge product. In other words, those that are in white rows (for which there is a corresponding DN in the yellow column) had no in-focus elements and thus were not incorporated into the merged product, even if they had been commanded to be merged. Which images were commanded to be merged can be determined by the yellow-colored column that indicates the corresponding DN values in the range map image product; for cases in which the commanded focus stack depth is > 8 , the corresponding DN values (yellow-colored column) will indicate the 8 commanded to be merged (the instrument cannot merge > 8 but it can acquire > 8 images in a focus stack).

In cases in which the focus stack parent images were returned to Earth, the data user has the option to perform a new focus merge using software approaches available on Earth, now or in the future, which might outperform the MAHLI onboard algorithm. The user also has the opportunity, in these cases, to improve each parent image before performing the merge (e.g., remove blemishes, perform flat field correction, etc.).

When a > 8 image focus stack has been acquired, the orange-colored rows can *also* indicate recommendations for images that would contain in-focus elements and could be added to a future focus merge product, whether performed onboard MAHLI or on Earth after receipt of the full-size images. Those images that are recommended, but were not merged onboard, have no “Corresponding DN in Range Map” in the yellow, rightmost columns of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*.

For the Sol 3548–3644 period, focus stacks that were merged onboard the instrument were acquired on **Sols 3551, 3553, 3555, 3558, 3560, 3562, 3564, 3566, 3568, 3571, 3573, 3575, 3578, 3583, 3592, 3594, 3596, 3599, 3601, 3603, 3605, 3609, 3624, 3626, 3628, 3630, 3633, 3635, 3637, 3639, 3641, 3644**. Unless otherwise stated, the onboard focus merges performed during this period were all of the “basic” type (see Edgett *et al.* 2012; Edgett *et al.* 2015).

5.2 Formulae

5.2.1 Range

When acquiring a focus stack, the MAHLI camera head is held in a fixed position. This means that the working distance (d_w) — and corresponding standoff distance (d_s) — is constant (see **Section 5.2.5**). However, each image acquired in a focus stack is done so at a different focus position; that is, a different stepper motor count position (m_{open} or m_{closed} ; usually m_{open}). That

motor count is related to the range (r_{fm}) between the front lens element of the camera and the in-focus elements of the image by the same empirical formula (**Equation 1**) as applied to determine working distance from motor count. In centimeters,

$$r_{fm} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (12)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For each parent image in a given focus stack, this range is given in the green-colored column on the right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

5.2.2 Range uncertainty estimate

The uncertainty ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) in the computed range (r_{fm}) is estimated using depth of field as related to the corresponding range (via motor count; **Equation 12**) for each merged parent image. The range uncertainty estimate is noted in the light green column on the lower right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Estimated Range Uncertainty”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created before Sol 942, our estimate of range uncertainty was based on the older (Edgett *et al.* 2013) depth of field equations described in **Section 4.2.3, Equations 4, 5, and 6**, in which we substituted r_{fm} for d_w .

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Depth of Field”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created starting with Sol 942, we used the refined knowledge of MAHLI depth of field, described by Edgett *et al.* (2015) and in **Equation 7** of **Section 4.2.3** to determine d_{far} and d_{near} for each focus stack parent image motor count. The resulting range uncertainty estimate ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) reported in the light green column on the lower right side of the corresponding *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is estimated by the average of the absolute values of d_{far} and d_{near} :

$$\pm r_{uncertainty} = ((-d_{near}) + d_{far})/2. \quad (13)$$

Alternatively, particularly after Sol 1000, the depth of field is reported in the form of both the near and far (d_{far} and d_{near}) depths of field, per **Equation 7**.

5.2.3 Corresponding DN in range map product

Focus merge range map products created onboard MAHLI are returned as grayscale JPEG compressed images. The pixel values (DN) range from 0 to 255. These are assigned by the onboard software on the basis of commanded focus stack depth. The table below, from Edgett *et al.* (2015), shows the relationship between each image commanded to be focus merged and its corresponding grayscale DN value in a MAHLI range map product. In other words, if the instrument is commanded to merge eight images, DN values are assigned according to the second column in the table; if commanded to merge only four images, the corresponding DN

values are those in the sixth column. Thus, each DN in a range map product can be related to a motor count position and a corresponding range via linear interpolation between these values.

Relation between commanded image participant in an onboard MAHLI focus merge and range map grayscale data value (DN)							
image commanded to be merged	DN for 8-image merge	DN for 7-image merge	DN for 6-image merge	DN for 5-image merge	DN for 4-image merge	DN for 3-image merge	DN for 2-image merge
1st	255	255	255	255	255	255	255
2nd	223	218	212	204	191	170	127
3rd	191	182	170	153	127	84	—
4th	159	145	127	102	63	—	—
5th	127	109	84	51	—	—	—
6th	95	72	42	—	—	—	—
7th	63	36	—	—	—	—	—
8th	31	—	—	—	—	—	—

5.2.4 Determination of which parent images participated in a given focus merge product (orange rows)

Focus merge parent images in the orange-colored rows on each of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* are an indicator of the images that were actually merged. A merge of up to 8 images might be commanded, but perhaps only 3, 4, or 5 of them actually exhibit in-focus elements the get incorporated into the best focus image product.

As discussed by Edgett *et al.* (2015), the parent images that were actually merged, relative to the number commanded to be merged (indicated by the number of yellow-colored rows regarding the corresponding DN in the range map products on the right side of each *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*), are determined by the range of grayscale DN, between 0 and 255, in the focus merge range map product. For example, if the DN range of this product is 71 to 138, then only four of 8 images commanded to be merged participated in that merge, per the DN values corresponding to an 8-image focus merge, per the table above.

5.2.5 Camera working distance and standoff distance

For a given focus stack, the distance between the MAHLI camera head and an imaged target can be determined from a corresponding image acquired via autofocus (assuming the autofocus effort found focus). In other words, while the range between the camera and the in-focus elements of a parent image are captured by the individual parent images in the focus stack (**Section 5.2.1**), the camera acquired the stack from a fixed working distance. On the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the corresponding autofocused image, and its stepper motor count focus position, are stated on the left side of the sheet, beneath the thumbnail images, in rows and columns colored light blue.

For some *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the working distance (d_w) and standoff distance (d_s) are provided in these blue rows and columns. These were computed from the motor count position using the same formulae for d_w and d_s described in **Section 4.2**

(**Equations 1 and 3**, respectively). Where these values are not given, the data user can apply **Equations 1 and 3** to the motor count, or use the corresponding full-frame image ID to identify the working distance and standoff distance using the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* for that Sol. We began to regularly provide a result for d_w and d_s starting with Sol 694; before that, the cases in which these values are not given are a reflection of the evolution of the production and content of the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* over time.

updated: 01_November_2022

Sol 3551 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Karisparo - ~24 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3551MH0003590011204537C00			
best focus image:	3551MH0001530001204582R00	4582	motor count:		13031	range (cm):	25.7		
range map product:	3551MH0001530001204583S00	4583	acquired sequence:		mhli00359	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	2-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3551	focus merged on sol:		3551	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3551MH0003590021204538C00	4538	12959	30.54	-2.3	2.7	114.4	8.8	255	1
3551MH0003590021204539C00	4539	12977	29.18	-2.1	2.4	109.6	8.0	223	2
3551MH0003590021204540C00	4540	12995	27.92	-2.0	2.2	105.2	7.4	191	3
3551MH0003590021204541C00	4541	13013	26.77	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	159	4
3551MH0003590021204542C00	4542	13031	25.70	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	127	5
3551MH0003590021204543C00	4543	13049	24.70	-1.6	1.7	93.8	5.8	95	6
3551MH0003590021204544C00	4544	13067	23.77	-1.4	1.6	90.6	5.3	63	7
3551MH0003590021204545C00	4545	13085	22.90	-1.3	1.5	87.5	5.0	31	8

updated: 01_November_2022

Sol 3551 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Karisparo - mosaic position 1 of 3 - ~4 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3551MH0003630011204547C00			
best focus image:	3551MH0001530001204580R00	4580	motor count:		14170	range (cm):	5.8		
range map product:	3551MH0001530001204581S00	4581	acquired sequence:		mhli00363	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	2-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		72	acquired on sol:		3551	focus merged on sol:		3551	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3551MH0003630021204548C00	4548	13882	7.69	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1
3551MH0003630021204549C00	4549	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3551MH0003630021204550C00	4550	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	191	3
3551MH0003630021204551C00	4551	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	159	4
3551MH0003630021204552C00	4552	14170	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	127	5
3551MH0003630021204553C00	4553	14242	5.49	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	95	6
3551MH0003630021204554C00	4554	14314	5.16	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	63	7
3551MH0003630021204555C00	4555	14386	4.85	-0.1	0.1	24.0	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3551 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Karisparo - mosaic position 2 of 3 - ~4 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3551MH0003630011204557C00			
best focus image:	3551MH0001530001204578R00	4578	motor count:		14170	range (cm):	5.8		
range map product:	3551MH0001530001204579S00	4579	acquired sequence:		mhli00363	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	2-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		72	acquired on sol:		3551	focus merged on sol:		3551	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3551MH0003630021204558C00	4558	13882	7.69	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1
3551MH0003630021204559C00	4559	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3551MH0003630021204560C00	4560	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	191	3
3551MH0003630021204561C00	4561	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	159	4
3551MH0003630021204562C00	4562	14170	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	127	5
3551MH0003630021204563C00	4563	14242	5.49	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	95	6
3551MH0003630021204564C00	4564	14314	5.16	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	63	7
3551MH0003630021204565C00	4565	14386	4.85	-0.1	0.1	24.0	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3551 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Karisparo - mosaic position 3 of 3 - ~4 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3551MH0003630011204567C00			
best focus image:	3551MH0001530001204576R00	4576	motor count:		14119	range (cm):	6.1		
range map product:	3551MH0001530001204577S00	4577	acquired sequence:		mhli00363	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	2-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		72	acquired on sol:		3551	focus merged on sol:		3551	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3551MH0003630021204568C00	4568	13831	8.10	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	255	1
3551MH0003630021204569C00	4569	13903	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	223	2
3551MH0003630021204570C00	4570	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3551MH0003630021204571C00	4571	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	159	4
3551MH0003630021204572C00	4572	14119	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	127	5
3551MH0003630021204573C00	4573	14191	5.74	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	95	6
3551MH0003630021204574C00	4574	14263	5.39	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	63	7
3551MH0003630021204575C00	4575	14335	5.07	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3553 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Arorouta - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3553MH0001820011204587C00				
best focus image:	3553MH0001530001204632R00	4632	motor count:		14225	range (cm):		5.6	
range map product:	3553MH0001530001204633S00	4633	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	4-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3553	focus merged on sol:		3553	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3553MH0001820021204588C00	4588	14129	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	255	1
3553MH0001820021204589C00	4589	14153	5.94	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	223	2
3553MH0001820021204590C00	4590	14177	5.81	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	191	3
3553MH0001820021204591C00	4591	14201	5.69	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	159	4
3553MH0001820021204592C00	4592	14225	5.57	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	127	5
3553MH0001820021204593C00	4593	14249	5.45	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	95	6
3553MH0001820021204594C00	4594	14273	5.34	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	63	7
3553MH0001820021204595C00	4595	14297	5.23	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3553 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Arorouta - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3553MH0001820011204597C00				
best focus image:	3553MH0001530001204630R00	4630	motor count:		14227	range (cm):		5.6	
range map product:	3553MH0001530001204631S00	4631	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	4-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3553	focus merged on sol:		3553	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3553MH0001820021204598C00	4598	14131	6.06	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	255	1
3553MH0001820021204599C00	4599	14155	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	223	2
3553MH0001820021204600C00	4600	14179	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	191	3
3553MH0001820021204601C00	4601	14203	5.68	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	159	4
3553MH0001820021204602C00	4602	14227	5.56	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	127	5
3553MH0001820021204603C00	4603	14251	5.44	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	95	6
3553MH0001820021204604C00	4604	14275	5.33	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	63	7
3553MH0001820021204605C00	4605	14299	5.22	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3553 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 1 of 2 - ~20 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3553MH0008540011204607C00			
best focus image:	3553MH0001530001204628R00	4628	motor count:		13117	range (cm):		21.5	
range map product:	3553MH0001530001204629S00	4629	acquired sequence:		mhli00854		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	4-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3553	focus merged on sol:		3553	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3553MH0008540021204608C00	4608	12997	27.79	-1.9	2.2	104.7	7.3	255	1
3553MH0008540021204609C00	4609	13027	25.93	-1.7	1.9	98.2	6.3	223	2
3553MH0008540021204610C00	4610	13057	24.28	-1.5	1.7	92.4	5.6	191	3
3553MH0008540021204611C00	4611	13087	22.81	-1.3	1.5	87.2	4.9	159	4
3553MH0008540021204612C00	4612	13117	21.49	-1.2	1.3	82.5	4.4	127	5
3553MH0008540021204613C00	4613	13147	20.30	-1.1	1.1	78.4	3.9	95	6
3553MH0008540021204614C00	4614	13177	19.22	-1.0	1.0	74.6	3.5	63	7
3553MH0008540021204615C00	4615	13207	18.24	-0.9	0.9	71.1	3.2	31	8

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Sol 3553 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 2 of 2 - ~21 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3553MH0008540011204617C00			
best focus image:	3553MH0001530001204626R00	4626	motor count:		13076	range (cm):		23.3	
range map product:	3553MH0001530001204627S00	4627	acquired sequence:		mhli00854		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	4-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3553	focus merged on sol:		3553	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3553MH0008540021204618C00	4618	12956	30.77	-2.4	2.7	115.2	9.0	255	1
3553MH0008540021204619C00	4619	12986	28.54	-2.0	2.3	107.4	7.7	223	2
3553MH0008540021204620C00	4620	13016	26.58	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	191	3
3553MH0008540021204621C00	4621	13046	24.86	-1.6	1.7	94.4	5.8	159	4
3553MH0008540021204622C00	4622	13076	23.33	-1.4	1.5	89.0	5.1	127	5
3553MH0008540021204623C00	4623	13106	21.96	-1.2	1.4	84.2	4.6	95	6
3553MH0008540021204624C00	4624	13136	20.72	-1.1	1.2	79.8	4.1	63	7
3553MH0008540021204625C00	4625	13166	19.60	-1.0	1.1	75.9	3.6	31	8

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Sol 3555 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Sloth_Island - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3555MH0002990011204637C00				
best focus image:	3556MH0002270001004696R00	4696	motor count:		14032	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3556MH0002270001004697S00	4697	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	7-Aug-22	merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3555	focus merged on sol:		3556	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3555MH0002990021204638C00	4638	13888	7.64	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
3555MH0002990021204639C00	4639	13924	7.37	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3555MH0002990021204640C00	4640	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
3555MH0002990021204641C00	4641	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
3555MH0002990021204642C00	4642	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3555MH0002990021204643C00	4643	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	95	6
3555MH0002990021204644C00	4644	14104	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	63	7
3555MH0002990021204645C00	4645	14140	6.01	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3555 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Sloth_Island - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3555MH0002990011204647C00				
best focus image:	3556MH0002270001004694R00	4694	motor count:		14029	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3556MH0002270001004695S00	4695	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	7-Aug-22	merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3555	focus merged on sol:		3556	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3555MH0002990021204648C00	4648	13885	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	255	1
3555MH0002990021204649C00	4649	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3555MH0002990021204650C00	4650	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3555MH0002990021204651C00	4651	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3555MH0002990021204652C00	4652	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3555MH0002990021204653C00	4653	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
3555MH0002990021204654C00	4654	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	63	7
3555MH0002990021204655C00	4655	14137	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3555 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Sloth_Island - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3555MH0003350011204657C00				
best focus image:	3556MH0002270001104692R00	4692	motor count:		14756	range (cm):		3.6	
range map product:	3556MH0002270001104693S00	4693	acquired sequence:		mhli00335		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	7-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3555	focus merged on sol:		3556	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3555MH0003350021204658C00	4658	14540	4.28	-0.1	0.1	22.0	0.3	255	1
3555MH0003350021204659C00	4659	14594	4.11	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	223	2
3555MH0003350021204660C00	4660	14648	3.94	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	191	3
3555MH0003350021204661C00	4661	14702	3.78	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	159	4
3555MH0003350021204662C00	4662	14756	3.63	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	127	5
3555MH0003350021204663C00	4663	14810	3.48	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	95	6
3555MH0003350021204664C00	4664	14864	3.35	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	63	7
3555MH0003350021204665C00	4665	14918	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3555 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Aponguao - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3555MH0001820011104669C00				
best focus image:	3556MH0002270001104690R00	4690	motor count:		14002	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3556MH0002270001104691S00	4691	acquired sequence:		mhli00182		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	7-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3555	focus merged on sol:		3556	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3555MH0001820021104670C00	4670	13906	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
3555MH0001820021104671C00	4671	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
3555MH0001820021104672C00	4672	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
3555MH0001820021104673C00	4673	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3555MH0001820021104674C00	4674	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3555MH0001820021104675C00	4675	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3555MH0001820021104676C00	4676	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3555MH0001820021104677C00	4677	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3555 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Aponguao - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3555MH0001820011104679C00				
best focus image:	3556MH0002270001104688R00	4688	motor count:		14006	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3556MH0002270001104689S00	4689	acquired sequence:		mhli00182		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	7-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3555	focus merged on sol:		3556	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3555MH0001820021104680C00	4680	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
3555MH0001820021104681C00	4681	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
3555MH0001820021104682C00	4682	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3555MH0001820021104683C00	4683	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3555MH0001820021104684C00	4684	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3555MH0001820021104685C00	4685	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3555MH0001820021104686C00	4686	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3555MH0001820021104687C00	4687	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3558 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Sao_Marcos - stereo-1 - ~3 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3558MH0003080011004701C00				
best focus image:	3558MH0001710000704785R00	4785	motor count:		14328	range (cm):		5.1	
range map product:	3558MH0001710000704786S00	4786	acquired sequence:		mhli00308	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	9-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3558	focus merged on sol:		3558	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3558MH0003080021004702C00	4702	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	255	1
3558MH0003080021004703C00	4703	14130	6.06	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	223	2
3558MH0003080021004704C00	4704	14196	5.71	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	191	3
3558MH0003080021004705C00	4705	14262	5.39	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	159	4
3558MH0003080021004706C00	4706	14328	5.10	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	127	5
3558MH0003080021004707C00	4707	14394	4.82	-0.1	0.1	23.9	0.4	95	6
3558MH0003080021004708C00	4708	14460	4.57	-0.1	0.1	23.0	0.3	63	7
3558MH0003080021004709C00	4709	14526	4.33	-0.1	0.1	22.1	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3558 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Sao_Marcos - stereo-2 - ~3 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3558MH0003080011004711C00				
best focus image:	3558MH0001710000704783R00	4783	motor count:		14370	range (cm):		4.9	
range map product:	3558MH0001710000704784S00	4784	acquired sequence:		mhli00308	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	9-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3558	focus merged on sol:		3558	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3558MH0003080021004712C00	4712	14106	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	255	1
3558MH0003080021004713C00	4713	14172	5.84	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	223	2
3558MH0003080021004714C00	4714	14238	5.51	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	191	3
3558MH0003080021004715C00	4715	14304	5.20	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	159	4
3558MH0003080021004716C00	4716	14370	4.92	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	127	5
3558MH0003080021004717C00	4717	14436	4.66	-0.1	0.1	23.3	0.3	95	6
3558MH0003080021004718C00	4718	14502	4.42	-0.1	0.1	22.4	0.3	63	7
3558MH0003080021004719C00	4719	14568	4.19	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3558 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Essequibo - stereo-1 - ~3 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3558MH0006730011004723C00			
best focus image:	3558MH0001710000704781R00	4781	motor count:		14431	range (cm):		4.7	
range map product:	3558MH0001710000704782S00	4782	acquired sequence:		mhli00673		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	9-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		84	acquired on sol:		3558	focus merged on sol:		3558	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3558MH0006730021004724C00	4724	14095	6.26	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	255	1
3558MH0006730021004725C00	4725	14179	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	223	2
3558MH0006730021004726C00	4726	14263	5.39	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	191	3
3558MH0006730021004727C00	4727	14347	5.01	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	159	4
3558MH0006730021004728C00	4728	14431	4.68	-0.1	0.1	23.4	0.3	127	5
3558MH0006730021004729C00	4729	14515	4.37	-0.1	0.1	22.3	0.3	95	6
3558MH0006730021004730C00	4730	14599	4.09	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	63	7
3558MH0006730021004731C00	4731	14683	3.83	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3558 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Essequibo - stereo-2 - ~3 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3558MH0006730011004733C00			
best focus image:	3558MH0001710000704779R00	4779	motor count:		14441	range (cm):		4.6	
range map product:	3558MH0001710000704780S00	4780	acquired sequence:		mhli00673		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	9-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		84	acquired on sol:		3558	focus merged on sol:		3558	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3558MH0006730021004734C00	4734	14105	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	255	1
3558MH0006730021004735C00	4735	14189	5.75	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	223	2
3558MH0006730020904736C00	4736	14273	5.34	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	191	3
3558MH0006730020904737C00	4737	14357	4.97	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	159	4
3558MH0006730020804738C00	4738	14441	4.64	-0.1	0.1	23.2	0.3	127	5
3558MH0006730020804739C00	4739	14525	4.34	-0.1	0.1	22.2	0.3	95	6
3558MH0006730020804740C00	4740	14609	4.06	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	63	7
3558MH0006730020804741C00	4741	14693	3.80	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3558 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Kumu_Falls - ~23 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3558MH0006780010804743C00				
best focus image:	3558MH0001710000704777R00	4777	motor count:		13037	range (cm):		25.4	
range map product:	3558MH0001710000704778S00	4778	acquired sequence:		mhli00678	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	9-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3558	focus merged on sol:		3558	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3558MH0006780030804745C00	4745	12941	32.02	-2.5	3.0	119.6	9.7	255	1
3558MH0006780030804746C00	4746	12965	30.07	-2.3	2.6	112.7	8.6	223	2
3558MH0006780030804747C00	4747	12989	28.33	-2.0	2.3	106.6	7.6	191	3
3558MH0006780030804748C00	4748	13013	26.77	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	159	4
3558MH0006780030804749C00	4749	13037	25.35	-1.6	1.8	96.2	6.1	127	5
3558MH0006780030804750C00	4750	13061	24.07	-1.5	1.6	91.6	5.5	95	6
3558MH0006780030804751C00	4751	13085	22.90	-1.3	1.5	87.5	5.0	63	7
3558MH0006780030804752C00	4752	13109	21.83	-1.2	1.3	83.7	4.5	31	8

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Sol 3558 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-1 - ~3 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3558MH0001660010804754C00				
best focus image:	3558MH0001710000704775R00	4775	motor count:		14292	range (cm):		5.3	
range map product:	3558MH0001710000704776S00	4776	acquired sequence:		mhli00166	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	9-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		78	acquired on sol:		3558	focus merged on sol:		3558	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3558MH0001660020804755C00	4755	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1
3558MH0001660020804756C00	4756	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	223	2
3558MH0001660020804757C00	4757	14136	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	191	3
3558MH0001660020804758C00	4758	14214	5.62	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	159	4
3558MH0001660020804759C00	4759	14292	5.25	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	127	5
3558MH0001660020804760C00	4760	14370	4.92	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	95	6
3558MH0001660020804761C00	4761	14448	4.61	-0.1	0.1	23.1	0.3	63	7
3558MH0001660020804762C00	4762	14526	4.33	-0.1	0.1	22.1	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3558 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Kumu_Falls - stereo-2 - ~3 cm standoff												
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3558MH0001660010704764C00								
best focus image:		3558MH0001710000704773R00		4773		motor count:		14303		range (cm):		5.2		
range map product:		3558MH0001710000704774S00		4774		acquired sequence:		mhli00166		stack type:		Relative		
acquired on date:		9-Aug-22				merge sequence:		mhli00171		merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:			78		acquired on sol:		3558		focus merged on sol:		3558			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8					
				near	far									
3558MH0001660020704765C00	4765	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	255	1					
3558MH0001660020704766C00	4766	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	223	2					
3558MH0001660020704767C00	4767	14147	5.97	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	191	3					
3558MH0001660020704768C00	4768	14225	5.57	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	159	4					
3558MH0001660020704769C00	4769	14303	5.21	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	127	5					
3558MH0001660020704770C00	4770	14381	4.87	-0.1	0.1	24.1	0.4	95	6					
3558MH0001660020704771C00	4771	14459	4.57	-0.1	0.1	23.0	0.3	63	7					
3558MH0001660020704772C00	4772	14537	4.29	-0.1	0.1	22.0	0.3	31	8					

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Sol 3560 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Annai - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3560MH0007630010704791C00			
best focus image:	3560MH0002270000504853R00	4853	motor count:		14006	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3560MH0002270000504854S00	4854	acquired sequence:		mhli00763		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	12-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3560	focus merged on sol:		3560	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3560MH0007630030704793C00	4793	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
3560MH0007630030704794C00	4794	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
3560MH0007630030704795C00	4795	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3560MH0007630030704796C00	4796	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3560MH0007630030704797C00	4797	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3560MH0007630030704798C00	4798	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3560MH0007630030704799C00	4799	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3560MH0007630030704800C00	4800	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3560 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Annai - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3560MH0007630010704802C00			
best focus image:	3560MH0002270000504851R00	4851	motor count:		14009	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3560MH0002270000504852S00	4852	acquired sequence:		mhli00763		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	12-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3560	focus merged on sol:		3560	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3560MH0007630030704804C00	4804	13913	7.45	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	255	1
3560MH0007630030704805C00	4805	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
3560MH0007630030704806C00	4806	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
3560MH0007630030704807C00	4807	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3560MH0007630030704808C00	4808	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3560MH0007630030704809C00	4809	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
3560MH0007630030704810C00	4810	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3560MH0007630030704811C00	4811	14081	6.34	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3560 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Annai - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3560MH0008350010704813C00				
best focus image:	3560MH0002270000604849R00	4849	motor count:		15124	range (cm):		2.8	
range map product:	3560MH0002270000504850S00	4850	acquired sequence:		mhli00835	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	12-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3560	focus merged on sol:		3560	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3560MH0008350030704815C00	4815	15004	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	255	1
3560MH0008350030704816C00	4816	15034	2.97	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	223	2
3560MH0008350030704817C00	4817	15064	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	191	3
3560MH0008350030704818C00	4818	15094	2.85	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	159	4
3560MH0008350030704819C00	4819	15124	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	127	5
3560MH0008350030704820C00	4820	15154	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	95	6
3560MH0008350030704821C00	4821	15184	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	63	7
3560MH0008350030704822C00	4822	15214	2.62	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3560 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mirizal - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3560MH0002240010704826C00				
best focus image:	3560MH0002270000604847R00	4847	motor count:		14138	range (cm):		6.0	
range map product:	3560MH0002270000604848S00	4848	acquired sequence:		mhli00224	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	12-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3560	focus merged on sol:		3560	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3560MH0002240020704827C00	4827	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
3560MH0002240020704828C00	4828	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	223	2
3560MH0002240020704829C00	4829	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	191	3
3560MH0002240020604830C00	4830	14096	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	159	4
3560MH0002240020604831C00	4831	14138	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	127	5
3560MH0002240020604832C00	4832	14180	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	95	6
3560MH0002240020604833C00	4833	14222	5.58	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	63	7
3560MH0002240020604834C00	4834	14264	5.38	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3560 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Mirizal - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3560MH0002240010604836C00				
best focus image:	3560MH0002270000604845R00	4845	motor count:		14141	range (cm):		6.0	
range map product:	3560MH0002270000604846S00	4846	acquired sequence:		mhli00224		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	12-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3560	focus merged on sol:		3560	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3560MH0002240020604837C00	4837	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	255	1
3560MH0002240020604838C00	4838	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	223	2
3560MH0002240020604839C00	4839	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	191	3
3560MH0002240020604840C00	4840	14099	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	159	4
3560MH0002240020604841C00	4841	14141	6.00	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	127	5
3560MH0002240020604842C00	4842	14183	5.78	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	95	6
3560MH0002240020604843C00	4843	14225	5.57	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	63	7
3560MH0002240020604844C00	4844	14267	5.37	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3562 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target El_Silencio - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff											
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3562MH0007210011300005C00							
best focus image:		3562MH0007070001300057R00		57		motor count:		14181		range (cm):		5.8	
range map product:		3562MH0007070001300058S00		58		acquired sequence:		mhli00721		stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:		14-Aug-22				merge sequence:		mhli00707		merge type:		Basic	
motor count interval:		42		acquired on sol:		3562		focus merged on sol:		3562			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8				
				near	far								
3562MH0007210031300007C00	7	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	255	1				
3562MH0007210031300008C00	8	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	223	2				
3562MH0007210031300009C00	9	14097	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	191	3				
3562MH0007210031300010C00	10	14139	6.01	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	159	4				
3562MH0007210031300011C00	11	14181	5.79	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	127	5				
3562MH0007210031300012C00	12	14223	5.58	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	95	6				
3562MH0007210031300013C00	13	14265	5.38	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	63	7				
3562MH0007210031300014C00	14	14307	5.19	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	31	8				

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Sol 3562 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target El_Silencio - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff											
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3562MH0007210011300016C00							
best focus image:		3562MH0007070001300055R00		55		motor count:		14183		range (cm):		5.8	
range map product:		3562MH0007070001300056S00		56		acquired sequence:		mhli00721		stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:		14-Aug-22				merge sequence:		mhli00707		merge type:		Basic	
motor count interval:		42		acquired on sol:		3562		focus merged on sol:		3562			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8				
				near	far								
3562MH0007210031300018C00	18	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	255	1				
3562MH0007210031300019C00	19	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	223	2				
3562MH0007210031300020C00	20	14099	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	191	3				
3562MH0007210031300021C00	21	14141	6.00	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	159	4				
3562MH0007210031300022C00	22	14183	5.78	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	127	5				
3562MH0007210031300023C00	23	14225	5.57	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	95	6				
3562MH0007210031300024C00	24	14267	5.37	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	63	7				
3562MH0007210031300025C00	25	14309	5.18	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	31	8				

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Sol 3562 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Orinduik - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3562MH0007630011300030C00				
best focus image:	3562MH0007070001300053R00	53	motor count:		14203	range (cm):		5.7	
range map product:	3562MH0007070001300054S00	54	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Aug-22	merge sequence:		mhli00707	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3562	focus merged on sol:		3562	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3562MH0007630031300032C00	32	14107	6.19	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	255	1
3562MH0007630031300033C00	33	14131	6.06	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	223	2
3562MH0007630031300034C00	34	14155	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	191	3
3562MH0007630031300035C00	35	14179	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	159	4
3562MH0007630031300036C00	36	14203	5.68	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	127	5
3562MH0007630031300037C00	37	14227	5.56	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	95	6
3562MH0007630031300038C00	38	14251	5.44	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	63	7
3562MH0007630031300039C00	39	14275	5.33	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3562 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Orinduik - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3562MH0007630011300041C00				
best focus image:	3562MH0007070001300051R00	51	motor count:		14205	range (cm):		5.7	
range map product:	3562MH0007070001300052S00	52	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Aug-22	merge sequence:		mhli00707	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3562	focus merged on sol:		3562	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3562MH0007630031300043C00	43	14109	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	255	1
3562MH0007630031300044C00	44	14133	6.05	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	223	2
3562MH0007630031300045C00	45	14157	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	191	3
3562MH0007630031300046C00	46	14181	5.79	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	159	4
3562MH0007630031300047C00	47	14205	5.67	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	127	5
3562MH0007630031300048C00	48	14229	5.55	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	95	6
3562MH0007630031300049C00	49	14253	5.43	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	63	7
3562MH0007630031300050C00	50	14277	5.32	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3564 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Sand_Creek - ~35 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3564MH0007140011300063C00				
best focus image:	3564MH0008060001300111R00	111	motor count:		14229	range (cm):		5.5	
range map product:	3564MH0008060001300112S00	112	acquired sequence:		mhli00714	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	16-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00806	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3564	focus merged on sol:		3564	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3564MH0007140031300065C00	65	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
3564MH0007140031300066C00	66	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	223	2
3564MH0007140031300067C00	67	14097	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	191	3
3564MH0007140031300068C00	68	14163	5.88	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	159	4
3564MH0007140031300069C00	69	14229	5.55	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	127	5
3564MH0007140031300070C00	70	14295	5.24	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	95	6
3564MH0007140031300071C00	71	14361	4.96	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	63	7
3564MH0007140031300072C00	72	14427	4.69	-0.1	0.1	23.4	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3564 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nascente - stereo-1 - ~55 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3564MH0002990011300076C00				
best focus image:	3564MH0008060001300109R00	109	motor count:		13908	range (cm):		7.5	
range map product:	3564MH0008060001300110S00	110	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	16-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00806	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3564	focus merged on sol:		3564	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3564MH0002990021300077C00	77	13764	8.70	-0.2	0.2	37.5	0.8	255	1
3564MH0002990021300078C00	78	13800	8.37	-0.2	0.2	36.4	0.8	223	2
3564MH0002990021300079C00	79	13836	8.06	-0.2	0.2	35.3	0.7	191	3
3564MH0002990021300080C00	80	13872	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	159	4
3564MH0002990021300081C00	81	13908	7.49	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	127	5
3564MH0002990021300082C00	82	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	95	6
3564MH0002990021300083C00	83	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	63	7
3564MH0002990021300084C00	84	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	31	8

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Sol 3564 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nascente - stereo-2 - ~55 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3564MH0002990011300086C00				
best focus image:	3564MH0008060001300107R00	107	motor count:		13913	range (cm):	7.5		
range map product:	3564MH0008060001300108S00	108	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	16-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00806	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3564	focus merged on sol:		3564	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3564MH0002990021300087C00	87	13769	8.65	-0.2	0.2	37.3	0.8	255	1
3564MH0002990021300088C00	88	13805	8.32	-0.2	0.2	36.2	0.8	223	2
3564MH0002990021300089C00	89	13841	8.02	-0.2	0.2	35.1	0.7	191	3
3564MH0002990021300090C00	90	13877	7.73	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	159	4
3564MH0002990021300091C00	91	13913	7.45	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	127	5
3564MH0002990021300092C00	92	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	95	6
3564MH0002990021300093C00	93	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	63	7
3564MH0002990021300094C00	94	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	31	8

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Sol 3564 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nascente - ~25 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3564MH0003370011300096C00				
best focus image:	3564MH0008060001300105R00	105	motor count:		14477	range (cm):	4.5		
range map product:	3564MH0008060001300106S00	106	acquired sequence:		mhli00337	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	16-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00806	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3564	focus merged on sol:		3564	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3564MH0003370021300097C00	97	14309	5.18	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	255	1
3564MH0003370021300098C00	98	14351	5.00	-0.1	0.1	24.5	0.4	223	2
3564MH0003370021300099C00	99	14393	4.83	-0.1	0.1	23.9	0.4	191	3
3564MH0003370021300100C00	100	14435	4.66	-0.1	0.1	23.3	0.3	159	4
3564MH0003370021300101C00	101	14477	4.51	-0.1	0.1	22.8	0.3	127	5
3564MH0003370021300102C00	102	14519	4.36	-0.1	0.1	22.2	0.3	95	6
3564MH0003370021300103C00	103	14561	4.21	-0.1	0.1	21.7	0.3	63	7
3564MH0003370021300104C00	104	14603	4.08	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3566 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Yupakari - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3566MH0007090011300119C00				
best focus image:	3567MH0007030001300142R00	142	motor count:		14252	range (cm):		5.4	
range map product:	3567MH0007030001300143S00	143	acquired sequence:		mhli00709	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	18-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00703	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3566	focus merged on sol:		3567	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3566MH0007090031300121C00	121	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	255	1
3566MH0007090031300122C00	122	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	223	2
3566MH0007090031300123C00	123	14156	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.5	191	3
3566MH0007090031300124C00	124	14204	5.67	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	159	4
3566MH0007090031300125C00	125	14252	5.44	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	127	5
3566MH0007090031300126C00	126	14300	5.22	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	95	6
3566MH0007090031300127C00	127	14348	5.01	-0.1	0.1	24.5	0.4	63	7
3566MH0007090031300128C00	128	14396	4.81	-0.1	0.1	23.8	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3566 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Yupakari - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3566MH0007090011300130C00				
best focus image:	3567MH0007030001300140R00	140	motor count:		14254	range (cm):		5.4	
range map product:	3567MH0007030001300141S00	141	acquired sequence:		mhli00709	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	18-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00703	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3566	focus merged on sol:		3567	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3566MH0007090031300132C00	132	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	255	1
3566MH0007090031300133C00	133	14110	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	223	2
3566MH0007090031300134C00	134	14158	5.91	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	191	3
3566MH0007090031300135C00	135	14206	5.66	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	159	4
3566MH0007090031300136C00	136	14254	5.43	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	127	5
3566MH0007090031300137C00	137	14302	5.21	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	95	6
3566MH0007090031300138C00	138	14350	5.00	-0.1	0.1	24.5	0.4	63	7
3566MH0007090031300139C00	139	14398	4.81	-0.1	0.1	23.8	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3568 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Fortaleza - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3568MH0007140011300157C00				
best focus image:	3570MH0002270001300222R00	222	motor count:		14223	range (cm):		5.6	
range map product:	3570MH0002270001300223S00	223	acquired sequence:		mhli00714	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	20-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3568	focus merged on sol:		3570	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3568MH0007140031300159C00	159	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	255	1
3568MH0007140031300160C00	160	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	223	2
3568MH0007140031300161C00	161	14091	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	191	3
3568MH0007140031300162C00	162	14157	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	159	4
3568MH0007140031300163C00	163	14223	5.58	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	127	5
3568MH0007140031300164C00	164	14289	5.27	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	95	6
3568MH0007140031300165C00	165	14355	4.98	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	63	7
3568MH0007140031300166C00	166	14421	4.72	-0.1	0.1	23.5	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3568 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Fortaleza - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3568MH0007140011300168C00				
best focus image:	3570MH0002270001300220R00	220	motor count:		14240	range (cm):		5.5	
range map product:	3570MH0002270001300221S00	221	acquired sequence:		mhli00714	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	20-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3568	focus merged on sol:		3570	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3568MH0007140031300170C00	170	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	255	1
3568MH0007140031300171C00	171	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	223	2
3568MH0007140031300172C00	172	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	191	3
3568MH0007140031300173C00	173	14174	5.83	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	159	4
3568MH0007140031300174C00	174	14240	5.50	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	127	5
3568MH0007140031300175C00	175	14306	5.19	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	95	6
3568MH0007140031300176C00	176	14372	4.91	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	63	7
3568MH0007140031300177C00	177	14438	4.65	-0.1	0.1	23.3	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3568 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Massara - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3568MH0008340011300182C00				
best focus image:	3570MH0002270001300218R00	218	motor count:		13969	range (cm):		7.1	
range map product:	3570MH0002270001300219S00	219	acquired sequence:		mhli00834	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	20-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3568	focus merged on sol:		3570	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3568MH0008340031300184C00	184	13897	7.57	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3568MH0008340031300185C00	185	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2
3568MH0008340031300186C00	186	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
3568MH0008340031300187C00	187	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	159	4
3568MH0008340031300188C00	188	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	127	5
3568MH0008340031300189C00	189	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	95	6
3568MH0008340031300190C00	190	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	63	7
3568MH0008340031300191C00	191	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	31	8

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Sol 3568 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Massara - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3568MH0008340011300193C00				
best focus image:	3570MH0002270001300216R00	216	motor count:		13959	range (cm):		7.1	
range map product:	3570MH0002270001300217S00	217	acquired sequence:		mhli00834	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	20-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3568	focus merged on sol:		3570	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3568MH0008340031300195C00	195	13887	7.65	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
3568MH0008340031300196C00	196	13905	7.51	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
3568MH0008340031300197C00	197	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	191	3
3568MH0008340031300198C00	198	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	159	4
3568MH0008340031300199C00	199	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	127	5
3568MH0008340031300200C00	200	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	95	6
3568MH0008340031300201C00	201	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	63	7
3568MH0008340031300202C00	202	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	31	8

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Sol 3568 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Massara - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3568MH0007850011300204C00				
best focus image:	3570MH0002270001300214R00	214	motor count:		14987	range (cm):		3.1	
range map product:	3570MH0002270001300215S00	215	acquired sequence:		mhli00785		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	20-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3568	focus merged on sol:		3570	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3568MH0007850031300206C00	206	14819	3.46	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	255	1
3568MH0007850031300207C00	207	14861	3.36	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	223	2
3568MH0007850031300208C00	208	14903	3.26	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	191	3
3568MH0007850031300209C00	209	14945	3.16	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	159	4
3568MH0007850031300210C00	210	14987	3.07	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	127	5
3568MH0007850031300211C00	211	15029	2.98	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	95	6
3568MH0007850031300212C00	212	15071	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	63	7
3568MH0007850031300213C00	213	15113	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3571 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Raimundo - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3571MH0002240011300227C00				
best focus image:	3571MH0001930001300260R00	260	motor count:		13966	range (cm):		7.1	
range map product:	3571MH0001930001300261S00	261	acquired sequence:		mhli00224	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	23-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3571	focus merged on sol:		3571	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3571MH0002240021300228C00	228	13798	8.39	-0.2	0.2	36.4	0.8	255	1
3571MH0002240021300229C00	229	13840	8.03	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	223	2
3571MH0002240021300230C00	230	13882	7.69	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	191	3
3571MH0002240021300231C00	231	13924	7.37	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	159	4
3571MH0002240021300232C00	232	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	127	5
3571MH0002240021300233C00	233	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
3571MH0002240021300234C00	234	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3571MH0002240021300235C00	235	14092	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3571 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Raimundo - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3571MH0002240011300237C00				
best focus image:	3571MH0001930001300258R00	258	motor count:		13987	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3571MH0001930001300259S00	259	acquired sequence:		mhli00224	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	23-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3571	focus merged on sol:		3571	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3571MH0002240021300238C00	238	13819	8.20	-0.2	0.2	35.8	0.7	255	1
3571MH0002240021300239C00	239	13861	7.85	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	223	2
3571MH0002240021300240C00	240	13903	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	191	3
3571MH0002240021300241C00	241	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	159	4
3571MH0002240021300242C00	242	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3571MH0002240021300243C00	243	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3571MH0002240021300244C00	244	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3571MH0002240021300245C00	245	14113	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3571 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Raimundo - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3571MH0003070011300247C00				
best focus image:	3571MH0001930001300256R00	256	motor count:		14629	range (cm):		4.0	
range map product:	3571MH0001930001300257S00	257	acquired sequence:		mhli00307		stack type:		Relative
acquired on date:	23-Aug-22		merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		72	acquired on sol:		3571		focus merged on sol:		3571
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3571MH0003070021300248C00	248	14341	5.04	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	255	1
3571MH0003070021300249C00	249	14413	4.75	-0.1	0.1	23.6	0.3	223	2
3571MH0003070021300250C00	250	14485	4.48	-0.1	0.1	22.7	0.3	191	3
3571MH0003070021300251C00	251	14557	4.23	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	159	4
3571MH0003070021300252C00	252	14629	4.00	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	127	5
3571MH0003070021300253C00	253	14701	3.78	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	95	6
3571MH0003070021300254C00	254	14773	3.58	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	63	7
3571MH0003070021300255C00	255	14845	3.40	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3573 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Kanuku - relief model position 1 - stereo-1 - ~65 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3573MH0002970011300265C00				
best focus image:	3574MH0002270001300330R00	330	motor count:		13808	range (cm):		8.3	
range map product:	3574MH0002270001300331S00	331	acquired sequence:		mhli00297	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	25-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3573	focus merged on sol:		3574	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3573MH0002970021300266C00	266	13568	10.88	-0.3	0.3	45.2	1.2	255	1
3573MH0002970021300267C00	267	13628	10.13	-0.3	0.3	42.6	1.1	223	2
3573MH0002970021300268C00	268	13688	9.46	-0.3	0.3	40.2	0.9	191	3
3573MH0002970021300269C00	269	13748	8.85	-0.2	0.2	38.0	0.8	159	4
3573MH0002970021300270C00	270	13808	8.30	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	127	5
3573MH0002970021300271C00	271	13868	7.80	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	95	6
3573MH0002970021300272C00	272	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	63	7
3573MH0002970021300273C00	273	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	31	8

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Sol 3573 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Kanuku - relief model position 2 - stereo-2 - ~65 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3573MH0002970011300275C00				
best focus image:	3574MH0002270001300328R00	328	motor count:		13810	range (cm):		8.3	
range map product:	3574MH0002270001300329S00	329	acquired sequence:		mhli00297	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	25-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3573	focus merged on sol:		3574	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3573MH0002970021300276C00	276	13570	10.86	-0.3	0.3	45.1	1.2	255	1
3573MH0002970021300277C00	277	13630	10.11	-0.3	0.3	42.5	1.0	223	2
3573MH0002970021300278C00	278	13690	9.43	-0.3	0.3	40.1	0.9	191	3
3573MH0002970021300279C00	279	13750	8.83	-0.2	0.2	38.0	0.8	159	4
3573MH0002970021300280C00	280	13810	8.28	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	127	5
3573MH0002970021300281C00	281	13870	7.78	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	95	6
3573MH0002970021300282C00	282	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	63	7
3573MH0002970021300283C00	283	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	31	8

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Sol 3573 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Kanuku - ~35 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3573MH0003110011300291C00				
best focus image:	3574MH0002270001300326R00	326	motor count:		14266	range (cm):		5.4	
range map product:	3574MH0002270001300327S00	327	acquired sequence:		mhli00311	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	25-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3573	focus merged on sol:		3574	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3573MH0003110021300292C00	292	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	255	1
3573MH0003110021300293C00	293	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	223	2
3573MH0003110021300294C00	294	14134	6.04	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	191	3
3573MH0003110021300295C00	295	14200	5.69	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	159	4
3573MH0003110021300296C00	296	14266	5.37	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	127	5
3573MH0003110021300297C00	297	14332	5.08	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	95	6
3573MH0003110021300298C00	298	14398	4.81	-0.1	0.1	23.8	0.4	63	7
3573MH0003110021300299C00	299	14464	4.55	-0.1	0.1	22.9	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3573 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3573MH0001820011300303C00				
best focus image:	3574MH0002270001300324R00	324	motor count:		13955	range (cm):		7.1	
range map product:	3574MH0002270001300325S00	325	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	25-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3573	focus merged on sol:		3574	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3573MH0001820021300304C00	304	13859	7.87	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	255	1
3573MH0001820021300305C00	305	13883	7.68	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
3573MH0001820021300306C00	306	13907	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	191	3
3573MH0001820021300307C00	307	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	159	4
3573MH0001820021300308C00	308	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	127	5
3573MH0001820021300309C00	309	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	95	6
3573MH0001820021300310C00	310	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	63	7
3573MH0001820021300311C00	311	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	31	8

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Sol 3573 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Wadakapiapue - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3573MH0001820011300313C00				
best focus image:	3574MH0002270001300322R00	322	motor count:		13964	range (cm):		7.1	
range map product:	3574MH0002270001300323S00	323	acquired sequence:		mhli00182		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	25-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3573		focus merged on sol:		3574
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3573MH0001820021300314C00	314	13868	7.80	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	255	1
3573MH0001820021300315C00	315	13892	7.61	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	223	2
3573MH0001820021300316C00	316	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	191	3
3573MH0001820021300317C00	317	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	159	4
3573MH0001820021300318C00	318	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	127	5
3573MH0001820021300319C00	319	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	95	6
3573MH0001820021300320C00	320	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	63	7
3573MH0001820021300321C00	321	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3575 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3575MH0001730011300335C00		
best focus image:	3575MH0001700001300432R00	432		motor count:		14000	range (cm):	6.8	
range map product:	3575MH0001700001300433S00	433		acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3575	focus merged on sol:		3575	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3575MH0001730021300336C00	336	13880	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1
3575MH0001730021300337C00	337	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	223	2
3575MH0001730021300338C00	338	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3575MH0001730021300339C00	339	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3575MH0001730021300340C00	340	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3575MH0001730021300341C00	341	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3575MH0001730021300342C00	342	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3575MH0001730021300343C00	343	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3575 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3575MH0001730011300345C00		
best focus image:	3575MH0001700001300430R00	430		motor count:		14001	range (cm):	6.8	
range map product:	3575MH0001700001300431S00	431		acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3575	focus merged on sol:		3575	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3575MH0001730021300346C00	346	13881	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1
3575MH0001730021300347C00	347	13911	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	223	2
3575MH0001730021300348C00	348	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3575MH0001730021300349C00	349	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3575MH0001730021300350C00	350	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3575MH0001730021300351C00	351	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3575MH0001730021300352C00	352	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3575MH0001730021300353C00	353	14091	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3575 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3575MH0001730011300355C00				
best focus image:	3575MH0001700001300428R00	428	motor count:		13997	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3575MH0001700001300429S00	429	acquired sequence:		mhli00173		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	27-Aug-22	merge sequence:		mhli00170		merge type: Basic			
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3575	focus merged on sol:		3575	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3575MH0001730021300356C00	356	13877	7.73	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	255	1
3575MH0001730021300357C00	357	13907	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
3575MH0001730021300358C00	358	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
3575MH0001730021300359C00	359	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3575MH0001730021300360C00	360	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3575MH0001730021300361C00	361	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3575MH0001730021300362C00	362	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3575MH0001730021300363C00	363	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3575 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3575MH0001730011300367C00				
best focus image:	3575MH0001700001300426R00	426	motor count:		14014	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3575MH0001700001300427S00	427	acquired sequence:		mhli00173		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	27-Aug-22	merge sequence:		mhli00170		merge type: Basic			
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3575	focus merged on sol:		3575	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3575MH0001730021300368C00	368	13894	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3575MH0001730021300369C00	369	13924	7.37	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3575MH0001730021300370C00	370	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
3575MH0001730021300371C00	371	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3575MH0001730021300372C00	372	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3575MH0001730021300373C00	373	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
3575MH0001730021300374C00	374	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3575MH0001730021300375C00	375	14104	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3575 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3575MH0001730011300377C00				
best focus image:	3575MH0001700001300424R00	424	motor count:		14016	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3575MH0001700001300425S00	425	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3575	focus merged on sol:		3575	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3575MH0001730021300378C00	378	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3575MH0001730021300379C00	379	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3575MH0001730021300380C00	380	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3575MH0001730021300381C00	381	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3575MH0001730021300382C00	382	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3575MH0001730021300383C00	383	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
3575MH0001730021300384C00	384	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3575MH0001730021300385C00	385	14106	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3575 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nova_Estrela - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3575MH0003020011300387C00				
best focus image:	3575MH0001700001300422R00	422	motor count:		14720	range (cm):		3.7	
range map product:	3575MH0001700001300423S00	423	acquired sequence:		mhli00302	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3575	focus merged on sol:		3575	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3575MH0003020021300388C00	388	14600	4.09	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	255	1
3575MH0003020021300389C00	389	14630	3.99	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	223	2
3575MH0003020021300390C00	390	14660	3.90	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	191	3
3575MH0003020021300391C00	391	14690	3.81	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	159	4
3575MH0003020021300392C00	392	14720	3.73	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	127	5
3575MH0003020021300393C00	393	14750	3.64	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	95	6
3575MH0003020021300394C00	394	14780	3.56	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	63	7
3575MH0003020021300395C00	395	14810	3.48	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3575 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Enamuna - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3575MH0003060011300399C00				
best focus image:	3575MH0001700001300420R00	420	motor count:		14252	range (cm):		5.4	
range map product:	3575MH0001700001300421S00	421	acquired sequence:		mhli00306	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3575	focus merged on sol:		3575	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3575MH0003060021300400C00	400	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	255	1
3575MH0003060021300401C00	401	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	223	2
3575MH0003060021300402C00	402	14144	5.99	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	191	3
3575MH0003060021300403C00	403	14198	5.70	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	159	4
3575MH0003060021300404C00	404	14252	5.44	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	127	5
3575MH0003060021300405C00	405	14306	5.19	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	95	6
3575MH0003060021300406C00	406	14360	4.96	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	63	7
3575MH0003060021300407C00	407	14414	4.74	-0.1	0.1	23.6	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3575 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Enamuna - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3575MH0003060011300409C00				
best focus image:	3575MH0001700001300418R00	418	motor count:		14277	range (cm):		5.3	
range map product:	3575MH0001700001300419S00	419	acquired sequence:		mhli00306	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3575	focus merged on sol:		3575	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3575MH0003060021300410C00	410	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	255	1
3575MH0003060021300411C00	411	14115	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	223	2
3575MH0003060021300412C00	412	14169	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	191	3
3575MH0003060021300413C00	413	14223	5.58	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	159	4
3575MH0003060021300414C00	414	14277	5.32	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	127	5
3575MH0003060021300415C00	415	14331	5.08	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	95	6
3575MH0003060021300416C00	416	14385	4.86	-0.1	0.1	24.0	0.4	63	7
3575MH0003060021300417C00	417	14439	4.65	-0.1	0.1	23.3	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3578 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Jacamim - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3578MH0001680011300437C00				
best focus image:	3578MH0001710001300525R00	525	motor count:		14009	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3578MH0001710001300526S00	526	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	30-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3578	focus merged on sol:		3578	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3578MH0001680021300438C00	438	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
3578MH0001680021300439C00	439	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3578MH0001680021300440C00	440	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3578MH0001680021300441C00	441	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3578MH0001680021300442C00	442	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3578MH0001680021300443C00	443	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3578MH0001680021300444C00	444	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3578MH0001680021300445C00	445	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3578 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Jacamim - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3578MH0001680011300447C00				
best focus image:	3578MH0001710001300523R00	523	motor count:		14013	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3578MH0001710001300524S00	524	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	30-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3578	focus merged on sol:		3578	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3578MH0001680021300448C00	448	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
3578MH0001680021300449C00	449	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
3578MH0001680021300450C00	450	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
3578MH0001680021300451C00	451	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
3578MH0001680021300452C00	452	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3578MH0001680021300453C00	453	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3578MH0001680021300454C00	454	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3578MH0001680021300455C00	455	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3578 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Jacamim - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3578MH0004260011300457C00				
best focus image:	3578MH0001710001300521R00	521	motor count:		15139	range (cm):		2.8	
range map product:	3578MH0001710001300522S00	522	acquired sequence:		mhli00426	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	30-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3578	focus merged on sol:		3578	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3578MH0004260021300458C00	458	14947	3.16	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	255	1
3578MH0004260021300459C00	459	14995	3.05	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	223	2
3578MH0004260021300460C00	460	15043	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	191	3
3578MH0004260021300461C00	461	15091	2.85	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	159	4
3578MH0004260021300462C00	462	15139	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	127	5
3578MH0004260021300463C00	463	15187	2.67	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	95	6
3578MH0004260021300464C00	464	15235	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	63	7
3578MH0004260021300465C00	465	15283	2.50	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3578 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Micobie - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3578MH0008340011300470C00				
best focus image:	3578MH0001710001300519R00	519	motor count:		14017	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3578MH0001710001300520S00	520	acquired sequence:		mhli00834	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	30-Aug-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3578	focus merged on sol:		3578	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3578MH0008340031300472C00	472	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
3578MH0008340031300473C00	473	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
3578MH0008340031300474C00	474	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
3578MH0008340031300475C00	475	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3578MH0008340031300476C00	476	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3578MH0008340031300477C00	477	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
3578MH0008340031300478C00	478	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3578MH0008340031300479C00	479	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3578 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Micobie - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3578MH0008340011300481C00				
best focus image:	3578MH0001710001300517R00	517	motor count:		14026	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3578MH0001710001300518S00	518	acquired sequence:		mhli00834		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	30-Aug-22		merge sequence:		mhli00171		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3578		focus merged on sol:		3578
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3578MH0008340031300483C00	483	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
3578MH0008340031300484C00	484	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
3578MH0008340031300485C00	485	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
3578MH0008340031300486C00	486	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	159	4
3578MH0008340031300487C00	487	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
3578MH0008340031300488C00	488	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
3578MH0008340031300489C00	489	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3578MH0008340031300490C00	490	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3578 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Micobie - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3578MH0008350011300492C00				
best focus image:	3578MH0001710001300515R00	515	motor count:		15161	range (cm):		2.7	
range map product:	3578MH0001710001300516S00	516	acquired sequence:		mhli00835		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	30-Aug-22		merge sequence:		mhli00171		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3578		focus merged on sol:		3578
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3578MH0008350031300494C00	494	15041	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	255	1
3578MH0008350031300495C00	495	15071	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	223	2
3578MH0008350031300496C00	496	15101	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	191	3
3578MH0008350031300497C00	497	15131	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	159	4
3578MH0008350031300498C00	498	15161	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	127	5
3578MH0008350031300499C00	499	15191	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	95	6
3578MH0008350031300500C00	500	15221	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	63	7
3578MH0008350031300501C00	501	15251	2.56	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3578 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Micobie - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3578MH0008340011300503C00				
best focus image:	3578MH0001710001300513R00	513	motor count:		14012	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3578MH0001710001300514S00	514	acquired sequence:		mhli00834		stack type:		Relative
acquired on date:	30-Aug-22		merge sequence:		mhli00171		merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3578		focus merged on sol:		3578
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3578MH0008340031300505C00	505	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
3578MH0008340031300506C00	506	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
3578MH0008340031300507C00	507	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3578MH0008340031300508C00	508	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
3578MH0008340031300509C00	509	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3578MH0008340031300510C00	510	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3578MH0008340031300511C00	511	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3578MH0008340031300512C00	512	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3583 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Marie_Island - ~25 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3583MH0008550011300528C00				
best focus image:	3590MH0002270001300589R00	589	motor count:		13006	range (cm):		27.2	
range map product:	3590MH0002270001300590S00	590	acquired sequence:		mhli00855		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	4-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3583	focus merged on sol:		3590	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3583MH0008550021300529C00	529	12886	37.49	-3.4	4.2	138.9	13.4	255	1
3583MH0008550021300530C00	530	12916	34.31	-2.9	3.5	127.7	11.2	223	2
3583MH0008550021300531C00	531	12946	31.59	-2.5	2.9	118.1	9.5	191	3
3583MH0008550021300532C00	532	12976	29.25	-2.1	2.5	109.9	8.1	159	4
3583MH0008550021300533C00	533	13006	27.21	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	127	5
3583MH0008550021300534C00	534	13036	25.41	-1.6	1.8	96.3	6.1	95	6
3583MH0008550021300535C00	535	13066	23.82	-1.4	1.6	90.7	5.3	63	7
3583MH0008550021300536C00	536	13096	22.40	-1.3	1.4	85.7	4.7	31	8

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Sol 3583 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Branco - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3583MH0003060011300540C00				
best focus image:	3590MH0002270001300587R00	587	motor count:		13959	range (cm):		7.1	
range map product:	3590MH0002270001300588S00	588	acquired sequence:		mhli00306		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	4-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3583	focus merged on sol:		3590	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3583MH0003060021300541C00	541	13743	8.90	-0.3	0.2	38.2	0.8	255	1
3583MH0003060021300542C00	542	13797	8.40	-0.2	0.2	36.5	0.8	223	2
3583MH0003060021300543C00	543	13851	7.94	-0.2	0.2	34.8	0.7	191	3
3583MH0003060021300544C00	544	13905	7.51	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	159	4
3583MH0003060021300545C00	545	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	127	5
3583MH0003060021300546C00	546	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
3583MH0003060021300547C00	547	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3583MH0003060021300548C00	548	14121	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3583 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Branco - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3583MH0003060011300550C00				
best focus image:	3590MH0002270001300585R00	585	motor count:		13978	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3590MH0002270001300586S00	586	acquired sequence:		mhli00306	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	4-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3583	focus merged on sol:		3590	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3583MH0003060021300551C00	551	13762	8.72	-0.2	0.2	37.6	0.8	255	1
3583MH0003060021300552C00	552	13816	8.23	-0.2	0.2	35.9	0.8	223	2
3583MH0003060021300553C00	553	13870	7.78	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	191	3
3583MH0003060021300554C00	554	13924	7.37	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	159	4
3583MH0003060021300555C00	555	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
3583MH0003060021300556C00	556	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3583MH0003060021300557C00	557	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3583MH0003060021300558C00	558	14140	6.01	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3583 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Machado - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3583MH0002990011300562C00				
best focus image:	3590MH0002270001300583R00	583	motor count:		13991	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3590MH0002270001300584S00	584	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	4-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3583	focus merged on sol:		3590	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3583MH0002990021300563C00	563	13847	7.97	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	255	1
3583MH0002990021300564C00	564	13883	7.68	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
3583MH0002990021300565C00	565	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	191	3
3583MH0002990021300566C00	566	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	159	4
3583MH0002990021300567C00	567	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3583MH0002990021300568C00	568	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3583MH0002990021300569C00	569	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3583MH0002990021300570C00	570	14099	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3583 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Machado - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3583MH0002990011300572C00				
best focus image:	3590MH0002270001300581R00	581	motor count:		13989	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3590MH0002270001300582S00	582	acquired sequence:		mhli00299		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	4-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3583	focus merged on sol:		3590	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3583MH0002990021300573C00	573	13845	7.98	-0.2	0.2	35.0	0.7	255	1
3583MH0002990021300574C00	574	13881	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	223	2
3583MH0002990021300575C00	575	13917	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	191	3
3583MH0002990021300576C00	576	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	159	4
3583MH0002990021300577C00	577	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3583MH0002990021300578C00	578	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3583MH0002990021300579C00	579	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3583MH0002990021300580C00	580	14097	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3592 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Piabas - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3592MH0003630011300594C00				
best focus image:	3592MH0002650001300615R00	615	motor count:		14115	range (cm):		6.1	
range map product:	3592MH0002650001300616S00	616	acquired sequence:		mhli00363	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	13-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		72	acquired on sol:		3592	focus merged on sol:		3592	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3592MH0003630021300595C00	595	13827	8.13	-0.2	0.2	35.5	0.7	255	1
3592MH0003630021300596C00	596	13899	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	223	2
3592MH0003630021300597C00	597	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3592MH0003630021300598C00	598	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	159	4
3592MH0003630021300599C00	599	14115	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	127	5
3592MH0003630021300600C00	600	14187	5.76	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	95	6
3592MH0003630021300601C00	601	14259	5.41	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	63	7
3592MH0003630021300602C00	602	14331	5.08	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3592 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Piabas - stereo-2 - ~3 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3592MH0003630011300604C00				
best focus image:	3592MH0002650001300613R00	613	motor count:		14410	range (cm):		4.8	
range map product:	3592MH0002650001300614S00	614	acquired sequence:		mhli00363	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	13-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		72	acquired on sol:		3592	focus merged on sol:		3592	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3592MH0003630021300605C00	605	14122	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	255	1
3592MH0003630021300606C00	606	14194	5.72	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	223	2
3592MH0003630021300607C00	607	14266	5.37	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	191	3
3592MH0003630021300608C00	608	14338	5.05	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	159	4
3592MH0003630021300609C00	609	14410	4.76	-0.1	0.1	23.7	0.3	127	5
3592MH0003630021300610C00	610	14482	4.49	-0.1	0.1	22.7	0.3	95	6
3592MH0003630021300611C00	611	14554	4.24	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	63	7
3592MH0003630021300612C00	612	14626	4.00	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3594 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tiger_Pond - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3594MH0006730011300620C00				
best focus image:	3594MH0002270001300677R00	677	motor count:		13998	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3594MH0002270001300678S00	678	acquired sequence:		mhli00673	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	15-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		84	acquired on sol:		3594	focus merged on sol:		3594	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3594MH0006730021300621C00	621	13662	9.74	-0.3	0.3	41.2	1.0	255	1
3594MH0006730021300622C00	622	13746	8.87	-0.2	0.2	38.1	0.8	223	2
3594MH0006730021300623C00	623	13830	8.11	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	191	3
3594MH0006730021300624C00	624	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	159	4
3594MH0006730021300625C00	625	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3594MH0006730021300626C00	626	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	95	6
3594MH0006730021300627C00	627	14166	5.87	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	63	7
3594MH0006730021300628C00	628	14250	5.45	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3594 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tiger_Pond - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3594MH0006730011300630C00				
best focus image:	3594MH0002270001300675R00	675	motor count:		14003	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3594MH0002270001300676S00	676	acquired sequence:		mhli00673	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	15-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		84	acquired on sol:		3594	focus merged on sol:		3594	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3594MH0006730021300631C00	631	13667	9.68	-0.3	0.3	41.0	1.0	255	1
3594MH0006730021300632C00	632	13751	8.82	-0.2	0.2	37.9	0.8	223	2
3594MH0006730021300633C00	633	13835	8.07	-0.2	0.2	35.3	0.7	191	3
3594MH0006730021300634C00	634	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	159	4
3594MH0006730021300635C00	635	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3594MH0006730021300636C00	636	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	95	6
3594MH0006730021300637C00	637	14171	5.84	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	63	7
3594MH0006730021300638C00	638	14255	5.42	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3594 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target La_Mata - ~9 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3594MH0002910011300640C00				
best focus image:	3594MH0002270001300673R00	673	motor count:		13547	range (cm):		11.2	
range map product:	3594MH0002270001300674S00	674	acquired sequence:		mhli00291	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	15-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3594	focus merged on sol:		3594	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3594MH0002910021300641C00	641	13403	13.49	-0.5	0.5	54.4	1.8	255	1
3594MH0002910021300642C00	642	13439	12.84	-0.5	0.5	52.1	1.6	223	2
3594MH0002910021300643C00	643	13475	12.24	-0.4	0.4	50.0	1.5	191	3
3594MH0002910021300644C00	644	13511	11.68	-0.4	0.4	48.0	1.4	159	4
3594MH0002910021300645C00	645	13547	11.17	-0.4	0.4	46.2	1.3	127	5
3594MH0002910021300646C00	646	13583	10.69	-0.3	0.3	44.5	1.1	95	6
3594MH0002910021300647C00	647	13619	10.24	-0.3	0.3	42.9	1.1	63	7
3594MH0002910021300648C00	648	13655	9.82	-0.3	0.3	41.5	1.0	31	8

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Sol 3594 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target La_Mata - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3594MH0003080011300650C00				
best focus image:	3594MH0002270001300671R00	671	motor count:		14123	range (cm):		6.1	
range map product:	3594MH0002270001300672S00	672	acquired sequence:		mhli00308	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	15-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3594	focus merged on sol:		3594	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3594MH0003080021300651C00	651	13859	7.87	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	255	1
3594MH0003080021300652C00	652	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3594MH0003080021300653C00	653	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
3594MH0003080021300654C00	654	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	159	4
3594MH0003080021300655C00	655	14123	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	127	5
3594MH0003080021300656C00	656	14189	5.75	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	95	6
3594MH0003080021300657C00	657	14255	5.42	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	63	7
3594MH0003080021300658C00	658	14321	5.13	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3594 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target La_Mata - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3594MH0003080011300660C00				
best focus image:	3594MH0002270001300669R00	669	motor count:		14142	range (cm):		6.0	
range map product:	3594MH0002270001300670S00	670	acquired sequence:		mhli00308	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	15-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3594	focus merged on sol:		3594	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3594MH0003080021300661C00	661	13878	7.72	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	255	1
3594MH0003080021300662C00	662	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3594MH0003080021300663C00	663	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
3594MH0003080021300664C00	664	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	159	4
3594MH0003080021300665C00	665	14142	6.00	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	127	5
3594MH0003080021300666C00	666	14208	5.65	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	95	6
3594MH0003080021300667C00	667	14274	5.34	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	63	7
3594MH0003080021300668C00	668	14340	5.04	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3596 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Corona_Falls - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3596MH0002240011300686C00				
best focus image:	3596MH0001630001300761R00	761	motor count:		14024	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3596MH0001630001300762S00	762	acquired sequence:		mhli00224		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	18-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3596	focus merged on sol:		3596	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3596MH0002240021300687C00	687	13856	7.89	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	255	1
3596MH0002240021300688C00	688	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	223	2
3596MH0002240021300689C00	689	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3596MH0002240021300690C00	690	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3596MH0002240021300691C00	691	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
3596MH0002240021300692C00	692	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	95	6
3596MH0002240021300693C00	693	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7
3596MH0002240021300694C00	694	14150	5.95	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3596 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Corona_Falls - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3596MH0002240011300696C00				
best focus image:	3596MH0001630001300759R00	759	motor count:		14028	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3596MH0001630001300760S00	760	acquired sequence:		mhli00224		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	18-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3596	focus merged on sol:		3596	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3596MH0002240021300697C00	697	13860	7.86	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	255	1
3596MH0002240021300698C00	698	13902	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	223	2
3596MH0002240021300699C00	699	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3596MH0002240021300700C00	700	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3596MH0002240021300701C00	701	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
3596MH0002240021300702C00	702	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	95	6
3596MH0002240021300703C00	703	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	63	7
3596MH0002240021300704C00	704	14154	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3596 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Corona_Falls - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3596MH0003070011300706C00				
best focus image:	3596MH0001630001300757R00	757	motor count:		14738	range (cm):		3.7	
range map product:	3596MH0001630001300758S00	758	acquired sequence:		mhli00307	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	18-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		72	acquired on sol:		3596	focus merged on sol:		3596	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3596MH0003070021300707C00	707	14450	4.61	-0.1	0.1	23.1	0.3	255	1
3596MH0003070021300708C00	708	14522	4.35	-0.1	0.1	22.2	0.3	223	2
3596MH0003070021300709C00	709	14594	4.11	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	191	3
3596MH0003070021300710C00	710	14666	3.88	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	159	4
3596MH0003070021300711C00	711	14738	3.68	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	127	5
3596MH0003070021300712C00	712	14810	3.48	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	95	6
3596MH0003070021300713C00	713	14882	3.31	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	63	7
3596MH0003070021300714C00	714	14954	3.14	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3596 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Marshall_Falls - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3596MH0006990011300719C00				
best focus image:	3596MH0001630001300755R00	755	motor count:		14027	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3596MH0001630001300756S00	756	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	18-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3596	focus merged on sol:		3596	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3596MH0006990031300721C00	721	13907	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
3596MH0006990031300722C00	722	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
3596MH0006990031300723C00	723	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3596MH0006990031300724C00	724	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
3596MH0006990031300725C00	725	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
3596MH0006990031300726C00	726	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
3596MH0006990031300727C00	727	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3596MH0006990031300728C00	728	14117	6.13	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3596 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Marshall_Falls - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3596MH0006990011300730C00				
best focus image:	3596MH0001630001300753R00	753	motor count:		14030	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3596MH0001630001300754S00	754	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	18-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3596	focus merged on sol:		3596	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3596MH0006990031300732C00	732	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
3596MH0006990031300733C00	733	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
3596MH0006990031300734C00	734	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3596MH0006990031300735C00	735	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3596MH0006990031300736C00	736	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3596MH0006990031300737C00	737	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
3596MH0006990031300738C00	738	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
3596MH0006990031300739C00	739	14120	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3596 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Marshall_Falls - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3596MH0008230011300741C00				
best focus image:	3596MH0001630001300751R00	751	motor count:		15178	range (cm):		2.7	
range map product:	3596MH0001630001300752S00	752	acquired sequence:		mhli00823	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	18-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3596	focus merged on sol:		3596	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3596MH0008230031300743C00	743	14938	3.18	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	255	1
3596MH0008230031300744C00	744	14998	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	223	2
3596MH0008230031300745C00	745	15058	2.92	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	191	3
3596MH0008230031300746C00	746	15118	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	159	4
3596MH0008230031300747C00	747	15178	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	127	5
3596MH0008230031300748C00	748	15238	2.58	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	95	6
3596MH0008230031300749C00	749	15298	2.48	0.0	0.1	15.6	0.2	63	7
3596MH0008230031300750C00	750	15358	2.38	0.0	0.1	15.3	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3599 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target El_Triunfo - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3599MH0008550011300764C00				
best focus image:	3599MH0005360001300873R00	873	motor count:		13026	range (cm):		26.0	
range map product:	3599MH0005360001300874S00	874	acquired sequence:		mhli00855	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	21-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3599	focus merged on sol:		3599	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3599MH0008550021300765C00	765	12906	35.31	-3.1	3.7	131.2	11.9	255	1
3599MH0008550021300766C00	766	12936	32.45	-2.6	3.1	121.1	10.0	223	2
3599MH0008550021300767C00	767	12966	29.99	-2.2	2.6	112.5	8.5	191	3
3599MH0008550021300768C00	768	12996	27.86	-2.0	2.2	105.0	7.3	159	4
3599MH0008550021300769C00	769	13026	25.99	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	127	5
3599MH0008550021300770C00	770	13056	24.33	-1.5	1.7	92.5	5.6	95	6
3599MH0008550021300771C00	771	13086	22.85	-1.3	1.5	87.3	4.9	63	7
3599MH0008550021300772C00	772	13116	21.53	-1.2	1.3	82.7	4.4	31	8

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Sol 3599 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target El_Triunfo - stereo-1 - ~9 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3599MH0002910011300774C00				
best focus image:	3599MH0005360001300871R00	871	motor count:		13556	range (cm):		11.0	
range map product:	3599MH0005360001300872S00	872	acquired sequence:		mhli00291	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	21-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3599	focus merged on sol:		3599	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3599MH0002910021300775C00	775	13412	13.32	-0.5	0.5	53.8	1.7	255	1
3599MH0002910021300776C00	776	13448	12.69	-0.5	0.5	51.6	1.6	223	2
3599MH0002910021300777C00	777	13484	12.10	-0.4	0.4	49.5	1.4	191	3
3599MH0002910021300778C00	778	13520	11.55	-0.4	0.4	47.6	1.3	159	4
3599MH0002910021300779C00	779	13556	11.04	-0.4	0.3	45.8	1.2	127	5
3599MH0002910021300780C00	780	13592	10.57	-0.3	0.3	44.1	1.1	95	6
3599MH0002910021300781C00	781	13628	10.13	-0.3	0.3	42.6	1.1	63	7
3599MH0002910021300782C00	782	13664	9.72	-0.3	0.3	41.1	1.0	31	8

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Sol 3599 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target El_Triunfo - stereo-2 - ~9 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3599MH0002910011300784C00				
best focus image:	3599MH0005360001300869R00	869	motor count:		13571	range (cm):		10.8	
range map product:	3599MH0005360001300870S00	870	acquired sequence:		mhli00291		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	21-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3599	focus merged on sol:		3599	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3599MH0002910021300785C00	785	13427	13.05	-0.5	0.5	52.8	1.7	255	1
3599MH0002910021300786C00	786	13463	12.44	-0.4	0.4	50.7	1.5	223	2
3599MH0002910021300787C00	787	13499	11.87	-0.4	0.4	48.7	1.4	191	3
3599MH0002910021300788C00	788	13535	11.34	-0.4	0.4	46.8	1.3	159	4
3599MH0002910021300789C00	789	13571	10.84	-0.3	0.3	45.1	1.2	127	5
3599MH0002910021300790C00	790	13607	10.38	-0.3	0.3	43.5	1.1	95	6
3599MH0002910021300791C00	791	13643	9.96	-0.3	0.3	41.9	1.0	63	7
3599MH0002910021300792C00	792	13679	9.55	-0.3	0.3	40.5	1.0	31	8

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Sol 3599 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3599MH0001730011300796C00				
best focus image:	3599MH0005360001300867R00	867	motor count:		13973	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3599MH0005360001300868S00	868	acquired sequence:		mhli00173		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	21-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3599	focus merged on sol:		3599	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3599MH0001730021300797C00	797	13853	7.92	-0.2	0.2	34.8	0.7	255	1
3599MH0001730021300798C00	798	13883	7.68	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
3599MH0001730021300799C00	799	13913	7.45	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	191	3
3599MH0001730021300800C00	800	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	159	4
3599MH0001730021300801C00	801	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	127	5
3599MH0001730021300802C00	802	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
3599MH0001730021300803C00	803	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
3599MH0001730021300804C00	804	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3599 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3599MH0001730011300806C00				
best focus image:	3599MH0005360001300865R00	865	motor count:		13965	range (cm):		7.1	
range map product:	3599MH0005360001300866S00	866	acquired sequence:		mhli00173		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	21-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3599	focus merged on sol:		3599	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3599MH0001730021300807C00	807	13845	7.98	-0.2	0.2	35.0	0.7	255	1
3599MH0001730021300808C00	808	13875	7.74	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	223	2
3599MH0001730021300809C00	809	13905	7.51	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	191	3
3599MH0001730021300810C00	810	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	159	4
3599MH0001730021300811C00	811	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	127	5
3599MH0001730021300812C00	812	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	95	6
3599MH0001730021300813C00	813	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
3599MH0001730021300814C00	814	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3599 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nova_Cintra - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3599MH0003370011300816C00				
best focus image:	3599MH0005360001300863R00	863	motor count:		14639	range (cm):		4.0	
range map product:	3599MH0005360001300864S00	864	acquired sequence:		mhli00337		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	21-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3599	focus merged on sol:		3599	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3599MH0003370021300817C00	817	14471	4.53	-0.1	0.1	22.8	0.3	255	1
3599MH0003370021300818C00	818	14513	4.38	-0.1	0.1	22.3	0.3	223	2
3599MH0003370021300819C00	819	14555	4.23	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	191	3
3599MH0003370021300820C00	820	14597	4.10	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	159	4
3599MH0003370021300821C00	821	14639	3.96	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	127	5
3599MH0003370021300822C00	822	14681	3.84	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	95	6
3599MH0003370021300823C00	823	14723	3.72	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	63	7
3599MH0003370021300824C00	824	14765	3.60	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3599 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Pirara - stereo-1 - ~6 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3599MH0002990011300828C00				
best focus image:	3599MH0005360001300861R00	861	motor count:		13831	range (cm):	8.1		
range map product:	3599MH0005360001300862S00	862	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	21-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3599	focus merged on sol:		3599	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3599MH0002990021300829C00	829	13687	9.47	-0.3	0.3	40.2	0.9	255	1
3599MH0002990021300830C00	830	13723	9.09	-0.3	0.2	38.9	0.9	223	2
3599MH0002990021300831C00	831	13759	8.74	-0.2	0.2	37.7	0.8	191	3
3599MH0002990021300832C00	832	13795	8.41	-0.2	0.2	36.5	0.8	159	4
3599MH0002990021300833C00	833	13831	8.10	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	127	5
3599MH0002990021300834C00	834	13867	7.81	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	95	6
3599MH0002990021300835C00	835	13903	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	63	7
3599MH0002990021300836C00	836	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	31	8

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Sol 3599 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Pirara - stereo-2 - ~6 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3599MH0002990011300838C00				
best focus image:	3599MH0005360001300859R00	859	motor count:		13831	range (cm):	8.1		
range map product:	3599MH0005360001300860S00	860	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	21-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3599	focus merged on sol:		3599	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3599MH0002990021300839C00	839	13687	9.47	-0.3	0.3	40.2	0.9	255	1
3599MH0002990021300840C00	840	13723	9.09	-0.3	0.2	38.9	0.9	223	2
3599MH0002990021300841C00	841	13759	8.74	-0.2	0.2	37.7	0.8	191	3
3599MH0002990021300842C00	842	13795	8.41	-0.2	0.2	36.5	0.8	159	4
3599MH0002990021300843C00	843	13831	8.10	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	127	5
3599MH0002990021300844C00	844	13867	7.81	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	95	6
3599MH0002990021300845C00	845	13903	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	63	7
3599MH0002990021300846C00	846	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	31	8

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Sol 3599 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Pirara - ~3 cm standoff									
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3599MH0003370011300848C00					
best focus image:		3599MH0005360001300857R00		857		motor count:		14344		range (cm): 5.0	
range map product:		3599MH0005360001300858S00		858		acquired sequence:		mhli00337		stack type: Relative	
acquired on date:		21-Sep-22				merge sequence:		mhli00536		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:			42	acquired on sol:		3599		focus merged on sol:		3599	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8		
				near	far						
3599MH0003370021300849C00	849	14176	5.82	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	255	1		
3599MH0003370021300850C00	850	14218	5.60	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	223	2		
3599MH0003370021300851C00	851	14260	5.40	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	191	3		
3599MH0003370021300852C00	852	14302	5.21	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	159	4		
3599MH0003370021300853C00	853	14344	5.03	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	127	5		
3599MH0003370021300854C00	854	14386	4.85	-0.1	0.1	24.0	0.4	95	6		
3599MH0003370021300855C00	855	14428	4.69	-0.1	0.1	23.4	0.3	63	7		
3599MH0003370021300856C00	856	14470	4.53	-0.1	0.1	22.8	0.3	31	8		

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Sol 3601 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Cuarane - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3601MH0001820011300878C00				
best focus image:	3601MH0001930001300911R00	911	motor count:		13990	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3601MH0001930001300912S00	912	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	23-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3601	focus merged on sol:		3601	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3601MH0001820021300879C00	879	13894	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3601MH0001820021300880C00	880	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
3601MH0001820021300881C00	881	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3601MH0001820021300882C00	882	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3601MH0001820021300883C00	883	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3601MH0001820021300884C00	884	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
3601MH0001820021300885C00	885	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3601MH0001820021300886C00	886	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3601 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Cuarane - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3601MH0001820011300888C00				
best focus image:	3601MH0001930001300909R00	909	motor count:		13991	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3601MH0001930001300910S00	910	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	23-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3601	focus merged on sol:		3601	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3601MH0001820021300889C00	889	13895	7.59	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3601MH0001820021300890C00	890	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
3601MH0001820021300891C00	891	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3601MH0001820021300892C00	892	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3601MH0001820021300893C00	893	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3601MH0001820021300894C00	894	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3601MH0001820021300895C00	895	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3601MH0001820021300896C00	896	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3601 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Cauarane - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3601MH0008380011300898C00				
best focus image:	3601MH0001930001300907R00	907	motor count:		15072	range (cm):		2.9	
range map product:	3601MH0001930001300908S00	908	acquired sequence:		mhli00838	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	23-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3601	focus merged on sol:		3601	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3601MH0008380021300899C00	899	14808	3.49	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	255	1
3601MH0008380021300900C00	900	14874	3.33	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	223	2
3601MH0008380021300901C00	901	14940	3.17	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	191	3
3601MH0008380021300902C00	902	15006	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	159	4
3601MH0008380021300903C00	903	15072	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	127	5
3601MH0008380021300904C00	904	15138	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	95	6
3601MH0008380021300905C00	905	15204	2.64	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	63	7
3601MH0008380021300906C00	906	15270	2.53	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3603 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tapirapeco - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3603MH0002240011300916C00				
best focus image:	3603MH0001630001300989R00	989	motor count:		14232	range (cm):		5.5	
range map product:	3603MH0001630001300990S00	990	acquired sequence:		mhli00224	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	25-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3603	focus merged on sol:		3603	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3603MH0002240021300917C00	917	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	255	1
3603MH0002240021300918C00	918	14106	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	223	2
3603MH0002240021300919C00	919	14148	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	191	3
3603MH0002240021300920C00	920	14190	5.74	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	159	4
3603MH0002240021300921C00	921	14232	5.53	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	127	5
3603MH0002240021300922C00	922	14274	5.34	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	95	6
3603MH0002240021300923C00	923	14316	5.15	-0.1	0.1	25.0	0.4	63	7
3603MH0002240021300924C00	924	14358	4.97	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3603 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tapirapeco - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3603MH0002240011300926C00				
best focus image:	3603MH0001630001300987R00	987	motor count:		14236	range (cm):		5.5	
range map product:	3603MH0001630001300988S00	988	acquired sequence:		mhli00224	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	25-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3603	focus merged on sol:		3603	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3603MH0002240021300927C00	927	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	255	1
3603MH0002240021300928C00	928	14110	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	223	2
3603MH0002240021300929C00	929	14152	5.94	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	191	3
3603MH0002240021300930C00	930	14194	5.72	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	159	4
3603MH0002240021300931C00	931	14236	5.52	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	127	5
3603MH0002240021300932C00	932	14278	5.32	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	95	6
3603MH0002240021300933C00	933	14320	5.13	-0.1	0.1	25.0	0.4	63	7
3603MH0002240021300934C00	934	14362	4.95	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3603 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3603MH0001680011300938C00				
best focus image:	3603MH0001630001300985R00	985	motor count:		14164	range (cm):		5.9	
range map product:	3603MH0001630001300986S00	986	acquired sequence:		mhli00168		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	25-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3603	focus merged on sol:		3603	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3603MH0001680021300939C00	939	14092	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	255	1
3603MH0001680021300940C00	940	14110	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	223	2
3603MH0001680021300941C00	941	14128	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	191	3
3603MH0001680021300942C00	942	14146	5.97	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	159	4
3603MH0001680021300943C00	943	14164	5.88	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	127	5
3603MH0001680021300944C00	944	14182	5.78	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	95	6
3603MH0001680021300945C00	945	14200	5.69	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	63	7
3603MH0001680021300946C00	946	14218	5.60	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3603 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3603MH0001680011300948C00				
best focus image:	3603MH0001630001300983R00	983	motor count:		14166	range (cm):		5.9	
range map product:	3603MH0001630001300984S00	984	acquired sequence:		mhli00168		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	25-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3603	focus merged on sol:		3603	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3603MH0001680021300949C00	949	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	255	1
3603MH0001680021300950C00	950	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	223	2
3603MH0001680021300951C00	951	14130	6.06	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	191	3
3603MH0001680021300952C00	952	14148	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	159	4
3603MH0001680021300953C00	953	14166	5.87	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	127	5
3603MH0001680021300954C00	954	14184	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	95	6
3603MH0001680021300955C00	955	14202	5.68	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	63	7
3603MH0001680021300956C00	956	14220	5.59	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3603 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3603MH0001680011300960C00				
best focus image:	3603MH0001630001300981R00	981	motor count:		14186	range (cm):		5.8	
range map product:	3603MH0001630001300982S00	982	acquired sequence:		mhli00168		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	25-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3603	focus merged on sol:		3603	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3603MH0001680021300961C00	961	14114	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	255	1
3603MH0001680021300962C00	962	14132	6.05	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	223	2
3603MH0001680021300963C00	963	14150	5.95	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	191	3
3603MH0001680021300964C00	964	14168	5.86	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	159	4
3603MH0001680021300965C00	965	14186	5.76	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	127	5
3603MH0001680021300966C00	966	14204	5.67	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	95	6
3603MH0001680021300967C00	967	14222	5.58	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	63	7
3603MH0001680021300968C00	968	14240	5.50	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3603 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3603MH0001680011300970C00				
best focus image:	3603MH0001630001300979R00	979	motor count:		14193	range (cm):		5.7	
range map product:	3603MH0001630001300980S00	980	acquired sequence:		mhli00168		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	25-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3603	focus merged on sol:		3603	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3603MH0001680021300971C00	971	14121	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	255	1
3603MH0001680021300972C00	972	14139	6.01	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	223	2
3603MH0001680021300973C00	973	14157	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	191	3
3603MH0001680021300974C00	974	14175	5.82	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	159	4
3603MH0001680021300975C00	975	14193	5.73	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	127	5
3603MH0001680021300976C00	976	14211	5.64	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	95	6
3603MH0001680021300977C00	977	14229	5.55	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	63	7
3603MH0001680021300978C00	978	14247	5.46	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3605 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Tapirapeco - mosaic position 1 of 6 - ~15 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3605MH0008410011300992C00				
best focus image:	3605MH0001630001301061R00	1061	motor count:		13245	range (cm):		17.1	
range map product:	3605MH0001630001301062S00	1062	acquired sequence:		mhli00841		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	27-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3605	focus merged on sol:		3605	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3605MH0008410021300993C00	993	13173	19.36	-1.0	1.0	75.0	3.6	255	1
3605MH0008410021300994C00	994	13191	18.75	-0.9	1.0	72.9	3.3	223	2
3605MH0008410021300995C00	995	13209	18.18	-0.9	0.9	70.9	3.1	191	3
3605MH0008410021300996C00	996	13227	17.63	-0.8	0.9	69.0	3.0	159	4
3605MH0008410021300997C00	997	13245	17.11	-0.8	0.8	67.1	2.8	127	5
3605MH0008410021300998C00	998	13263	16.62	-0.7	0.8	65.4	2.6	95	6
3605MH0008410021300999C00	999	13281	16.15	-0.7	0.7	63.8	2.5	63	7
3605MH0008410021301000C00	1000	13299	15.71	-0.7	0.7	62.2	2.4	31	8

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Sol 3605 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Tapirapeco - mosaic position 2 of 6 - ~15 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3605MH0008410011301002C00				
best focus image:	3605MH0001630001301059R00	1059	motor count:		13242	range (cm):		17.2	
range map product:	3605MH0001630001301060S00	1060	acquired sequence:		mhli00841		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	27-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3605	focus merged on sol:		3605	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3605MH0008410021301003C00	1003	13170	19.46	-1.0	1.1	75.4	3.6	255	1
3605MH0008410021301004C00	1004	13188	18.85	-0.9	1.0	73.3	3.4	223	2
3605MH0008410021301005C00	1005	13206	18.27	-0.9	0.9	71.2	3.2	191	3
3605MH0008410021301006C00	1006	13224	17.72	-0.8	0.9	69.3	3.0	159	4
3605MH0008410021301007C00	1007	13242	17.20	-0.8	0.8	67.4	2.8	127	5
3605MH0008410021301008C00	1008	13260	16.70	-0.7	0.8	65.7	2.7	95	6
3605MH0008410021301009C00	1009	13278	16.23	-0.7	0.7	64.0	2.5	63	7
3605MH0008410021301010C00	1010	13296	15.78	-0.7	0.7	62.4	2.4	31	8

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Sol 3605 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tapirapeco - mosaic position 3 of 6 - ~16 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3605MH0008410011301012C00				
best focus image:	3605MH0001630001301057R00	1057	motor count:		13221	range (cm):		17.8	
range map product:	3605MH0001630001301058S00	1058	acquired sequence:		mhli00841		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	27-Sep-22		merge sequence:		mhli00163		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3605	focus merged on sol:		3605	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3605MH0008410021301013C00	1013	13149	20.22	-1.1	1.1	78.1	3.9	255	1
3605MH0008410021301014C00	1014	13167	19.57	-1.0	1.1	75.8	3.6	223	2
3605MH0008410021301015C00	1015	13185	18.95	-0.9	1.0	73.6	3.4	191	3
3605MH0008410021301016C00	1016	13203	18.36	-0.9	0.9	71.5	3.2	159	4
3605MH0008410021301017C00	1017	13221	17.81	-0.8	0.9	69.6	3.0	127	5
3605MH0008410021301018C00	1018	13239	17.28	-0.8	0.8	67.7	2.8	95	6
3605MH0008410021301019C00	1019	13257	16.78	-0.8	0.8	66.0	2.7	63	7
3605MH0008410021301020C00	1020	13275	16.31	-0.7	0.7	64.3	2.5	31	8

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Sol 3605 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tapirapeco - mosaic position 4 of 6 - ~16 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3605MH0008410011301022C00				
best focus image:	3605MH0001630001301055R00	1055	motor count:		13213	range (cm):		18.1	
range map product:	3605MH0001630001301056S00	1056	acquired sequence:		mhli00841		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	27-Sep-22		merge sequence:		mhli00163		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3605	focus merged on sol:		3605	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3605MH0008410021301023C00	1023	13141	20.53	-1.1	1.2	79.2	4.0	255	1
3605MH0008410021301024C00	1024	13159	19.86	-1.0	1.1	76.8	3.7	223	2
3605MH0008410021301025C00	1025	13177	19.22	-1.0	1.0	74.6	3.5	191	3
3605MH0008410021301026C00	1026	13195	18.62	-0.9	1.0	72.4	3.3	159	4
3605MH0008410021301027C00	1027	13213	18.05	-0.9	0.9	70.4	3.1	127	5
3605MH0008410021301028C00	1028	13231	17.51	-0.8	0.9	68.6	2.9	95	6
3605MH0008410021301029C00	1029	13249	17.00	-0.8	0.8	66.8	2.8	63	7
3605MH0008410021301030C00	1030	13267	16.52	-0.7	0.8	65.0	2.6	31	8

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Sol 3605 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Tapirapeco - mosaic position 5 of 6 - ~16 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3605MH0008410011301032C00				
best focus image:	3605MH0001630001301053R00	1053	motor count:		13218	range (cm):		17.9	
range map product:	3605MH0001630001301054S00	1054	acquired sequence:		mhli00841		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	27-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3605	focus merged on sol:		3605	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3605MH0008410021301033C00	1033	13146	20.34	-1.1	1.2	78.5	3.9	255	1
3605MH0008410021301034C00	1034	13164	19.68	-1.0	1.1	76.2	3.7	223	2
3605MH0008410021301035C00	1035	13182	19.05	-1.0	1.0	74.0	3.4	191	3
3605MH0008410021301036C00	1036	13200	18.46	-0.9	0.9	71.9	3.2	159	4
3605MH0008410021301037C00	1037	13218	17.90	-0.8	0.9	69.9	3.0	127	5
3605MH0008410021301038C00	1038	13236	17.37	-0.8	0.8	68.0	2.9	95	6
3605MH0008410021301039C00	1039	13254	16.87	-0.8	0.8	66.3	2.7	63	7
3605MH0008410021301040C00	1040	13272	16.39	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	31	8

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Sol 3605 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Tapirapeco - mosaic position 6 of 6 - ~16 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3605MH0008410011301042C00				
best focus image:	3605MH0001630001301051R00	1051	motor count:		13228	range (cm):		17.6	
range map product:	3605MH0001630001301052S00	1052	acquired sequence:		mhli00841		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	27-Sep-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3605	focus merged on sol:		3605	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3605MH0008410021301043C00	1043	13156	19.96	-1.0	1.1	77.2	3.8	255	1
3605MH0008410021301044C00	1044	13174	19.32	-1.0	1.0	74.9	3.5	223	2
3605MH0008410021301045C00	1045	13192	18.72	-0.9	1.0	72.8	3.3	191	3
3605MH0008410021301046C00	1046	13210	18.15	-0.9	0.9	70.8	3.1	159	4
3605MH0008410021301047C00	1047	13228	17.60	-0.8	0.9	68.9	2.9	127	5
3605MH0008410021301048C00	1048	13246	17.09	-0.8	0.8	67.0	2.8	95	6
3605MH0008410021301049C00	1049	13264	16.60	-0.7	0.8	65.3	2.6	63	7
3605MH0008410021301050C00	1050	13282	16.13	-0.7	0.7	63.7	2.5	31	8

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Sol 3609 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Canaima - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3609MH0001730011301082C00			
best focus image:	3609MH0001530001301129R00		1129	motor count:		14007	range (cm):	6.8	
range map product:	3609MH0001530001301130S00		1130	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	1-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3609	focus merged on sol:		3609	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3609MH0001730021301083C00	1083	13887	7.65	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
3609MH0001730021301084C00	1084	13917	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
3609MH0001730021301085C00	1085	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3609MH0001730021301086C00	1086	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3609MH0001730021301087C00	1087	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3609MH0001730021301088C00	1088	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
3609MH0001730021301089C00	1089	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3609MH0001730021301090C00	1090	14097	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3609 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Canaima - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3609MH0001730011301092C00			
best focus image:	3609MH0001530001301127R00		1127	motor count:		14009	range (cm):	6.8	
range map product:	3609MH0001530001301128S00		1128	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	1-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3609	focus merged on sol:		3609	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3609MH0001730021301093C00	1093	13889	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
3609MH0001730021301094C00	1094	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
3609MH0001730021301095C00	1095	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3609MH0001730021301096C00	1096	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3609MH0001730021301097C00	1097	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3609MH0001730021301098C00	1098	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
3609MH0001730021301099C00	1099	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3609MH0001730021301100C00	1100	14099	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_November_2022

Sol 3609 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Canaima - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3609MH0006490011301102C00			
best focus image:	3609MH0001530001301125R00		1125	motor count:		15131	range (cm):	2.8	
range map product:	3609MH0001530001301126S00		1126	acquired sequence:		mhli00649	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	1-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		78	acquired on sol:		3609	focus merged on sol:		3609	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3609MH0006490021301103C00	1103	14819	3.46	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	255	1
3609MH0006490021301104C00	1104	14897	3.27	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	223	2
3609MH0006490021301105C00	1105	14975	3.09	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	191	3
3609MH0006490021301106C00	1106	15053	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	159	4
3609MH0006490021301107C00	1107	15131	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	127	5
3609MH0006490021301108C00	1108	15209	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	95	6
3609MH0006490021301109C00	1109	15287	2.50	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	63	7
3609MH0006490021301110C00	1110	15365	2.37	0.0	0.1	15.3	0.2	31	8

updated: 01_November_2022

Sol 3609 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Canaima - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3609MH0001730011301112C00			
best focus image:	3609MH0001530001301123R00		1123	motor count:		14002	range (cm):	6.8	
range map product:	3609MH0001530001301124S00		1124	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	1-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3609	focus merged on sol:		3609	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3609MH0001730021301113C00	1113	13882	7.69	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1
3609MH0001730021301114C00	1114	13912	7.46	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	223	2
3609MH0001730021301115C00	1115	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3609MH0001730021301116C00	1116	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3609MH0001730021301117C00	1117	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3609MH0001730021301118C00	1118	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3609MH0001730021301119C00	1119	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3609MH0001730021301120C00	1120	14092	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

updated: 04_May_2023

Sol 3624 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		Canaima drill cuttings - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3624MH0001520011301138C00				
best focus image:	3624MH0002580001301147R00	1147	motor count:		14218	range (cm):		5.6	
range map product:	3624MH0002580001301148S00	1148	acquired sequence:		mhli00152		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	16-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00258		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3624		focus merged on sol:		3624
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3624MH0001520021301139C00	1139	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	255	1
3624MH0001520021301140C00	1140	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	223	2
3624MH0001520021301141C00	1141	14122	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	191	3
3624MH0001520021301142C00	1142	14170	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	159	4
3624MH0001520021301143C00	1143	14218	5.60	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	127	5
3624MH0001520021301144C00	1144	14266	5.37	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	95	6
3624MH0001520021301145C00	1145	14314	5.16	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	63	7
3624MH0001520021301146C00	1146	14362	4.95	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	31	8

updated: 01_November_2022

Sol 3626 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Bacabal - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3626MH0001730011301152C00				
best focus image:	3626MH0002650001301175R00	1175	motor count:		14046	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3626MH0002650001301176S00	1176	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	18-Oct-22	merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3626	focus merged on sol:		3626	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3626MH0001730021301153C00	1153	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
3626MH0001730021301154C00	1154	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
3626MH0001730021301155C00	1155	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
3626MH0001730021301156C00	1156	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
3626MH0001730021301157C00	1157	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
3626MH0001730021301158C00	1158	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	95	6
3626MH0001730021301159C00	1159	14106	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7
3626MH0001730021301160C00	1160	14136	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_November_2022

Sol 3626 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Bacabal - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3626MH0001730011301162C00				
best focus image:	3626MH0002650001301173R00	1173	motor count:		14048	range (cm):		6.5	
range map product:	3626MH0002650001301174S00	1174	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	18-Oct-22	merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3626	focus merged on sol:		3626	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3626MH0001730021301163C00	1163	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
3626MH0001730021301164C00	1164	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
3626MH0001730021301165C00	1165	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
3626MH0001730021301166C00	1166	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
3626MH0001730021301167C00	1167	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	127	5
3626MH0001730021301168C00	1168	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	95	6
3626MH0001730021301169C00	1169	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7
3626MH0001730021301170C00	1170	14138	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 04_May_2023

Sol 3628 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pacu - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3628MH0001680011301180C00				
best focus image:	3628MH0001930001301213R00	1213	motor count:		13954	range (cm):		7.2	
range map product:	3628MH0001930001301214S00	1214	acquired sequence:		mhli00168		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	20-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3628	focus merged on sol:		3628	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3628MH0001680021301181C00	1181	13882	7.69	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1
3628MH0001680021301182C00	1182	13900	7.55	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	223	2
3628MH0001680021301183C00	1183	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	191	3
3628MH0001680021301184C00	1184	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4
3628MH0001680021301185C00	1185	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	127	5
3628MH0001680021301186C00	1186	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	95	6
3628MH0001680021301187C00	1187	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	63	7
3628MH0001680021301188C00	1188	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	31	8

updated: 04_May_2023

Sol 3628 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pacu - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3628MH0001680011301190C00				
best focus image:	3628MH0001930001301211R00	1211	motor count:		13961	range (cm):		7.1	
range map product:	3628MH0001930001301212S00	1212	acquired sequence:		mhli00168		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	20-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3628	focus merged on sol:		3628	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3628MH0001680021301191C00	1191	13889	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
3628MH0001680021301192C00	1192	13907	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
3628MH0001680021301193C00	1193	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	191	3
3628MH0001680021301194C00	1194	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	159	4
3628MH0001680021301195C00	1195	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	127	5
3628MH0001680021301196C00	1196	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	95	6
3628MH0001680021301197C00	1197	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	63	7
3628MH0001680021301198C00	1198	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	31	8

updated: 04_May_2023

Sol 3628 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pacu - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3628MH0003860011301200C00				
best focus image:	3628MH0001930001301209R00	1209	motor count:		14963	range (cm):		3.1	
range map product:	3628MH0001930001301210S00	1210	acquired sequence:		mhli00386		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	20-Oct-22		merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3628		focus merged on sol:		3628
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3628MH0003860021301201C00	1201	14747	3.65	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	255	1
3628MH0003860021301202C00	1202	14801	3.51	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	223	2
3628MH0003860021301203C00	1203	14855	3.37	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	191	3
3628MH0003860021301204C00	1204	14909	3.24	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	159	4
3628MH0003860021301205C00	1205	14963	3.12	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	127	5
3628MH0003860021301206C00	1206	15017	3.00	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	95	6
3628MH0003860021301207C00	1207	15071	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	63	7
3628MH0003860021301208C00	1208	15125	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	31	8

updated: 28_November_2022

Sol 3630 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Vista_Alegre - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3630MH0001820011301218C00		
best focus image:	3631MH0001530001301265R00	1265		motor count:		14011	range (cm):	6.8	
range map product:	3631MH0001530001301266S00	1266		acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	23-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3630	focus merged on sol:		3631	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3630MH0001820021301219C00	1219	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	255	1
3630MH0001820021301220C00	1220	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
3630MH0001820021301221C00	1221	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
3630MH0001820021301222C00	1222	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3630MH0001820021301223C00	1223	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3630MH0001820021301224C00	1224	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
3630MH0001820021301225C00	1225	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3630MH0001820021301226C00	1226	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

updated: 28_November_2022

Sol 3630 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Vista_Alegre - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3630MH0001820011301228C00		
best focus image:	3631MH0001530001301263R00	1263		motor count:		14015	range (cm):	6.7	
range map product:	3631MH0001530001301264S00	1264		acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	23-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3630	focus merged on sol:		3631	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3630MH0001820021301229C00	1229	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
3630MH0001820021301230C00	1230	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
3630MH0001820021301231C00	1231	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3630MH0001820021301232C00	1232	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3630MH0001820021301233C00	1233	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3630MH0001820021301234C00	1234	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
3630MH0001820021301235C00	1235	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3630MH0001820021301236C00	1236	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 28_November_2022

Sol 3630 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Santa_Silvia - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3630MH0001820011301240C00					
best focus image:		3631MH0001530001301261R00		1261		motor count:		14006		range (cm): 6.8	
range map product:		3631MH0001530001301262S00		1262		acquired sequence:		mhli00182		stack type: Relative	
acquired on date:		23-Oct-22				merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		24		acquired on sol:		3630		focus merged on sol:		3631	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8		
				near	far						
3630MH0001820021301241C00	1241	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1		
3630MH0001820021301242C00	1242	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2		
3630MH0001820021301243C00	1243	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3		
3630MH0001820021301244C00	1244	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4		
3630MH0001820021301245C00	1245	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5		
3630MH0001820021301246C00	1246	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6		
3630MH0001820021301247C00	1247	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7		
3630MH0001820021301248C00	1248	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8		

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Sol 3630 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Santa_Silvia - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3630MH0001820011301250C00					
best focus image:		3631MH0001530001301259R00		1259		motor count:		14015		range (cm): 6.7	
range map product:		3631MH0001530001301260S00		1260		acquired sequence:		mhli00182		stack type: Relative	
acquired on date:		23-Oct-22				merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		24		acquired on sol:		3630		focus merged on sol:		3631	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8		
				near	far						
3630MH0001820021301251C00	1251	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1		
3630MH0001820021301252C00	1252	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2		
3630MH0001820021301253C00	1253	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3		
3630MH0001820021301254C00	1254	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4		
3630MH0001820021301255C00	1255	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5		
3630MH0001820021301256C00	1256	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6		
3630MH0001820021301257C00	1257	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7		
3630MH0001820021301258C00	1258	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8		

updated: 28_November_2022

Sol 3633 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Balata - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3633MH0001680011301270C00				
best focus image:	3633MH0002650001301291R00	1291	motor count:		14004	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3633MH0002650001301292S00	1292	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	26-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3633	focus merged on sol:		3633	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3633MH0001680021301271C00	1271	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
3633MH0001680021301272C00	1272	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3633MH0001680021301273C00	1273	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3633MH0001680021301274C00	1274	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3633MH0001680021301275C00	1275	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3633MH0001680021301276C00	1276	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3633MH0001680021301277C00	1277	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3633MH0001680021301278C00	1278	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 28_November_2022

Sol 3633 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Balata - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3633MH0001680011301280C00				
best focus image:	3633MH0002650001301289R00	1289	motor count:		14008	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3633MH0002650001301290S00	1290	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	26-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3633	focus merged on sol:		3633	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3633MH0001680021301281C00	1281	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
3633MH0001680021301282C00	1282	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3633MH0001680021301283C00	1283	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3633MH0001680021301284C00	1284	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3633MH0001680021301285C00	1285	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3633MH0001680021301286C00	1286	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3633MH0001680021301287C00	1287	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3633MH0001680021301288C00	1288	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 28_November_2022

Sol 3635 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mau - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3635MH0002990011301298C00				
best focus image:	3635MH0001930001301335R00	1335	motor count:		13990	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3635MH0001930001301336S00	1336	acquired sequence:		mhli00299		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	28-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3635	focus merged on sol:		3635	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3635MH0002990021301299C00	1299	13846	7.98	-0.2	0.2	35.0	0.7	255	1
3635MH0002990021301300C00	1300	13882	7.69	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	223	2
3635MH0002990021301301C00	1301	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	191	3
3635MH0002990021301302C00	1302	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	159	4
3635MH0002990021301303C00	1303	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3635MH0002990021301304C00	1304	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3635MH0002990021301305C00	1305	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3635MH0002990021301306C00	1306	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3635 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mau - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3635MH0002990011301308C00				
best focus image:	3635MH0001930001301333R00	1333	motor count:		13999	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3635MH0001930001301334S00	1334	acquired sequence:		mhli00299		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	28-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3635	focus merged on sol:		3635	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3635MH0002990021301309C00	1309	13855	7.90	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	255	1
3635MH0002990021301310C00	1310	13891	7.62	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	223	2
3635MH0002990021301311C00	1311	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	191	3
3635MH0002990021301312C00	1312	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3635MH0002990021301313C00	1313	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3635MH0002990021301314C00	1314	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
3635MH0002990021301315C00	1315	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3635MH0002990021301316C00	1316	14107	6.19	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 28_November_2022

Sol 3635 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Univini - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3635MH0006990011301321C00				
best focus image:	3635MH0001930001301331R00	1331	motor count:		14094	range (cm):		6.3	
range map product:	3635MH0001930001301332S00	1332	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	28-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3635	focus merged on sol:		3635	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3635MH0006990031301323C00	1323	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	255	1
3635MH0006990031301324C00	1324	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	223	2
3635MH0006990031301325C00	1325	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	191	3
3635MH0006990031301326C00	1326	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	159	4
3635MH0006990031301327C00	1327	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	127	5
3635MH0006990031301328C00	1328	14124	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	95	6
3635MH0006990031301329C00	1329	14154	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	63	7
3635MH0006990031301330C00	1330	14184	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	31	8

updated: 28_November_2022

Sol 3637 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Catrimani - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3637MH0001730011301340C00				
best focus image:	3637MH0002270001301402R00	1402	motor count:		13969	range (cm):	7.1		
range map product:	3637MH0002270001301403S00	1403	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	30-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3637	focus merged on sol:		3637	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3637MH0001730021301341C00	1341	13849	7.95	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	255	1
3637MH0001730021301342C00	1342	13879	7.71	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	223	2
3637MH0001730021301343C00	1343	13909	7.48	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	191	3
3637MH0001730021301344C00	1344	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4
3637MH0001730021301345C00	1345	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	127	5
3637MH0001730021301346C00	1346	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	95	6
3637MH0001730021301347C00	1347	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
3637MH0001730021301348C00	1348	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 28_November_2022

Sol 3637 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Catrimani - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3637MH0001730011301350C00				
best focus image:	3637MH0002270001301400R00	1400	motor count:		13970	range (cm):	7.0		
range map product:	3637MH0002270001301401S00	1401	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	30-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3637	focus merged on sol:		3637	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3637MH0001730021301351C00	1351	13850	7.94	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	255	1
3637MH0001730021301352C00	1352	13880	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	223	2
3637MH0001730021301353C00	1353	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	191	3
3637MH0001730021301354C00	1354	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	159	4
3637MH0001730021301355C00	1355	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	127	5
3637MH0001730021301356C00	1356	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	95	6
3637MH0001730021301357C00	1357	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
3637MH0001730021301358C00	1358	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 28_November_2022

Sol 3637 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Catrimani - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3637MH0007160011301360C00			
best focus image:	3637MH0002270001301398R00		1398	motor count:		14980	range (cm):	3.1	
range map product:	3637MH0002270001301399S00		1399	acquired sequence:		mhli00716	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	30-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3637	focus merged on sol:		3637	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3637MH0007160021301361C00	1361	14740	3.67	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	255	1
3637MH0007160021301362C00	1362	14800	3.51	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	223	2
3637MH0007160021301363C00	1363	14860	3.36	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	191	3
3637MH0007160021301364C00	1364	14920	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	159	4
3637MH0007160021301365C00	1365	14980	3.08	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	127	5
3637MH0007160021301366C00	1366	15040	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	95	6
3637MH0007160021301367C00	1367	15100	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	63	7
3637MH0007160021301368C00	1368	15160	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	31	8

updated: 28_November_2022

Sol 3637 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Marari - stereo-1 - ~3 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3637MH0007210011301373C00			
best focus image:	3637MH0002270001301396R00		1396	motor count:		14323	range (cm):	5.1	
range map product:	3637MH0002270001301397S00		1397	acquired sequence:		mhli00721	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	30-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3637	focus merged on sol:		3637	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3637MH0007210031301375C00	1375	14155	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	255	1
3637MH0007210031301376C00	1376	14197	5.71	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	223	2
3637MH0007210031301377C00	1377	14239	5.50	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	191	3
3637MH0007210031301378C00	1378	14281	5.30	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	159	4
3637MH0007210031301379C00	1379	14323	5.12	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	127	5
3637MH0007210031301380C00	1380	14365	4.94	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	95	6
3637MH0007210031301381C00	1381	14407	4.77	-0.1	0.1	23.7	0.3	63	7
3637MH0007210031301382C00	1382	14449	4.61	-0.1	0.1	23.1	0.3	31	8

updated: 28_November_2022

Sol 3637 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Marari - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3637MH0007210011301384C00				
best focus image:	3637MH0002270001301394R00	1394	motor count:		14301	range (cm):		5.2	
range map product:	3637MH0002270001301395S00	1395	acquired sequence:		mhli00721	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	30-Oct-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3637	focus merged on sol:		3637	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3637MH0007210031301386C00	1386	14133	6.05	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	255	1
3637MH0007210031301387C00	1387	14175	5.82	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	223	2
3637MH0007210031301388C00	1388	14217	5.61	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	191	3
3637MH0007210031301389C00	1389	14259	5.41	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	159	4
3637MH0007210031301390C00	1390	14301	5.21	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	127	5
3637MH0007210031301391C00	1391	14343	5.03	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	95	6
3637MH0007210031301392C00	1392	14385	4.86	-0.1	0.1	24.0	0.4	63	7
3637MH0007210031301393C00	1393	14427	4.69	-0.1	0.1	23.4	0.3	31	8

updated: 29_November_2022

Sol 3639 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Nicara - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3639MH0001730011301407C00		
best focus image:	3639MH0001930001301440R00	1440		motor count:		14034	range (cm):	6.6	
range map product:	3639MH0001930001301441S00	1441		acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	1-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3639	focus merged on sol:		3639	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3639MH0001730021301408C00	1408	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	255	1
3639MH0001730021301409C00	1409	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3639MH0001730021301410C00	1410	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3639MH0001730021301411C00	1411	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3639MH0001730021301412C00	1412	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
3639MH0001730021301413C00	1413	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
3639MH0001730021301414C00	1414	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
3639MH0001730021301415C00	1415	14124	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_November_2022

Sol 3639 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Nicara - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3639MH0001730011301417C00		
best focus image:	3639MH0001930001301438R00	1438		motor count:		14034	range (cm):	6.6	
range map product:	3639MH0001930001301439S00	1439		acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	1-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3639	focus merged on sol:		3639	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3639MH0001730021301418C00	1418	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	255	1
3639MH0001730021301419C00	1419	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3639MH0001730021301420C00	1420	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3639MH0001730021301421C00	1421	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3639MH0001730021301422C00	1422	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
3639MH0001730021301423C00	1423	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
3639MH0001730021301424C00	1424	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
3639MH0001730021301425C00	1425	14124	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_November_2022

Sol 3639 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Nicara - ~7 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3639MH0003860011301427C00				
best focus image:	3639MH0001930001301436R00	1436	motor count:		15210	range (cm):		2.6	
range map product:	3639MH0001930001301437S00	1437	acquired sequence:		mhli00386		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	1-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3639	focus merged on sol:		3639	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3639MH0003860021301428C00	1428	14994	3.05	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	255	1
3639MH0003860021301429C00	1429	15048	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	223	2
3639MH0003860021301430C00	1430	15102	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	191	3
3639MH0003860021301431C00	1431	15156	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	159	4
3639MH0003860021301432C00	1432	15210	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	127	5
3639MH0003860021301433C00	1433	15264	2.54	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	95	6
3639MH0003860021301434C00	1434	15318	2.45	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	63	7
3639MH0003860021301435C00	1435	15372	2.36	0.0	0.1	15.2	0.2	31	8

updated: 02_December_2022

Sol 3641 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mel - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3641MH0003080011301449C00			
best focus image:	3642MH0003690001301568R00		1568	motor count:		13965	range (cm):	7.1	
range map product:	3642MH0003690001301569S00		1569	acquired sequence:		mhli00308	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	3-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00369	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3641	focus merged on sol:		3642	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3641MH0003080021301450C00	1450	13701	9.32	-0.3	0.3	39.7	0.9	255	1
3641MH0003080021301451C00	1451	13767	8.67	-0.2	0.2	37.4	0.8	223	2
3641MH0003080021301452C00	1452	13833	8.08	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	191	3
3641MH0003080021301453C00	1453	13899	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	159	4
3641MH0003080021301454C00	1454	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	127	5
3641MH0003080021301455C00	1455	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3641MH0003080021301456C00	1456	14097	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	63	7
3641MH0003080021301457C00	1457	14163	5.88	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	31	8

updated: 02_December_2022

Sol 3641 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mel - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3641MH0003080011301459C00			
best focus image:	3642MH0003690001301566R00		1566	motor count:		13972	range (cm):	7.0	
range map product:	3642MH0003690001301567S00		1567	acquired sequence:		mhli00308	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	3-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00369	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3641	focus merged on sol:		3642	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3641MH0003080021301460C00	1460	13708	9.25	-0.3	0.3	39.4	0.9	255	1
3641MH0003080021301461C00	1461	13774	8.60	-0.2	0.2	37.2	0.8	223	2
3641MH0003080021301462C00	1462	13840	8.03	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	191	3
3641MH0003080021301463C00	1463	13906	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	159	4
3641MH0003080021301464C00	1464	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	127	5
3641MH0003080021301465C00	1465	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
3641MH0003080021301466C00	1466	14104	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	63	7
3641MH0003080021301467C00	1467	14170	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	31	8

updated: 02_December_2022

Sol 3641 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mel - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3641MH0004280011301469C00			
best focus image:	3642MH0003690001301564R00	1564	motor count:		14587	range (cm):		4.1	
range map product:	3642MH0003690001301565S00	1565	acquired sequence:		mhli00428	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	3-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00369	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		78	acquired on sol:		3641	focus merged on sol:		3642	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3641MH0004280021301470C00	1470	14275	5.33	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	255	1
3641MH0004280021301471C00	1471	14353	4.99	-0.1	0.1	24.5	0.4	223	2
3641MH0004280021301472C00	1472	14431	4.68	-0.1	0.1	23.4	0.3	191	3
3641MH0004280021301473C00	1473	14509	4.39	-0.1	0.1	22.4	0.3	159	4
3641MH0004280021301474C00	1474	14587	4.13	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	127	5
3641MH0004280021301475C00	1475	14665	3.89	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	95	6
3641MH0004280021301476C00	1476	14743	3.66	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	63	7
3641MH0004280021301477C00	1477	14821	3.46	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	31	8

updated: 02_December_2022

Sol 3641 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mamupi - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3641MH0002240011301481C00			
best focus image:	3642MH0003690001301562R00	1562	motor count:		13987	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3642MH0003690001301563S00	1563	acquired sequence:		mhli00224	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	3-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00369	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3641	focus merged on sol:		3642	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3641MH0002240021301482C00	1482	13819	8.20	-0.2	0.2	35.8	0.7	255	1
3641MH0002240021301483C00	1483	13861	7.85	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	223	2
3641MH0002240021301484C00	1484	13903	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	191	3
3641MH0002240021301485C00	1485	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	159	4
3641MH0002240021301486C00	1486	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3641MH0002240021301487C00	1487	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3641MH0002240021301488C00	1488	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3641MH0002240021301489C00	1489	14113	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 02_December_2022

Sol 3641 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mamupi - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3641MH0002240011301491C00				
best focus image:	3642MH0003690001301560R00	1560	motor count:		13982	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3642MH0003690001301561S00	1561	acquired sequence:		mhli00224	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	3-Nov-22	merge sequence:		mhli00369	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3641	focus merged on sol:		3642	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3641MH0002240021301492C00	1492	13814	8.25	-0.2	0.2	35.9	0.8	255	1
3641MH0002240021301493C00	1493	13856	7.89	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	223	2
3641MH0002240021301494C00	1494	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	191	3
3641MH0002240021301495C00	1495	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	159	4
3641MH0002240021301496C00	1496	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5
3641MH0002240021301497C00	1497	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3641MH0002240021301498C00	1498	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3641MH0002240021301499C00	1499	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 02_December_2022

Sol 3641 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mamupi - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3641MH0003070011301501C00				
best focus image:	3642MH0003690001301558R00	1558	motor count:		14646	range (cm):		3.9	
range map product:	3642MH0003690001301559S00	1559	acquired sequence:		mhli00307	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	3-Nov-22	merge sequence:		mhli00369	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		72	acquired on sol:		3641	focus merged on sol:		3642	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3641MH0003070021301502C00	1502	14358	4.97	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	255	1
3641MH0003070021301503C00	1503	14430	4.68	-0.1	0.1	23.4	0.3	223	2
3641MH0003070021301504C00	1504	14502	4.42	-0.1	0.1	22.4	0.3	191	3
3641MH0003070021301505C00	1505	14574	4.17	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	159	4
3641MH0003070021301506C00	1506	14646	3.94	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	127	5
3641MH0003070021301507C00	1507	14718	3.73	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	95	6
3641MH0003070021301508C00	1508	14790	3.54	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	63	7
3641MH0003070021301509C00	1509	14862	3.35	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	31	8

updated: 02_December_2022

Sol 3641 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Iracema - ~25 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3641MH0008550011301511C00				
best focus image:	3642MH0003690001301556R00	1556	motor count:		13013	range (cm):		26.8	
range map product:	3642MH0003690001301557S00	1557	acquired sequence:		mhli00855		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	3-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00369		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3641	focus merged on sol:		3642	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3641MH0008550021301512C00	1512	12893	36.70	-3.3	4.0	136.1	12.8	255	1
3641MH0008550021301513C00	1513	12923	33.64	-2.8	3.3	125.3	10.7	223	2
3641MH0008550021301514C00	1514	12953	31.01	-2.4	2.8	116.1	9.1	191	3
3641MH0008550021301515C00	1515	12983	28.75	-2.1	2.4	108.1	7.8	159	4
3641MH0008550021301516C00	1516	13013	26.77	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	127	5
3641MH0008550021301517C00	1517	13043	25.02	-1.6	1.8	95.0	5.9	95	6
3641MH0008550021301518C00	1518	13073	23.47	-1.4	1.6	89.5	5.2	63	7
3641MH0008550021301519C00	1519	13103	22.09	-1.3	1.4	84.6	4.6	31	8

updated: 02_December_2022

Sol 3641 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Iracema - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3641MH0002990011301521C00				
best focus image:	3642MH0003690001301554R00	1554	motor count:		14006	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3642MH0003690001301555S00	1555	acquired sequence:		mhli00299		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	3-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00369		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3641	focus merged on sol:		3642	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3641MH0002990021301522C00	1522	13862	7.85	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	255	1
3641MH0002990021301523C00	1523	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	223	2
3641MH0002990021301524C00	1524	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
3641MH0002990021301525C00	1525	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3641MH0002990021301526C00	1526	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3641MH0002990021301527C00	1527	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	95	6
3641MH0002990021301528C00	1528	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3641MH0002990021301529C00	1529	14114	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 02_December_2022

Sol 3641 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Iracema - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3641MH0002990011301531C00				
best focus image:	3642MH0003690001301552R00	1552	motor count:		14018	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3642MH0003690001301553S00	1553	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	3-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00369	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3641	focus merged on sol:		3642	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3641MH0002990021301532C00	1532	13874	7.75	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	255	1
3641MH0002990021301533C00	1533	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	223	2
3641MH0002990021301534C00	1534	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3641MH0002990021301535C00	1535	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3641MH0002990021301536C00	1536	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3641MH0002990021301537C00	1537	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
3641MH0002990021301538C00	1538	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
3641MH0002990021301539C00	1539	14126	6.08	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 02_December_2022

Sol 3641 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Iracema - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3641MH0006490011301541C00				
best focus image:	3642MH0003690001301550R00	1550	motor count:		15119	range (cm):		2.8	
range map product:	3642MH0003690001301551S00	1551	acquired sequence:		mhli00649	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	3-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00369	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		78	acquired on sol:		3641	focus merged on sol:		3642	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3641MH0006490021301542C00	1542	14807	3.49	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	255	1
3641MH0006490021301543C00	1543	14885	3.30	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	223	2
3641MH0006490021301544C00	1544	14963	3.12	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	191	3
3641MH0006490021301545C00	1545	15041	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	159	4
3641MH0006490021301546C00	1546	15119	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	127	5
3641MH0006490021301547C00	1547	15197	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	95	6
3641MH0006490021301548C00	1548	15275	2.52	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	63	7
3641MH0006490021301549C00	1549	15353	2.39	0.0	0.1	15.3	0.2	31	8

updated: 05_December_2022

Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Mixiguana - stereo-1 - ~23 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0008550011301571C00				
best focus image:	3645MH0008570001301798R00	1798	motor count:		13041	range (cm):		25.1	
range map product:	3645MH0008570001301799S00	1799	acquired sequence:		mhli00855	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22	merge sequence:		mhli00857	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0008550021301572C00	1572	12921	33.82	-2.8	3.4	126.0	10.9	255	1
3644MH0008550021301573C00	1573	12951	31.18	-2.4	2.8	116.6	9.2	223	2
3644MH0008550021301574C00	1574	12981	28.89	-2.1	2.4	108.6	7.9	191	3
3644MH0008550021301575C00	1575	13011	26.89	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	159	4
3644MH0008550021301576C00	1576	13041	25.13	-1.6	1.8	95.4	6.0	127	5
3644MH0008550021301577C00	1577	13071	23.57	-1.4	1.6	89.9	5.2	95	6
3644MH0008550021301578C00	1578	13101	22.17	-1.3	1.4	85.0	4.6	63	7
3644MH0008550021301579C00	1579	13131	20.92	-1.1	1.2	80.5	4.1	31	8

updated: 05_December_2022

Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Mixiguana - stereo-2 - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0008550011301581C00				
best focus image:	3645MH0008570001301796R00	1796	motor count:		13032	range (cm):		25.6	
range map product:	3645MH0008570001301797S00	1797	acquired sequence:		mhli00855	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22	merge sequence:		mhli00857	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0008550021301582C00	1582	12912	34.70	-3.0	3.5	129.1	11.4	255	1
3644MH0008550021301583C00	1583	12942	31.93	-2.5	3.0	119.3	9.7	223	2
3644MH0008550021301584C00	1584	12972	29.54	-2.2	2.5	110.9	8.3	191	3
3644MH0008550021301585C00	1585	13002	27.46	-1.9	2.2	103.6	7.1	159	4
3644MH0008550021301586C00	1586	13032	25.64	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	127	5
3644MH0008550021301587C00	1587	13062	24.02	-1.5	1.6	91.5	5.4	95	6
3644MH0008550021301588C00	1588	13092	22.58	-1.3	1.4	86.4	4.8	63	7
3644MH0008550021301589C00	1589	13122	21.28	-1.2	1.3	81.8	4.3	31	8

updated: 05_December_2022

Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mixiguana - mosaic position 1 of 12 - ~12 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0008560011301591C00			
best focus image:	3645MH0008570001301794R00	1794	motor count:		13373	range (cm):		14.1	
range map product:	3645MH0008570001301795S00	1795	acquired sequence:		mhli00856		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00857		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0008560021301592C00	1592	13205	18.30	-0.9	0.9	71.3	3.2	255	1
3644MH0008560021301593C00	1593	13247	17.06	-0.8	0.8	66.9	2.8	223	2
3644MH0008560021301594C00	1594	13289	15.95	-0.7	0.7	63.1	2.4	191	3
3644MH0008560021301595C00	1595	13331	14.96	-0.6	0.6	59.6	2.2	159	4
3644MH0008560021301596C00	1596	13373	14.07	-0.5	0.6	56.4	1.9	127	5
3644MH0008560021301597C00	1597	13415	13.27	-0.5	0.5	53.6	1.7	95	6
3644MH0008560021301598C00	1598	13457	12.53	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.6	63	7
3644MH0008560021301599C00	1599	13499	11.87	-0.4	0.4	48.7	1.4	31	8

updated: 05_December_2022

Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mixiguana - mosaic position 2 of 12 - ~12 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0008560011301601C00			
best focus image:	3645MH0008570001301792R00	1792	motor count:		13404	range (cm):		13.5	
range map product:	3645MH0008570001301793S00	1793	acquired sequence:		mhli00856		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00857		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0008560021301602C00	1602	13236	17.37	-0.8	0.8	68.0	2.9	255	1
3644MH0008560021301603C00	1603	13278	16.23	-0.7	0.7	64.0	2.5	223	2
3644MH0008560021301604C00	1604	13320	15.21	-0.6	0.6	60.4	2.2	191	3
3644MH0008560021301605C00	1605	13362	14.30	-0.6	0.6	57.2	2.0	159	4
3644MH0008560021301606C00	1606	13404	13.47	-0.5	0.5	54.3	1.8	127	5
3644MH0008560021301607C00	1607	13446	12.72	-0.5	0.5	51.7	1.6	95	6
3644MH0008560021301608C00	1608	13488	12.03	-0.4	0.4	49.3	1.4	63	7
3644MH0008560021301609C00	1609	13530	11.41	-0.4	0.4	47.1	1.3	31	8

updated: 05_December_2022

Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mixiguana - mosaic position 3 of 12 - ~13 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0008560011301611C00				
best focus image:	3645MH0008570001301790R00	1790	motor count:		13327	range (cm):	15.1		
range map product:	3645MH0008570001301791S00	1791	acquired sequence:		mhli00856	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22			merge sequence:	mhli00857	merge type:	Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0008560021301612C00	1612	13159	19.86	-1.0	1.1	76.8	3.7	255	1
3644MH0008560021301613C00	1613	13201	18.43	-0.9	0.9	71.8	3.2	223	2
3644MH0008560021301614C00	1614	13243	17.17	-0.8	0.8	67.3	2.8	191	3
3644MH0008560021301615C00	1615	13285	16.05	-0.7	0.7	63.4	2.5	159	4
3644MH0008560021301616C00	1616	13327	15.05	-0.6	0.6	59.9	2.2	127	5
3644MH0008560021301617C00	1617	13369	14.15	-0.6	0.6	56.7	1.9	95	6
3644MH0008560021301618C00	1618	13411	13.34	-0.5	0.5	53.9	1.7	63	7
3644MH0008560021301619C00	1619	13453	12.60	-0.5	0.4	51.3	1.6	31	8

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Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mixiguana - mosaic position 4 of 12 - ~13 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0008560011301621C00				
best focus image:	3645MH0008570001301788R00	1788	motor count:		13326	range (cm):	15.1		
range map product:	3645MH0008570001301789S00	1789	acquired sequence:		mhli00856	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22			merge sequence:	mhli00857	merge type:	Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0008560021301622C00	1622	13158	19.89	-1.0	1.1	76.9	3.8	255	1
3644MH0008560021301623C00	1623	13200	18.46	-0.9	0.9	71.9	3.2	223	2
3644MH0008560021301624C00	1624	13242	17.20	-0.8	0.8	67.4	2.8	191	3
3644MH0008560021301625C00	1625	13284	16.08	-0.7	0.7	63.5	2.5	159	4
3644MH0008560021301626C00	1626	13326	15.08	-0.6	0.6	60.0	2.2	127	5
3644MH0008560021301627C00	1627	13368	14.17	-0.6	0.6	56.8	1.9	95	6
3644MH0008560021301628C00	1628	13410	13.36	-0.5	0.5	53.9	1.7	63	7
3644MH0008560021301629C00	1629	13452	12.62	-0.5	0.4	51.3	1.6	31	8

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Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mixiguana - mosaic position 5 of 12 - ~13 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0008560011301631C00				
best focus image:	3645MH0008570001301786R00	1786	motor count:		13345	range (cm):		14.7	
range map product:	3645MH0008570001301787S00	1787	acquired sequence:		mhli00856	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00857	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0008560021301632C00	1632	13177	19.22	-1.0	1.0	74.6	3.5	255	1
3644MH0008560021301633C00	1633	13219	17.87	-0.8	0.9	69.8	3.0	223	2
3644MH0008560021301634C00	1634	13261	16.68	-0.7	0.8	65.6	2.7	191	3
3644MH0008560021301635C00	1635	13303	15.61	-0.7	0.7	61.9	2.3	159	4
3644MH0008560021301636C00	1636	13345	14.66	-0.6	0.6	58.5	2.1	127	5
3644MH0008560021301637C00	1637	13387	13.80	-0.5	0.5	55.5	1.9	95	6
3644MH0008560021301638C00	1638	13429	13.02	-0.5	0.5	52.7	1.7	63	7
3644MH0008560021301639C00	1639	13471	12.30	-0.4	0.4	50.2	1.5	31	8

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Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mixiguana - mosaic position 6 of 12 - ~13 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0008560011301641C00				
best focus image:	3645MH0008570001301784R00	1784	motor count:		13342	range (cm):		14.7	
range map product:	3645MH0008570001301785S00	1785	acquired sequence:		mhli00856	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00857	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0008560021301642C00	1642	13174	19.32	-1.0	1.0	74.9	3.5	255	1
3644MH0008560021301643C00	1643	13216	17.96	-0.9	0.9	70.1	3.1	223	2
3644MH0008560021301644C00	1644	13258	16.76	-0.8	0.8	65.9	2.7	191	3
3644MH0008560021301645C00	1645	13300	15.68	-0.7	0.7	62.1	2.4	159	4
3644MH0008560021301646C00	1646	13342	14.72	-0.6	0.6	58.7	2.1	127	5
3644MH0008560021301647C00	1647	13384	13.85	-0.5	0.5	55.7	1.9	95	6
3644MH0008560021301648C00	1648	13426	13.07	-0.5	0.5	52.9	1.7	63	7
3644MH0008560021301649C00	1649	13468	12.35	-0.4	0.4	50.4	1.5	31	8

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Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Mixiguana - mosaic position 7 of 12 - ~14 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0008560011301651C00				
best focus image:	3645MH0008570001301782R00	1782	motor count:		13313	range (cm):	15.4		
range map product:	3645MH0008570001301783S00	1783	acquired sequence:		mhli00856	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00857	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0008560021301652C00	1652	13145	20.37	-1.1	1.2	78.6	3.9	255	1
3644MH0008560021301653C00	1653	13187	18.88	-0.9	1.0	73.4	3.4	223	2
3644MH0008560021301654C00	1654	13229	17.57	-0.8	0.9	68.8	2.9	191	3
3644MH0008560021301655C00	1655	13271	16.41	-0.7	0.7	64.7	2.6	159	4
3644MH0008560021301656C00	1656	13313	15.37	-0.6	0.7	61.0	2.3	127	5
3644MH0008560021301657C00	1657	13355	14.44	-0.6	0.6	57.7	2.0	95	6
3644MH0008560021301658C00	1658	13397	13.60	-0.5	0.5	54.8	1.8	63	7
3644MH0008560021301659C00	1659	13439	12.84	-0.5	0.5	52.1	1.6	31	8

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Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Mixiguana - mosaic position 8 of 12 - ~13 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0008560011301661C00				
best focus image:	3645MH0008570001301780R00	1780	motor count:		13315	range (cm):	15.3		
range map product:	3645MH0008570001301781S00	1781	acquired sequence:		mhli00856	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00857	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0008560021301662C00	1662	13147	20.30	-1.1	1.1	78.4	3.9	255	1
3644MH0008560021301663C00	1663	13189	18.82	-0.9	1.0	73.1	3.4	223	2
3644MH0008560021301664C00	1664	13231	17.51	-0.8	0.9	68.6	2.9	191	3
3644MH0008560021301665C00	1665	13273	16.36	-0.7	0.7	64.5	2.6	159	4
3644MH0008560021301666C00	1666	13315	15.33	-0.6	0.7	60.9	2.3	127	5
3644MH0008560021301667C00	1667	13357	14.40	-0.6	0.6	57.6	2.0	95	6
3644MH0008560021301668C00	1668	13399	13.56	-0.5	0.5	54.7	1.8	63	7
3644MH0008560021301669C00	1669	13441	12.81	-0.5	0.5	52.0	1.6	31	8

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Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mixiguana - mosaic position 9 of 12 - ~13 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0008560011301671C00				
best focus image:	3645MH0008570001301778R00	1778	motor count:		13343	range (cm):		14.7	
range map product:	3645MH0008570001301779S00	1779	acquired sequence:		mhli00856		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22		merge sequence:		mhli00857		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0008560021301672C00	1672	13175	19.29	-1.0	1.0	74.8	3.5	255	1
3644MH0008560021301673C00	1673	13217	17.93	-0.9	0.9	70.0	3.1	223	2
3644MH0008560021301674C00	1674	13259	16.73	-0.7	0.8	65.8	2.7	191	3
3644MH0008560021301675C00	1675	13301	15.66	-0.7	0.7	62.0	2.3	159	4
3644MH0008560021301676C00	1676	13343	14.70	-0.6	0.6	58.6	2.1	127	5
3644MH0008560021301677C00	1677	13385	13.83	-0.5	0.5	55.6	1.9	95	6
3644MH0008560021301678C00	1678	13427	13.05	-0.5	0.5	52.8	1.7	63	7
3644MH0008560021301679C00	1679	13469	12.34	-0.4	0.4	50.3	1.5	31	8

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Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mixiguana - mosaic position 10 of 12 - ~13 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0008560011301681C00				
best focus image:	3645MH0008570001301776R00	1776	motor count:		13359	range (cm):		14.4	
range map product:	3645MH0008570001301777S00	1777	acquired sequence:		mhli00856		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22		merge sequence:		mhli00857		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0008560021301682C00	1682	13191	18.75	-0.9	1.0	72.9	3.3	255	1
3644MH0008560021301683C00	1683	13233	17.46	-0.8	0.8	68.3	2.9	223	2
3644MH0008560021301684C00	1684	13275	16.31	-0.7	0.7	64.3	2.5	191	3
3644MH0008560021301685C00	1685	13317	15.28	-0.6	0.6	60.7	2.2	159	4
3644MH0008560021301686C00	1686	13359	14.36	-0.6	0.6	57.4	2.0	127	5
3644MH0008560021301687C00	1687	13401	13.53	-0.5	0.5	54.5	1.8	95	6
3644MH0008560021301688C00	1688	13443	12.77	-0.5	0.5	51.9	1.6	63	7
3644MH0008560021301689C00	1689	13485	12.08	-0.4	0.4	49.4	1.4	31	8

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Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mixiguana - mosaic position 11 of 12 - ~13 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0008560011301691C00				
best focus image:	3645MH0008570001301774R00	1774	motor count:		13349	range (cm):		14.6	
range map product:	3645MH0008570001301775S00	1775	acquired sequence:		mhli00856	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00857	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0008560021301692C00	1692	13181	19.08	-1.0	1.0	74.1	3.5	255	1
3644MH0008560021301693C00	1693	13223	17.75	-0.8	0.9	69.4	3.0	223	2
3644MH0008560021301694C00	1694	13265	16.57	-0.7	0.8	65.2	2.6	191	3
3644MH0008560021301695C00	1695	13307	15.52	-0.7	0.7	61.5	2.3	159	4
3644MH0008560021301696C00	1696	13349	14.57	-0.6	0.6	58.2	2.0	127	5
3644MH0008560021301697C00	1697	13391	13.72	-0.5	0.5	55.2	1.8	95	6
3644MH0008560021301698C00	1698	13433	12.94	-0.5	0.5	52.5	1.6	63	7
3644MH0008560021301699C00	1699	13475	12.24	-0.4	0.4	50.0	1.5	31	8

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Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mixiguana - mosaic position 12 of 12 - ~11 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0008560011301701C00				
best focus image:	3645MH0008570001301772R00	1772	motor count:		13430	range (cm):		13.0	
range map product:	3645MH0008570001301773S00	1773	acquired sequence:		mhli00856	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00857	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0008560021301702C00	1702	13262	16.65	-0.7	0.8	65.5	2.6	255	1
3644MH0008560021301703C00	1703	13304	15.59	-0.7	0.7	61.8	2.3	223	2
3644MH0008560021301704C00	1704	13346	14.63	-0.6	0.6	58.4	2.1	191	3
3644MH0008560021301705C00	1705	13388	13.78	-0.5	0.5	55.4	1.8	159	4
3644MH0008560021301706C00	1706	13430	13.00	-0.5	0.5	52.7	1.7	127	5
3644MH0008560021301707C00	1707	13472	12.29	-0.4	0.4	50.2	1.5	95	6
3644MH0008560021301708C00	1708	13514	11.64	-0.4	0.4	47.9	1.4	63	7
3644MH0008560021301709C00	1709	13556	11.04	-0.4	0.3	45.8	1.2	31	8

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Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Mixiguana - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0003830011301711C00				
best focus image:	3645MH0008570001301770R00	1770	motor count:		13977	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3645MH0008570001301771S00	1771	acquired sequence:		mhli00383	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00857	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		90	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0003830021301712C00	1712	13617	10.26	-0.3	0.3	43.0	1.1	255	1
3644MH0003830021301713C00	1713	13707	9.26	-0.3	0.3	39.5	0.9	223	2
3644MH0003830021301714C00	1714	13797	8.40	-0.2	0.2	36.5	0.8	191	3
3644MH0003830021301715C00	1715	13887	7.65	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	159	4
3644MH0003830021301716C00	1716	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
3644MH0003830021301717C00	1717	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	95	6
3644MH0003830021301718C00	1718	14157	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	63	7
3644MH0003830021301719C00	1719	14247	5.46	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Mocra - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0002990011301723C00				
best focus image:	3645MH0001530001301768R00	1768	motor count:		13954	range (cm):		7.2	
range map product:	3645MH0001530001301769S00	1769	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0002990021301724C00	1724	13810	8.28	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	255	1
3644MH0002990021301725C00	1725	13846	7.98	-0.2	0.2	35.0	0.7	223	2
3644MH0002990021301726C00	1726	13882	7.69	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	191	3
3644MH0002990021301727C00	1727	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	159	4
3644MH0002990021301728C00	1728	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	127	5
3644MH0002990021301729C00	1729	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	95	6
3644MH0002990021301730C00	1730	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
3644MH0002990021301731C00	1731	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mocra - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0002990011301733C00			
best focus image:	3645MH0001530001301766R00		1766	motor count:		13962	range (cm):	7.1	
range map product:	3645MH0001530001301767S00		1767	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0002990021301734C00	1734	13818	8.21	-0.2	0.2	35.8	0.8	255	1
3644MH0002990021301735C00	1735	13854	7.91	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	223	2
3644MH0002990021301736C00	1736	13890	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	191	3
3644MH0002990021301737C00	1737	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	159	4
3644MH0002990021301738C00	1738	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	127	5
3644MH0002990021301739C00	1739	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	95	6
3644MH0002990021301740C00	1740	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
3644MH0002990021301741C00	1741	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Mocra - APXS spot 2 - ~2 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0003110011301743C00			
best focus image:	3645MH0001530001301764R00		1764	motor count:		14600	range (cm):	4.1	
range map product:	3645MH0001530001301765S00		1765	acquired sequence:		mhli00311	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0003110021301744C00	1744	14336	5.06	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	255	1
3644MH0003110021301745C00	1745	14402	4.79	-0.1	0.1	23.8	0.4	223	2
3644MH0003110021301746C00	1746	14468	4.54	-0.1	0.1	22.9	0.3	191	3
3644MH0003110021301747C00	1747	14534	4.30	-0.1	0.1	22.1	0.3	159	4
3644MH0003110021301748C00	1748	14600	4.09	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	127	5
3644MH0003110021301749C00	1749	14666	3.88	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	95	6
3644MH0003110021301750C00	1750	14732	3.69	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	63	7
3644MH0003110021301751C00	1751	14798	3.52	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	31	8

updated: 05_December_2022

Sol 3644 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Mocras - APXS spot 1 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3644MH0002990011301753C00				
best focus image:	3645MH0001530001301762R00	1762	motor count:		13947	range (cm):		7.2	
range map product:	3645MH0001530001301763S00	1763	acquired sequence:		mhli00299		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	6-Nov-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3644	focus merged on sol:		3645	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3644MH0002990021301754C00	1754	13803	8.34	-0.2	0.2	36.3	0.8	255	1
3644MH0002990021301755C00	1755	13839	8.03	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	223	2
3644MH0002990021301756C00	1756	13875	7.74	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	191	3
3644MH0002990021301757C00	1757	13911	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	159	4
3644MH0002990021301758C00	1758	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	127	5
3644MH0002990021301759C00	1759	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	95	6
3644MH0002990021301760C00	1760	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7
3644MH0002990021301761C00	1761	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

6 Image comment, purpose, RATIONALE_DESC

A RATIONALE_DESC accompanies each MAHLI image and each focus merge product archived with the NASA PDS. It is found in in each archived image label file (.LBL).

The RATIONALE_DESC is a text description of the purpose (rationale) behind the acquisition of each MAHLI parent image.

For onboard focus merge products, the RATIONALE_DESC includes information regarding when the merge was performed and which parent images were merged. This information is not automatically tracked by the instrument or ground data system and thus requires human intervention; this is the only pathway by which this information is conveyed to the data user through the NASA PDS archival products.

The MAHLI Team drafts each RATIONALE_DESC as the data are acquired and returned to Earth. Final editing of each RATIONALE_DESC is performed a few months before the data are archived with the NASA PDS. In some cases, an error might be detected in a RATIONALE_DESC some time after the data are first archived; in such a case, the corrections are made in a later release of MAHLI data to the PDS (as long as the mission continues and funding is available to do so).

The pages that follow capture the RATIONALE_DESC for each MAHLI image acquired and lists the ID for the best available image or focus merge product returned to Earth. Note that the RATIONALE_DESC also applies to any other child images spawned by a given parent image and thus there might be additional images, not listed here, that correspond to a given RATIONALE_DESC. In some cases, it was only necessary to return a thumbnail image; the IDs for these are given in orange text. As noted earlier, purple text indicates Image IDs for which the last two characters might differ from those in the NASA PDS archives.

Note that the text on the pages that follow is tiny. We highly recommend that the reader view this document electronically (*i.e.*, PDF file on a computer screen) and magnify the view $\geq 400\%$.

The *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* that follow include data acquired Sol 3548–3644. During this period, the instrument obtained images and/or performed focus merges on **Sols 3551, 3553, 3555, 3556, 3558, 3560, 3562, 3564, 3566, 3567, 3568, 3570, 3571, 3573, 3574, 3575, 3578, 3583, 3590, 3592, 3594, 3596, 3599, 3601, 3603, 3605, 3607, 3609, 3612, 3624, 3626, 3628, 3630, 3631, 3633, 3635, 3637, 3639, 3641, 3642, 3644.**

updated: 11_October_2022

Sol 3551 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	2-Aug-22
camera position:	4
total parent images:	45
focus merges performed:	4
total focus merge products:	8
total parent images + focus merge products:	48

MAHLI imaged the target Karisparo, which included a 3x1 mosaic. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN000359	Karisparo ~24 cm standoff	3551MH000359001204536C0D	4536	autofocus sub-frame for target Karisparo - standoff near 24 cm
		3551MH000359001204537C0D	4537	target Karisparo - standoff near 24 cm
		3551MH000359001204538C0D	4538	target Karisparo - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000359001204539C0D	4539	target Karisparo - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000359001204540C0D	4540	target Karisparo - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000359001204541C0D	4541	target Karisparo - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000359001204542C0D	4542	target Karisparo - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000359001204543C0D	4543	target Karisparo - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000359001204544C0D	4544	target Karisparo - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000359001204545C0D	4545	target Karisparo - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000363	Karisparo mosaic position 1 of 3 ~4 cm standoff	3551MH000363001204546C0D	4546	autofocus sub-frame for target Karisparo - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm
		3551MH000363001204547C0D	4547	target Karisparo - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm
		3551MH000363001204548C0D	4548	target Karisparo - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204549C0D	4549	target Karisparo - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204550C0D	4550	target Karisparo - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204551C0D	4551	target Karisparo - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204552C0D	4552	target Karisparo - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204553C0D	4553	target Karisparo - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204554C0D	4554	target Karisparo - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204555C0D	4555	target Karisparo - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000363	Karisparo mosaic position 2 of 3 ~4 cm standoff	3551MH000363001204556C0D	4556	autofocus sub-frame for target Karisparo - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm
		3551MH000363001204557C0D	4557	target Karisparo - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm
		3551MH000363001204558C0D	4558	target Karisparo - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204559C0D	4559	target Karisparo - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204560C0D	4560	target Karisparo - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204561C0D	4561	target Karisparo - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204562C0D	4562	target Karisparo - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204563C0D	4563	target Karisparo - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204564C0D	4564	target Karisparo - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204565C0D	4565	target Karisparo - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000363	Karisparo mosaic position 3 of 3 ~4 cm standoff	3551MH000363001204566C0D	4566	autofocus sub-frame for target Karisparo - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm
		3551MH000363001204567C0D	4567	target Karisparo - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm
		3551MH000363001204568C0D	4568	target Karisparo - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204569C0D	4569	target Karisparo - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204570C0D	4570	target Karisparo - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204571C0D	4571	target Karisparo - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204572C0D	4572	target Karisparo - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204573C0D	4573	target Karisparo - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204574C0D	4574	target Karisparo - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3551MH000363001204575C0D	4575	target Karisparo - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000353	Focus Merges	3551MH000153001204576R0D	4576	target Karisparo - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3551 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4568-4575 - best focus image product
		3551MH000153001204577R0D	4577	target Karisparo - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3551 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4568-4575 - range map product
		3551MH000153001204578R0D	4578	target Karisparo - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3551 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4558-4565 - best focus image product
		3551MH000153001204579R0D	4579	target Karisparo - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3551 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4558-4565 - range map product
		3551MH000153001204580R0D	4580	target Karisparo - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3551 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4548-4555 - best focus image product
		3551MH000153001204581R0D	4581	target Karisparo - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3551 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4548-4555 - range map product
		3551MH000153001204582R0D	4582	target Karisparo - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3551 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4538-4545 - best focus image product
		3551MH000153001204583R0D	4583	target Karisparo - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3551 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4538-4545 - range map product

updated: 10_October_2022

Sol 3553 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	4 Aug 22
camera position	6
total parent images	43
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	50

MAHLI imaged the target Arorouta and acquired a 2x1 mosaic on the target Yakontipu. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Arorouta ~24 cm standoff	355MH000190001204984C0D	4584	autofocus sub-frame for target Arorouta - standoff near 24 cm
		355MH000190001204585C0D	4585	target Arorouta - standoff near 24 cm
mN00182	Arorouta stereo-1 ~35 mm standoff	355MH000182001204986C0D	4586	autofocus sub-frame for target Arorouta - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		355MH000182001204587C0D	4587	target Arorouta - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		355MH000182001204988C0D	4588	target Arorouta - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000182001204589C0D	4589	target Arorouta - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000182001204990C0D	4590	target Arorouta - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000182001204591C0D	4591	target Arorouta - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000182001204992C0D	4592	target Arorouta - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000182001204593C0D	4593	target Arorouta - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000182001204994C0D	4594	target Arorouta - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000182001204595C0D	4595	target Arorouta - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Arorouta stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff	355MH000182001204996C0D	4596	autofocus sub-frame for target Arorouta - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		355MH000182001204597C0D	4597	target Arorouta - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		355MH000182001204998C0D	4598	target Arorouta - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000182001204599C0D	4599	target Arorouta - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000182001204600C0D	4600	target Arorouta - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000182001204601C0D	4601	target Arorouta - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000182001204602C0D	4602	target Arorouta - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000182001204603C0D	4603	target Arorouta - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000182001204604C0D	4604	target Arorouta - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000182001204605C0D	4605	target Arorouta - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00854	Yakontipu mosaic position 1 of 2 ~20 cm standoff	355MH000854001204606C0D	4606	autofocus sub-frame for target Yakontipu - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm
		355MH000854001204607C0D	4607	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm
		355MH000854001204608C0D	4608	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000854001204609C0D	4609	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000854001204610C0D	4610	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000854001204611C0D	4611	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000854001204612C0D	4612	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000854001204613C0D	4613	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000854001204614C0D	4614	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000854001204615C0D	4615	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00854	Yakontipu mosaic position 2 of 2 ~21 cm standoff	355MH000854001204616C0D	4616	autofocus sub-frame for target Yakontipu - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 21 cm
		355MH000854001204617C0D	4617	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 21 cm
		355MH000854001204618C0D	4618	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 21 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000854001204619C0D	4619	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 21 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000854001204620C0D	4620	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 21 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000854001204621C0D	4621	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 21 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000854001204622C0D	4622	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 21 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000854001204623C0D	4623	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 21 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000854001204624C0D	4624	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 21 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355MH000854001204625C0D	4625	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 21 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00153	Focus Merges	355MH000153001204626C0D	4626	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 21 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3553 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4618-4625 - best focus image product
		355MH000153001204627C0D	4627	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 21 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3553 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4618-4625 - range map product
		355MH000153001204628C0D	4628	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3553 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4608-4615 - best focus image product
		355MH000153001204629C0D	4629	target Yakontipu - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3553 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4608-4615 - range map product
		355MH000153001204630C0D	4630	target Arorouta - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3553 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4598-4605 - best focus image product
		355MH000153001204631C0D	4631	target Arorouta - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3553 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4598-4605 - range map product
355MH000153001204632C0D	4632	target Arorouta - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3553 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4588-4595 - best focus image product		
355MH000153001204633C0D	4633	target Arorouta - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3553 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4588-4595 - range map product		

updated: 08_August_2022

Sol 3556 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	7 Aug 22
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	5
total focus merge products:	10
total parent images + focus merge products:	10

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3555 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3556MH0002270001D04688R00	4688	target Apoguaeo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3555 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4680-4687 - best focus image product
		3556MH0002270001D04689S00	4689	target Apoguaeo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3555 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4680-4687 - range map product
		3556MH0002270001D04690R00	4690	target Apoguaeo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3555 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4670-4677 - best focus image product
		3556MH0002270001D04691S00	4691	target Apoguaeo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3555 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4670-4677 - range map product
		3556MH0002270001D04692R00	4692	target Sloth_Island - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3555 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4658-4665 - best focus image product
		3556MH0002270001D04693S00	4693	target Sloth_Island - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3555 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4658-4665 - range map product
		3556MH0002270001D04694R00	4694	target Sloth_Island - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3555 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4648-4655 - best focus image product
		3556MH0002270001D04695S00	4695	target Sloth_Island - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3555 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4648-4655 - range map product
		3556MH0002270001D04696R00	4696	target Sloth_Island - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3555 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4638-4645 - best focus image product
		3556MH0002270001D04697S00	4697	target Sloth_Island - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3555 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4638-4645 - range map product

updated: 11_October_2022

Sol 3558 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	Image ID
camera position	75
total parent images	7
focus merges performed	14
total focus merge products	89
total parent images + focus merge products	89

MAHLI imaged the targets Sao_Marcos, Essequibo and Kumu_Falls. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Sao_Marcos ~23 cm standoff	3558MH0019000100469800	4698	autofocus sub-frame for target Sao_Marcos - standoff near 23 cm
		3558MH0019000100469900	4699	target Sao_Marcos - standoff near 23 cm
mN00308	Sao_Marcos stereo-1 ~3 cm standoff	3558MH00308002100470000	4700	autofocus sub-frame for target Sao_Marcos - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm
		3558MH003080011004701000	4701	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm
		3558MH003080021004702000	4702	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH003080021004703000	4703	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH003080021004704000	4704	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH003080021004705000	4705	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH003080021004706000	4706	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH003080021004707000	4707	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH003080021004708000	4708	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH003080021004709000	4709	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00308	Sao_Marcos stereo-2 ~3 cm standoff	3558MH003080021004710000	4710	autofocus sub-frame for target Sao_Marcos - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		3558MH003080011004711000	4711	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		3558MH003080021004712000	4712	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH003080021004713000	4713	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH003080021004714000	4714	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH003080021004715000	4715	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH003080021004716000	4716	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH003080021004717000	4717	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH003080021004718000	4718	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH003080021004719000	4719	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Essequibo ~23 cm standoff	3558MH00190001004720000	4720	autofocus sub-frame for target Essequibo - standoff near 23 cm
		3558MH00190001004721000	4721	target Essequibo - standoff near 23 cm
mN00673	Essequibo stereo-1 ~3 cm standoff	3558MH00673001004722000	4722	autofocus sub-frame for target Essequibo - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm
		3558MH00673001004723000	4723	target Essequibo - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm
		3558MH00673001004724000	4724	target Essequibo - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00673001004725000	4725	target Essequibo - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00673001004726000	4726	target Essequibo - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00673001004727000	4727	target Essequibo - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00673001004728000	4728	target Essequibo - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00673001004729000	4729	target Essequibo - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00673001004730000	4730	target Essequibo - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00673001004731000	4731	target Essequibo - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00673	Essequibo stereo-2 ~3 cm standoff	3558MH00673001004732000	4732	autofocus sub-frame for target Essequibo - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		3558MH00673001004733000	4733	target Essequibo - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		3558MH00673001004734000	4734	target Essequibo - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00673001004735000	4735	target Essequibo - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00673002004736000	4736	target Essequibo - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00673002004737000	4737	target Essequibo - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00673002004738000	4738	target Essequibo - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00673002004739000	4739	target Essequibo - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00673002004740000	4740	target Essequibo - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00673002004741000	4741	target Essequibo - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00678	Kumu_Falls ~23 cm standoff	3558MH00678003004742000	4742	autofocus sub-frame for target Kumu_Falls - standoff near 23 cm
		3558MH00678003004743000	4743	target Kumu_Falls - standoff near 23 cm
		3558MH00678003004744000	4744	target Kumu_Falls - standoff near 23 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3558MH00678003004745000	4745	target Kumu_Falls - standoff near 23 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00678003004746000	4746	target Kumu_Falls - standoff near 23 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00678003004747000	4747	target Kumu_Falls - standoff near 23 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00678003004748000	4748	target Kumu_Falls - standoff near 23 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00678003004749000	4749	target Kumu_Falls - standoff near 23 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00678003004750000	4750	target Kumu_Falls - standoff near 23 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00678003004751000	4751	target Kumu_Falls - standoff near 23 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00166	Kumu_Falls stereo-1 ~3 cm standoff	3558MH00166002004752000	4752	target Kumu_Falls - standoff near 23 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00166002004753000	4753	autofocus sub-frame for target Kumu_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm
		3558MH00166002004754000	4754	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm
		3558MH00166002004755000	4755	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00166002004756000	4756	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00166002004757000	4757	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00166002004758000	4758	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00166002004759000	4759	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00166002004760000	4760	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00166002004761000	4761	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3558MH00166002004762000	4762	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mh00166	Kumu Falls stereo-2 ~3 cm standoff	355BMH00166000704763C0D	4763	autofocus sub-frame for target Kumu_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		355BMH001660010704764C0D	4764	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		355BMH00166000704765C0D	4765	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355BMH001660020704766C0D	4766	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355BMH00166000704767C0D	4767	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355BMH001660020704768C0D	4768	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355BMH00166000704769C0D	4769	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355BMH001660020704770C0D	4770	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355BMH00166000704771C0D	4771	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		355BMH001660020704772C0D	4772	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mh00171	Focus Merges	355BMH001710000704773R0D	4773	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3558 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 4765-4772 - best focus image product
		355BMH001710000704774S0D	4774	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3558 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 4765-4772 - range map product
		355BMH001710000704775R0D	4775	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3558 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 4755-4762 - best focus image product
		355BMH001710000704776S0D	4776	target Kumu_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3558 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 4755-4762 - range map product
		355BMH001710000704777R0D	4777	target Kumu_Falls - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3558 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 4745-4752 - best focus image product
		355BMH001710000704778S0D	4778	target Kumu_Falls - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3558 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 4745-4752 - range map product
		355BMH001710000704779R0D	4779	target Essequibo - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3558 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 4734-4741 - best focus image product
		355BMH001710000704780S0D	4780	target Essequibo - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3558 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 4734-4741 - range map product
		355BMH001710000704781R0D	4781	target Essequibo - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3558 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 4724-4731 - best focus image product
		355BMH001710000704782S0D	4782	target Essequibo - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3558 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 4724-4731 - range map product
		355BMH001710000704783R0D	4783	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3558 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 4712-4719 - best focus image product
		355BMH001710000704784S0D	4784	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3558 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 4712-4719 - range map product
		355BMH001710000704785R0D	4785	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3558 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 4702-4709 - best focus image product
		355BMH001710000704786S0D	4786	target Sao_Marcos - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3558 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 4702-4709 - range map product

updated: 11_October_2022

Sol 3560 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	12-Aug-22
camera position	2
total parent images	58
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	68

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Annai and the target Mirizal. The focus stack images were also merged. MAHLI images that correspond to COPIDs 1 through 3313 (data from Sols 3362-3482) were deleted from the MAHLI DEA non-volatile memory storage.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	COPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00706	Annai after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3560MH000706002074787C0D	4787	autofocus sub-frame for target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm		
		3560MH000706001074788C0D	4788	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm		
		3560MH000706002074789C0D	4789	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mN00763	Annai after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3560MH0007630000704795C0D	4790	autofocus sub-frame for target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3560MH0007630010704795C0D	4791	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3560MH0007630020704795C0D	4792	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3560MH0007630030704795C0D	4793	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0007630040704795C0D	4794	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0007630050704795C0D	4795	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0007630060704795C0D	4796	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0007630070704795C0D	4797	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0007630080704795C0D	4798	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0007630090704795C0D	4799	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00763	Annai after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3560MH0007630000704800C0D	4800	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0007630010704800C0D	4801	autofocus sub-frame for target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3560MH0007630020704800C0D	4802	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3560MH0007630030704800C0D	4803	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3560MH0007630040704800C0D	4804	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0007630050704800C0D	4805	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0007630060704800C0D	4806	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0007630070704800C0D	4807	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0007630080704800C0D	4808	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0007630090704800C0D	4809	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00835	Annai after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3560MH0008350000704810C0D	4810	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0008350010704810C0D	4811	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0008350020704810C0D	4812	autofocus sub-frame for target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm		
		3560MH0008350030704810C0D	4813	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm		
		3560MH0008350040704810C0D	4814	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3560MH0008350050704810C0D	4815	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0008350060704810C0D	4816	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0008350070704810C0D	4817	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0008350080704810C0D	4818	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0008350090704810C0D	4819	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00190	Mirizal ~24 cm standoff	3560MH0001900000704820C0D	4820	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0001900010704820C0D	4821	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0001900020704820C0D	4822	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0001900030704820C0D	4823	autofocus sub-frame for target Mirizal - standoff near 24 cm		
		3560MH0001900040704820C0D	4824	target Mirizal - standoff near 24 cm		
		mN00224	Mirizal stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3560MH0002240000704825C0D	4825	autofocus sub-frame for target Mirizal - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
				3560MH0002240010704825C0D	4826	target Mirizal - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
				3560MH0002240020704825C0D	4827	target Mirizal - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3560MH0002240030704825C0D	4828	target Mirizal - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3560MH0002240040704825C0D	4829	target Mirizal - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
3560MH0002240050704825C0D	4830			target Mirizal - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3560MH0002240060704825C0D	4831			target Mirizal - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3560MH0002240070704825C0D	4832			target Mirizal - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3560MH0002240080704825C0D	4833			target Mirizal - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3560MH0002240090704825C0D	4834			target Mirizal - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00224	Mirizal stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3560MH0002240000704835C0D	4835	autofocus sub-frame for target Mirizal - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3560MH0002240010704835C0D	4836	target Mirizal - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3560MH0002240020704835C0D	4837	target Mirizal - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0002240030704835C0D	4838	target Mirizal - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0002240040704835C0D	4839	target Mirizal - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0002240050704835C0D	4840	target Mirizal - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0002240060704835C0D	4841	target Mirizal - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0002240070704835C0D	4842	target Mirizal - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0002240080704835C0D	4843	target Mirizal - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3560MH0002240090704835C0D	4844	target Mirizal - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00227	Focus Merges	3560MH000227000070048490D	4845	target Mirizal - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3560 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4837-4844 - best focus image product		
		3560MH000227000070048490D	4846	target Mirizal - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3560 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4837-4844 - range map product		
		3560MH000227000070048490D	4847	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3560 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4827-4834 - best focus image product		
		3560MH000227000070048490D	4848	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3560 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4827-4834 - range map product		
		3560MH000227000070048490D	4849	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3560 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4815-4822 - best focus image product		
		3560MH000227000070048490D	4850	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3560 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4815-4822 - range map product		
		3560MH000227000070048490D	4851	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3560 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4804-4811 - best focus image product		
		3560MH000227000070048490D	4852	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3560 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4804-4811 - range map product		
		3560MH000227000070048490D	4853	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3560 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4793-4800 - best focus image product		
		3560MH000227000070048490D	4854	target Annai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3560 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4793-4800 - range map product		

updated: 12_October_2022

Sol 3562 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	16-Aug-22
camera positions	6
total parent images	58
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	58

MAHLI imaged the targets El_Silencio and Orinduk and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mNI00706	El_Silencio ~24 cm standoff	3562MH000706001400001C00	1	autofocus sub-frame for target El_Silencio - standoff near 24 cm		
		3562MH000706001300002C00	2	target El_Silencio - standoff near 24 cm		
		3562MH000706001200003C00	3	target El_Silencio - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00721	El_Silencio stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3562MH0007210011300004C00	4	autofocus sub-frame for target El_Silencio - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3562MH0007210011300005C00	5	target El_Silencio - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3562MH0007210011300006C00	6	target El_Silencio - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3562MH0007210011300007C00	7	target El_Silencio - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3562MH0007210011300008C00	8	target El_Silencio - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3562MH0007210011300009C00	9	target El_Silencio - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3562MH0007210011300010C00	10	target El_Silencio - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3562MH0007210011300011C00	11	target El_Silencio - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3562MH0007210011300012C00	12	target El_Silencio - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3562MH0007210011300013C00	13	target El_Silencio - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3562MH0007210011300014C00	14	target El_Silencio - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00721	El_Silencio stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3562MH0007210011300015C00	15	autofocus sub-frame for target El_Silencio - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
				3562MH0007210011300016C00	16	target El_Silencio - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
3562MH0007210011300017C00	17			target El_Silencio - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
3562MH0007210011300018C00	18			target El_Silencio - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3562MH0007210011300019C00	19			target El_Silencio - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3562MH0007210011300020C00	20			target El_Silencio - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3562MH0007210011300021C00	21			target El_Silencio - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3562MH0007210011300022C00	22			target El_Silencio - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3562MH0007210011300023C00	23			target El_Silencio - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3562MH0007210011300024C00	24			target El_Silencio - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3562MH0007210011300025C00	25			target El_Silencio - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00706	Orinduk ~24 cm standoff			3562MH000706001300026C00	26	autofocus sub-frame for target Orinduk - standoff near 24 cm
				3562MH000706001200027C00	27	target Orinduk - standoff near 24 cm
		3562MH000706001100028C00	28	target Orinduk - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00763	Orinduk stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3562MH0007063001130029C00	29	autofocus sub-frame for target Orinduk - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3562MH0007063001130030C00	30	target Orinduk - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3562MH0007063001130031C00	31	target Orinduk - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3562MH0007063001130032C00	32	target Orinduk - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3562MH0007063001130033C00	33	target Orinduk - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3562MH0007063001130034C00	34	target Orinduk - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3562MH0007063001130035C00	35	target Orinduk - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3562MH0007063001130036C00	36	target Orinduk - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3562MH0007063001130037C00	37	target Orinduk - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3562MH0007063001130038C00	38	target Orinduk - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3562MH0007063001130039C00	39	target Orinduk - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00763	Orinduk stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3562MH0007063001130040C00	40	autofocus sub-frame for target Orinduk - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
				3562MH0007063001130041C00	41	target Orinduk - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
3562MH0007063001130042C00	42			target Orinduk - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
3562MH0007063001130043C00	43			target Orinduk - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3562MH0007063001130044C00	44			target Orinduk - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3562MH0007063001130045C00	45			target Orinduk - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3562MH0007063001130046C00	46			target Orinduk - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3562MH0007063001130047C00	47			target Orinduk - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3562MH0007063001130048C00	48			target Orinduk - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3562MH0007063001130049C00	49			target Orinduk - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3562MH0007063001130050C00	50			target Orinduk - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00707	Focus Merges			3562MH000707001130051N00	51	target Orinduk - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3562 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 43-50 - best focus image product
				3562MH000707001130052N00	52	target Orinduk - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3562 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 43-50 - range map product
		3562MH000707001130053N00	53	target Orinduk - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3562 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 32-39 - best focus image product		
		3562MH000707001130054N00	54	target Orinduk - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3562 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 32-39 - range map product		
		3562MH000707001130055N00	55	target El_Silencio - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3562 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 18-25 - best focus image product		
		3562MH000707001130056N00	56	target El_Silencio - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3562 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 18-25 - range map product		
		3562MH000707001130057N00	57	target El_Silencio - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3562 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 7-14 - best focus image product		
		3562MH000707001130058N00	58	target El_Silencio - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3562 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 7-14 - range map product		

updated: 17_October_2022

Sol 3564 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	16-Aug-22
camera positions	6
total parent images	45
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	54

MAHLI imaged the targets Sand_Creek and Nascente and the focus stacks were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00705	Sand_Creek ~24 cm standoff	3564MH000706001300095000	59	autofocus sub-frame for target Sand_Creek - standoff near 24 cm
		3564MH000706001300096000	60	target Sand_Creek - standoff near 24 cm
		3564MH000706001300096100	61	target Sand_Creek - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00714	Sand_Creek ~35 mm standoff	3564MH000714001300062000	62	autofocus sub-frame for target Sand_Creek - standoff near 35 mm
		3564MH000714001300063000	63	target Sand_Creek - standoff near 35 mm
		3564MH000714001300064000	64	target Sand_Creek - standoff near 35 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3564MH000714001300065000	65	target Sand_Creek - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000714001300066000	66	target Sand_Creek - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000714001300067000	67	target Sand_Creek - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000714001300068000	68	target Sand_Creek - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000714001300069000	69	target Sand_Creek - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000714001300070000	70	target Sand_Creek - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000714001300071000	71	target Sand_Creek - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000714001300072000	72	target Sand_Creek - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00730	Nascente ~26 cm standoff	3564MH000190001300073000
3564MH000190001300074000	74			target Nascente - standoff near 26 cm
mN00299	Nascente stereo-1 ~35 mm standoff	3564MH000299001300075000	75	autofocus sub-frame for target Nascente - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3564MH000299001300076000	76	target Nascente - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3564MH000299001300077000	77	target Nascente - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000299001300078000	78	target Nascente - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000299001300079000	79	target Nascente - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000299001300080000	80	target Nascente - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000299001300081000	81	target Nascente - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000299001300082000	82	target Nascente - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000299001300083000	83	target Nascente - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000299001300084000	84	target Nascente - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00299	Nascente stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff	3564MH000299001300085000	85	autofocus sub-frame for target Nascente - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3564MH000299001300086000	86	target Nascente - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3564MH000299001300087000	87	target Nascente - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000299001300088000	88	target Nascente - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000299001300089000	89	target Nascente - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000299001300090000	90	target Nascente - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000299001300091000	91	target Nascente - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000299001300092000	92	target Nascente - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000299001300093000	93	target Nascente - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000299001300094000	94	target Nascente - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00337	Nascente ~25 mm standoff	3564MH000337001300095000	95	autofocus sub-frame for target Nascente - standoff near 25 mm
		3564MH000337001300096000	96	target Nascente - standoff near 25 mm
		3564MH000337001300097000	97	target Nascente - standoff near 25 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000337001300098000	98	target Nascente - standoff near 25 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000337001300099000	99	target Nascente - standoff near 25 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000337001300100000	100	target Nascente - standoff near 25 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000337001300101000	101	target Nascente - standoff near 25 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000337001300102000	102	target Nascente - standoff near 25 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000337001300103000	103	target Nascente - standoff near 25 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3564MH000337001300104000	104	target Nascente - standoff near 25 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00806	Focus Merges	3564MH000806001300105000	105	target Nascente - standoff near 25 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3564 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 97-104 - best focus image product
		3564MH000806001300106000	106	target Nascente - standoff near 25 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3564 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 97-104 - range map product
		3564MH000806001300107000	107	target Nascente - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3564 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 87-94 - best focus image product
		3564MH000806001300108000	108	target Nascente - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3564 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 87-94 - range map product
		3564MH000806001300109000	109	target Nascente - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3564 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 77-84 - best focus image product
		3564MH000806001300110000	110	target Nascente - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3564 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 77-84 - range map product
		3564MH000806001300111000	111	target Sand_Creek - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3564 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 65-72 - best focus image product
		3564MH000806001300112000	112	target Sand_Creek - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3564 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 65-72 - range map product

updated: 14_October_2022

Sol 3566 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	18-Aug-22
camera position	4
total parent images	27
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	27

MAHLI imaged the REMS UV Sensor and the target Yupiter.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00095	REMS UV sensor ~15 cm standoff	3566MH0009500130011300	113	autofocus sub-frame for REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
		3566MH0009500130011400	114	REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
mN00706	Yupiter ~23 cm standoff	3566MH00070600130011500	115	autofocus sub-frame for target Yupiter - standoff near 23 cm
		3566MH00070600130011600	116	target Yupiter - standoff near 23 cm
		3566MH00070600130011700	117	target Yupiter - standoff near 23 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00709	Yupiter stereo-1 ~35 mm standoff	3566MH00070900130011800	118	autofocus sub-frame for target Yupiter - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3566MH00070900130011900	119	target Yupiter - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3566MH00070900130012000	120	target Yupiter - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3566MH00070900130012100	121	target Yupiter - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3566MH00070900130012200	122	target Yupiter - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3566MH00070900130012300	123	target Yupiter - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3566MH00070900130012400	124	target Yupiter - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3566MH00070900130012500	125	target Yupiter - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3566MH00070900130012600	126	target Yupiter - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3566MH00070900130012700	127	target Yupiter - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3566MH00070900130012800	128	target Yupiter - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00709	Yupiter stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff	3566MH00070900130012900	129	autofocus sub-frame for target Yupiter - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3566MH00070900130013000	130	target Yupiter - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3566MH00070900130013100	131	target Yupiter - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3566MH00070900130013200	132	target Yupiter - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3566MH00070900130013300	133	target Yupiter - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3566MH00070900130013400	134	target Yupiter - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3566MH00070900130013500	135	target Yupiter - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3566MH00070900130013600	136	target Yupiter - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3566MH00070900130013700	137	target Yupiter - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3566MH00070900130013800	138	target Yupiter - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3566MH00070900130013900	139	target Yupiter - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 07_September_2022

Sol 3567 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	19-Aug-22			
camera position:	0	Image ID:		
total parent images:	0	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
focus merges performed:	2	CDPID:		
total focus merge products:	4	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
total parent images + focus merge products:	4			
summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3566 were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m100703	Focus Merges	3567MH007030001300140900	140	target Yupukari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3566 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 132-139 - best focus image product
		3567MH007030001300141500	141	target Yupukari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3566 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 132-139 - range map product
		3567MH007030001300142900	142	target Yupukari - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3566 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 121-128 - best focus image product
		3567MH007030001300143500	143	target Yupukari - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3566 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 121-128 - range map product

updated: 13_October_2022

Sol 3568 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	20-Aug-22
camera positions	13
total parent images	75
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	75

MAHLI imaged the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets as well as the target Fortaleza and the DRT-brushed target Massara.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00371	MAHLI cal target - centered on bar target ~5 cm working distance	3568MH0003720013001440C0	144	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
		3568MH0003720013001450C0	145	MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
mNI00372	MAHLI cal target - centered on cent target ~5 cm working distance	3568MH0003720013001460C0	146	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
		3568MH0003720013001470C0	147	MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
mNI00374	MAHLI cal target + wheel + surface ~30 cm working distance from target	3568MH0003740013001480C0	148	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		3568MH0003740013001490C0	149	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		3568MH0003740013001500C0	150	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - manual focus at infinity
mNI00373	APXS cal target ~5 cm standoff	3568MH0003730013001510C0	151	autofocus sub-frame for APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
		3568MH0003730013001520C0	152	APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
mNI00376	Fortaleza ~24 cm standoff	3568MH000760013001530C0	153	autofocus sub-frame for target Fortaleza - standoff near 24 cm
		3568MH000760013001540C0	154	target Fortaleza - standoff near 24 cm
		3568MH000760013001550C0	155	target Fortaleza - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00714	Fortaleza stereo-1 ~35 mm standoff	3568MH0007140013001560C0	156	autofocus sub-frame for target Fortaleza - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3568MH0007140013001570C0	157	target Fortaleza - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3568MH0007140013001580C0	158	target Fortaleza - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3568MH0007140013001590C0	159	target Fortaleza - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0007140013001600C0	160	target Fortaleza - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0007140013001610C0	161	target Fortaleza - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0007140013001620C0	162	target Fortaleza - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0007140013001630C0	163	target Fortaleza - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0007140013001640C0	164	target Fortaleza - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0007140013001650C0	165	target Fortaleza - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00714	Fortaleza stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff	3568MH0007140013001660C0	166	target Fortaleza - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0007140013001670C0	167	autofocus sub-frame for target Fortaleza - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3568MH0007140013001680C0	168	target Fortaleza - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3568MH0007140013001690C0	169	target Fortaleza - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3568MH0007140013001700C0	170	target Fortaleza - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0007140013001710C0	171	target Fortaleza - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0007140013001720C0	172	target Fortaleza - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0007140013001730C0	173	target Fortaleza - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0007140013001740C0	174	target Fortaleza - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0007140013001750C0	175	target Fortaleza - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00706	Massara after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3568MH000760013001760C0	176	target Fortaleza - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0007140013001770C0	177	target Fortaleza - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH000760013001780C0	178	autofocus sub-frame for target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mNI00834	Massara after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3568MH0008340013001790C0	179	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3568MH0008340013001800C0	180	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3568MH0008340013001810C0	181	autofocus sub-frame for target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3568MH0008340013001820C0	182	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3568MH0008340013001830C0	183	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3568MH0008340013001840C0	184	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0008340013001850C0	185	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0008340013001860C0	186	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0008340013001870C0	187	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0008340013001880C0	188	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00834	Massara after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3568MH0008340013001890C0	189	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0008340013001900C0	190	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0008340013001910C0	191	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0008340013001920C0	192	autofocus sub-frame for target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3568MH0008340013001930C0	193	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3568MH0008340013001940C0	194	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3568MH0008340013001950C0	195	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0008340013001960C0	196	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0008340013001970C0	197	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0008340013001980C0	198	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00834	Massara after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3568MH0008340013001990C0	199	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0008340013002000C0	200	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0008340013002010C0	201	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3568MH0008340013002020C0	202	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

Continued on Next Page...

mH00785	Massara after DRT -1 cm standoff	356BMH00785001300203K00	203	autofocus sub-frame for target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		356BMH00785001300204C00	204	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		356BMH00785001300205C00	205	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		356BMH00785001300206C00	206	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		356BMH00785001300207C00	207	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		356BMH00785001300208C00	208	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		356BMH00785001300209C00	209	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		356BMH00785001300210C00	210	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		356BMH00785001300211C00	211	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		356BMH00785001300212C00	212	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		356BMH00785001300213C00	213	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 22_August_2022

Sol 3570 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	22-Aug-22
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	10

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3568 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3570MH0002270001300214800	214	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3568 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 206-213 - best focus image product
		3570MH0002270001300215500	215	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3568 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 206-213 - range map product
		3570MH0002270001300216800	216	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3568 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 195-202 - best focus image product
		3570MH0002270001300217500	217	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3568 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 195-202 - range map product
		3570MH0002270001300218800	218	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3568 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 184-191 - best focus image product
		3570MH0002270001300219500	219	target Massara - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3568 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 184-191 - range map product
		3570MH0002270001300220800	220	target Fortaleza - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3568 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 170-177 - best focus image product
		3570MH0002270001300221500	221	target Fortaleza - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3568 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 170-177 - range map product
		3570MH0002270001300222800	222	target Fortaleza - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3568 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 159-166 - best focus image product
		3570MH0002270001300223500	223	target Fortaleza - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3568 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 159-166 - range map product

updated: 13_October_2022

Sol 3571 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	23-Aug-22
camera positions	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the target Raimundo and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Raimundo ~25 cm standoff	3571MH000190001300224000	224	autofocus sub-frame for target Raimundo - standoff near 25 cm
		3571MH000190001300225000	225	target Raimundo - standoff near 25 cm
mN00224	Raimundo stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3571MH000224001300226000	226	autofocus sub-frame for target Raimundo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3571MH000224001300227000	227	target Raimundo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3571MH000224001300228000	228	target Raimundo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000224001300229000	229	target Raimundo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000224001300230000	230	target Raimundo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000224001300231000	231	target Raimundo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000224001300232000	232	target Raimundo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000224001300233000	233	target Raimundo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000224001300234000	234	target Raimundo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000224001300235000	235	target Raimundo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	Raimundo stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3571MH000224001300236000	236	autofocus sub-frame for target Raimundo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3571MH000224001300237000	237	target Raimundo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3571MH000224001300238000	238	target Raimundo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000224001300239000	239	target Raimundo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000224001300240000	240	target Raimundo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000224001300241000	241	target Raimundo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000224001300242000	242	target Raimundo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000224001300243000	243	target Raimundo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000224001300244000	244	target Raimundo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000224001300245000	245	target Raimundo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00307	Raimundo ~2 cm standoff	3571MH000307001300246000	246	autofocus sub-frame for target Raimundo - standoff near 2 cm
		3571MH000307001300247000	247	target Raimundo - standoff near 2 cm
		3571MH000307001300248000	248	target Raimundo - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000307001300249000	249	target Raimundo - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000307001300250000	250	target Raimundo - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000307001300251000	251	target Raimundo - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000307001300252000	252	target Raimundo - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000307001300253000	253	target Raimundo - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000307001300254000	254	target Raimundo - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3571MH000307001300255000	255	target Raimundo - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00289	Focus Merges	3571MH000193001300256000	256	target Raimundo - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3571 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 248-255 - best focus image product
		3571MH000193001300257000	257	target Raimundo - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3571 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 248-255 - range map product
		3571MH000193001300258000	258	target Raimundo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3571 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 238-245 - best focus image product
		3571MH000193001300259000	259	target Raimundo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3571 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 238-245 - range map product
		3571MH000193001300260000	260	target Raimundo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3571 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 228-235 - best focus image product
		3571MH000193001300261500	261	target Raimundo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3571 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 228-235 - range map product

updated: 14_October_2022

Sol 3573 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)		25-Aug-22	
		camera position	95	image ID:	
		total parent images	95	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received	
		focus merges performed	0	CDPID:	
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	
		total parent images + focus merge products	95		
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the targets Kanuku and Wadakapiapue.					
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)	
mN00190	Kanuku ~25 cm standoff	3573MH0001900011300262C00	262	autofocus sub-frame for target Kanuku - standoff near 25 cm	
		3573MH0001900011300263C00	263	target Kanuku - standoff near 25 cm	
mN00297	Kanuku stereo-1 relief model position 1 ~65 mm standoff	3573MH0002970011300264C00	264	autofocus sub-frame for target Kanuku - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 65 mm	
		3573MH0002970011300265C00	265	target Kanuku - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 65 mm	
		3573MH0002970011300266C00	266	target Kanuku - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 65 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0002970011300267C00	267	target Kanuku - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 65 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0002970011300268C00	268	target Kanuku - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 65 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0002970011300269C00	269	target Kanuku - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 65 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0002970011300270C00	270	target Kanuku - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 65 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0002970011300271C00	271	target Kanuku - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 65 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0002970011300272C00	272	target Kanuku - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 65 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0002970011300273C00	273	target Kanuku - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 65 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00297	Kanuku stereo-2 relief model position 2 ~65 mm standoff	3573MH0002970011300274C00	274	autofocus sub-frame for target Kanuku - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 65 mm	
		3573MH0002970011300275C00	275	target Kanuku - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 65 mm	
		3573MH0002970011300276C00	276	target Kanuku - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 65 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0002970011300277C00	277	target Kanuku - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 65 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0002970011300278C00	278	target Kanuku - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 65 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0002970011300279C00	279	target Kanuku - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 65 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0002970011300280C00	280	target Kanuku - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 65 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0002970011300281C00	281	target Kanuku - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 65 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0002970011300282C00	282	target Kanuku - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 65 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0002970011300283C00	283	target Kanuku - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 65 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00705	Kanuku relief model position 3 ~65 mm standoff	3573MH0007050011300284C00	284	autofocus sub-frame for target Kanuku - relief model position 3 - standoff near 65 mm	
		3573MH0007050011300285C00	285	target Kanuku - relief model position 3 - standoff near 65 mm	
mN00705	Kanuku relief model position 4 ~65 mm standoff	3573MH0007050011300286C00	286	autofocus sub-frame for target Kanuku - relief model position 4 - standoff near 65 mm	
		3573MH0007050011300287C00	287	target Kanuku - relief model position 4 - standoff near 65 mm	
mN00705	Kanuku relief model position 5 ~65 mm standoff	3573MH0007050011300288C00	288	autofocus sub-frame for target Kanuku - relief model position 5 - standoff near 65 mm	
		3573MH0007050011300289C00	289	target Kanuku - relief model position 5 - standoff near 65 mm	
mN00311	Kanuku ~35 mm standoff	3573MH0003110011300290C00	290	autofocus sub-frame for target Kanuku - standoff near 35 mm	
		3573MH0003110011300291C00	291	target Kanuku - standoff near 35 mm	
		3573MH0003110011300292C00	292	target Kanuku - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0003110011300293C00	293	target Kanuku - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0003110011300294C00	294	target Kanuku - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0003110011300295C00	295	target Kanuku - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0003110011300296C00	296	target Kanuku - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0003110011300297C00	297	target Kanuku - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0003110011300298C00	298	target Kanuku - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0003110011300299C00	299	target Kanuku - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00190	Wadakapiapue ~25 cm standoff	3573MH0001900011300300C00	300	autofocus sub-frame for target Wadakapiapue - standoff near 25 cm	
		3573MH0001900011300301C00	301	target Wadakapiapue - standoff near 25 cm	
mN00182	Wadakapiapue stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3573MH0001820011300302C00	302	autofocus sub-frame for target Wadakapiapue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm	
		3573MH0001820011300303C00	303	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm	
		3573MH0001820011300304C00	304	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0001820011300305C00	305	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0001820011300306C00	306	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0001820011300307C00	307	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0001820011300308C00	308	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0001820011300309C00	309	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0001820011300310C00	310	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0001820011300311C00	311	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00182	Wadakapiapue stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3573MH0001820011300312C00	312	autofocus sub-frame for target Wadakapiapue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm	
		3573MH0001820011300313C00	313	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm	
		3573MH0001820011300314C00	314	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0001820011300315C00	315	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0001820011300316C00	316	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0001820011300317C00	317	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0001820011300318C00	318	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0001820011300319C00	319	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0001820011300320C00	320	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3573MH0001820011300321C00	321	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	

updated: 29_August_2022

Sol 3574 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26-Aug-22
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total parent focus products	10
total focus merge products	10

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3573 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3574MH0002270001300322800	322	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3573 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 314-321 - best focus image product
		3574MH0002270001300323500	323	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3573 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 314-321 - range map product
		3574MH0002270001300324800	324	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3573 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 304-311 - best focus image product
		3574MH0002270001300325500	325	target Wadakapiapue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3573 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 304-311 - range map product
		3574MH0002270001300326800	326	target Kanuku - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3573 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 292-299 - best focus image product
		3574MH0002270001300327500	327	target Kanuku - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3573 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 292-299 - range map product
		3574MH0002270001300328800	328	target Kanuku - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 65 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3573 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 276-283 - best focus image product
		3574MH0002270001300329500	329	target Kanuku - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 65 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3573 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 276-283 - range map product
		3574MH0002270001300330800	330	target Kanuku - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 65 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3573 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 266-273 - best focus image product
		3574MH0002270001300331500	331	target Kanuku - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 65 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3573 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 266-273 - range map product

Sol 3575 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	27-Aug-22
camera positions	13
total parent images	85
focus merges performed	8
total focus merge products	18
total parent images + focus merge products	103

MAHLI imaged the targets Los_Rosos, Nova_Estrela and Enamuna and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN000190	Los_Rosos ~25 cm standoff	37575MH000178001130033200	332	autofocus sub-frame for target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
		37575MH000178001130033300	333	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
mN000173	Los_Rosos APXS spot 1 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	37575MH000178001130033400	334	autofocus sub-frame for target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		37575MH000178001130033500	335	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		37575MH000178001130033600	336	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130033700	337	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130033800	338	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130033900	339	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130034000	340	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130034100	341	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130034200	342	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130034300	343	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000173	Los_Rosos APXS spot 1 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	37575MH000178001130034400	344	autofocus sub-frame for target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		37575MH000178001130034500	345	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		37575MH000178001130034600	346	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130034700	347	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130034800	348	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130034900	349	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130035000	350	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130035100	351	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130035200	352	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130035300	353	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000173	Los_Rosos APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	37575MH000178001130035400	354	autofocus sub-frame for target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		37575MH000178001130035500	355	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		37575MH000178001130035600	356	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130035700	357	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130035800	358	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130035900	359	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130036000	360	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130036100	361	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130036200	362	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130036300	363	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000190	Nova_Estrela ~24 cm standoff	37575MH000190001130036400	364	autofocus sub-frame for target Nova_Estrela - standoff near 24 cm
mN000173	Nova_Estrela stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	37575MH000190001130036500	365	target Nova_Estrela - standoff near 24 cm
		37575MH000178001130036600	366	autofocus sub-frame for target Nova_Estrela - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		37575MH000178001130036700	367	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		37575MH000178001130036800	368	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130036900	369	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130037000	370	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130037100	371	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130037200	372	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130037300	373	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130037400	374	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000173	Nova_Estrela stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	37575MH000178001130037500	375	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130037600	376	autofocus sub-frame for target Nova_Estrela - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		37575MH000178001130037700	377	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		37575MH000178001130037800	378	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130037900	379	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130038000	380	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130038100	381	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130038200	382	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130038300	383	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000178001130038400	384	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000302	Nova_Estrela ~2 cm standoff	37575MH000302001130038500	385	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000302001130038600	386	autofocus sub-frame for target Nova_Estrela - standoff near 2 cm
		37575MH000302001130038700	387	target Nova_Estrela - standoff near 2 cm
		37575MH000302001130038800	388	target Nova_Estrela - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000302001130038900	389	target Nova_Estrela - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000302001130039000	390	target Nova_Estrela - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000302001130039100	391	target Nova_Estrela - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000302001130039200	392	target Nova_Estrela - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000302001130039300	393	target Nova_Estrela - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000302001130039400	394	target Nova_Estrela - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000190	Enamuna ~23 cm standoff	37575MH000190001130039500	395	target Nova_Estrela - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		37575MH000190001130039600	396	autofocus sub-frame for target Enamuna - standoff near 23 cm
		37575MH000190001130039700	397	target Enamuna - standoff near 23 cm

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mH00306	Enamuna stereo-1 *35 mm standoff	3575MH00306001300398C00	398	autofocus sub-frame for target Enamuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3575MH00306001300399C00	399	target Enamuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3575MH00306001300400C00	400	target Enamuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3575MH00306001300401C00	401	target Enamuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3575MH00306001300402C00	402	target Enamuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3575MH00306001300403C00	403	target Enamuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3575MH00306001300404C00	404	target Enamuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3575MH00306001300405C00	405	target Enamuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3575MH00306001300406C00	406	target Enamuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3575MH00306001300407C00	407	target Enamuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00306	Enamuna stereo-2 *35 mm standoff	3575MH00306001300408C00	408	autofocus sub-frame for target Enamuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3575MH00306001300409C00	409	target Enamuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3575MH00306001300410C00	410	target Enamuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3575MH00306001300411C00	411	target Enamuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3575MH00306001300412C00	412	target Enamuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3575MH00306001300413C00	413	target Enamuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3575MH00306001300414C00	414	target Enamuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3575MH00306001300415C00	415	target Enamuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3575MH00306001300416C00	416	target Enamuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3575MH00306001300417C00	417	target Enamuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00310	Focus Merges	3575MH00170001300418R00	418	target Enamuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 410-417 - best focus image product
		3575MH00170001300419S00	419	target Enamuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 410-417 - range map product
		3575MH00170001300420R00	420	target Enamuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 400-407 - best focus image product
		3575MH00170001300421S00	421	target Enamuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 400-407 - range map product
		3575MH00170001300422R00	422	target Nova_Estrela - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 388-395 - best focus image product
		3575MH00170001300423S00	423	target Nova_Estrela - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 388-395 - range map product
		3575MH00170001300424R00	424	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 378-385 - best focus image product
		3575MH00170001300425S00	425	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 378-385 - range map product
		3575MH00170001300426R00	426	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 368-375 - best focus image product
		3575MH00170001300427S00	427	target Nova_Estrela - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 368-375 - range map product
		3575MH00170001300428R00	428	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 356-363 - best focus image product
		3575MH00170001300429S00	429	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 356-363 - range map product
		3575MH00170001300430R00	430	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 344-353 - best focus image product
		3575MH00170001300431S00	431	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 344-353 - range map product
		3575MH00170001300432R00	432	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 336-343 - best focus image product
3575MH00170001300433S00	433	target Los_Rosos - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3575 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 336-343 - range map product		

Sol 3578 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	30-Aug-22
camera position	6
total parent images	75
focus merges performed	7
total focus merge products	14
total parent images + focus merge products	93

MAHLI imaged the target Jacamim and the DRT-brushed target Micobie. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Jacamim ~24 cm standoff	3578MH0019000130043420	434	autofocus sub-frame for target Jacamim - standoff near 24 cm
		3578MH0019000130043520	435	target Jacamim - standoff near 24 cm
mN00168	Jacamim stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3578MH0016800130043620	436	autofocus sub-frame for target Jacamim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3578MH0016800130043720	437	target Jacamim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3578MH0016800130043820	438	target Jacamim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0016800130043920	439	target Jacamim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0016800130044020	440	target Jacamim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0016800130044120	441	target Jacamim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0016800130044220	442	target Jacamim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0016800130044320	443	target Jacamim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0016800130044420	444	target Jacamim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0016800130044520	445	target Jacamim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Jacamim stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3578MH0016800130044620	446	autofocus sub-frame for target Jacamim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3578MH0016800130044720	447	target Jacamim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3578MH0016800130044820	448	target Jacamim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0016800130044920	449	target Jacamim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0016800130045020	450	target Jacamim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0016800130045120	451	target Jacamim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0016800130045220	452	target Jacamim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0016800130045320	453	target Jacamim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0016800130045420	454	target Jacamim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0016800130045520	455	target Jacamim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00426	Jacamim ~1 cm standoff	3578MH0042600130045620	456	autofocus sub-frame for target Jacamim - standoff near 1 cm
		3578MH0042600130045720	457	target Jacamim - standoff near 1 cm
		3578MH0042600130045820	458	target Jacamim - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0042600130045920	459	target Jacamim - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0042600130046020	460	target Jacamim - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0042600130046120	461	target Jacamim - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0042600130046220	462	target Jacamim - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0042600130046320	463	target Jacamim - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0042600130046420	464	target Jacamim - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0042600130046520	465	target Jacamim - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00706	Micobie after DRT ~24 cm standoff	3578MH0070600130046620	466	autofocus sub-frame for target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 24 cm
		3578MH0070600130046720	467	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 24 cm
mN00834	Micobie after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3578MH0083400130046820	468	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3578MH0083400130046920	469	autofocus sub-frame for target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3578MH0083400130047020	470	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3578MH0083400130047120	471	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3578MH0083400130047220	472	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083400130047320	473	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083400130047420	474	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083400130047520	475	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083400130047620	476	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083400130047720	477	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00834	Micobie after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3578MH0083400130047820	478	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083400130047920	479	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083400130048020	480	autofocus sub-frame for target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3578MH0083400130048120	481	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3578MH0083400130048220	482	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3578MH0083400130048320	483	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083400130048420	484	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083400130048520	485	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083400130048620	486	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083400130048720	487	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00835	Micobie after DRT APXS spot 2 ~1 cm standoff	3578MH0083500130048820	488	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083500130048920	489	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083500130049020	490	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083500130049120	491	autofocus sub-frame for target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3578MH0083500130049220	492	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3578MH0083500130049320	493	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3578MH0083500130049420	494	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083500130049520	495	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083500130049620	496	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083500130049720	497	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00835	Micobie after DRT APXS spot 2 ~1 cm standoff	3578MH0083500130049820	498	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083500130049920	499	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083500130050020	500	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083500130050120	501	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mH00814	Micobie after DBT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3578MH0083400130050200	502	autofocus sub-frame for target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DBT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3578MH0083400130050300	503	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DBT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3578MH0083400130050400	504	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DBT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3578MH0083400130050500	505	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DBT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083400130050600	506	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DBT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083400130050700	507	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DBT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083400130050800	508	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DBT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083400130050900	509	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DBT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083400130051000	510	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DBT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083400130051100	511	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DBT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3578MH0083400130051200	512	target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DBT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mH00171	Focus Merges	3578MH00171000130051300
3578MH00171000130051400	514			target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DBT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3578 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 505-512 - range map product
3578MH00171000130051500	515			target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DBT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3578 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 494-501 - best focus image product
3578MH00171000130051600	516			target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DBT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3578 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 494-501 - range map product
3578MH00171000130051700	517			target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DBT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3578 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 483-490 - best focus image product
3578MH00171000130051800	518			target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DBT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3578 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 483-490 - range map product
3578MH00171000130051900	519			target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DBT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3578 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 472-479 - best focus image product
3578MH00171000130052000	520			target Micobie - after dust removal tool (DBT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3578 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 472-479 - range map product
3578MH00171000130052100	521			target Jacamim - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3578 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 458-465 - best focus image product
3578MH00171000130052200	522			target Jacamim - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3578 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 458-465 - range map product
3578MH00171000130052300	523			target Jacamim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3578 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 448-455 - best focus image product
3578MH00171000130052400	524			target Jacamim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3578 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 448-455 - range map product
3578MH00171000130052500	525			target Jacamim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3578 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 438-445 - best focus image product
3578MH00171000130052600	526			target Jacamim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3578 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 438-445 - range map product

updated: 17_October_2022

Sol 3583 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	4 Sep 22
camera position	2
total parent images	54
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	54

MAHLI imaged the targets Marie_Island, Branco and Machado.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00855	Marie_Island ~25 cm standoff	358MH000855001130057920	527	autofocus sub-frame for target Marie_Island - standoff near 25 cm
		358MH000855001130052820	528	target Marie_Island - standoff near 25 cm
		358MH000855001130052920	529	target Marie_Island - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000855001130053020	530	target Marie_Island - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000855001130053120	531	target Marie_Island - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000855001130053220	532	target Marie_Island - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000855001130053320	533	target Marie_Island - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000855001130053420	534	target Marie_Island - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000855001130053520	535	target Marie_Island - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000855001130053620	536	target Marie_Island - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Branco ~25 cm standoff	358MH000190001130057920	537	autofocus sub-frame for target Branco - standoff near 25 cm
		358MH000190001130053820	538	target Branco - standoff near 25 cm
mN00306	Branco stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	358MH000306001130053920	539	autofocus sub-frame for target Branco - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		358MH000306001130054020	540	target Branco - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		358MH000306001130054120	541	target Branco - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000306001130054220	542	target Branco - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000306001130054320	543	target Branco - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000306001130054420	544	target Branco - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000306001130054520	545	target Branco - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000306001130054620	546	target Branco - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000306001130054720	547	target Branco - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000306001130054820	548	target Branco - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00306	Branco stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	358MH000306001130054920	549	autofocus sub-frame for target Branco - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		358MH000306001130055020	550	target Branco - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		358MH000306001130055120	551	target Branco - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000306001130055220	552	target Branco - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000306001130055320	553	target Branco - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000306001130055420	554	target Branco - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000306001130055520	555	target Branco - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000306001130055620	556	target Branco - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000306001130055720	557	target Branco - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000306001130055820	558	target Branco - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Machado ~25 cm standoff	358MH000190001130055920	559	autofocus sub-frame for target Machado - standoff near 25 cm
		358MH000190001130056020	560	target Machado - standoff near 25 cm
mN00299	Machado stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	358MH000299001130056120	561	autofocus sub-frame for target Machado - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		358MH000299001130056220	562	target Machado - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		358MH000299001130056320	563	target Machado - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000299001130056420	564	target Machado - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000299001130056520	565	target Machado - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000299001130056620	566	target Machado - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000299001130056720	567	target Machado - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000299001130056820	568	target Machado - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000299001130056920	569	target Machado - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000299001130057020	570	target Machado - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00299	Machado stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	358MH000299001130057120	571	autofocus sub-frame for target Machado - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		358MH000299001130057220	572	target Machado - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		358MH000299001130057320	573	target Machado - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000299001130057420	574	target Machado - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000299001130057520	575	target Machado - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000299001130057620	576	target Machado - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000299001130057720	577	target Machado - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000299001130057820	578	target Machado - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000299001130057920	579	target Machado - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		358MH000299001130058020	580	target Machado - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 12_September_2022

Sol 3590 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	11-Sep-22
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	10

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3583 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3590MH0002270001300581300	581	target Machado - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3583 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 573-580 - best focus image product
		3590MH0002270001300582500	582	target Machado - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3583 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 573-580 - range map product
		3590MH0002270001300583900	583	target Machado - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3583 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 563-570 - best focus image product
		3590MH0002270001300584500	584	target Machado - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3583 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 563-570 - range map product
		3590MH0002270001300585900	585	target Branco - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3583 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 551-558 - best focus image product
		3590MH0002270001300586500	586	target Branco - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3583 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 551-558 - range map product
		3590MH0002270001300587900	587	target Branco - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3583 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 541-548 - best focus image product
		3590MH0002270001300588500	588	target Branco - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3583 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 541-548 - range map product
		3590MH0002270001300589900	589	target Marie_Island - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3583 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 529-536 - best focus image product
		3590MH0002270001300590500	590	target Marie_Island - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3583 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 529-536 - range map product

updated: 17_October_2022

Sol 3592 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	18-Sep-22
camera positions	8
total parent images	23
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	26

MAHLI imaged the target Piabas and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Piabas ~24 cm standoff	3592MH000190001300591C00	591	autofocus sub-frame for target Piabas - standoff near 24 cm
		3592MH000190001300592C00	592	target Piabas - standoff near 24 cm
mN00363	Piabas stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3592MH000363001300593C00	593	autofocus sub-frame for target Piabas - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3592MH000363001300594C00	594	target Piabas - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3592MH000363001300595C00	595	target Piabas - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3592MH000363001300596C00	596	target Piabas - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3592MH000363001300597C00	597	target Piabas - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3592MH000363001300598C00	598	target Piabas - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3592MH000363001300599C00	599	target Piabas - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3592MH000363001300600C00	600	target Piabas - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3592MH000363001300601C00	601	target Piabas - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3592MH000363001300602C00	602	target Piabas - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00363	Piabas stereo-2 ~3 cm standoff	3592MH000363001300603C00	603	autofocus sub-frame for target Piabas - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		3592MH000363001300604C00	604	target Piabas - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		3592MH000363001300605C00	605	target Piabas - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3592MH000363001300606C00	606	target Piabas - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3592MH000363001300607C00	607	target Piabas - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3592MH000363001300608C00	608	target Piabas - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3592MH000363001300609C00	609	target Piabas - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3592MH000363001300610C00	610	target Piabas - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3592MH000363001300611C00	611	target Piabas - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3592MH000363001300612C00	612	target Piabas - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00265	Focus Merges	3592MH000265001300613R00	613	target Piabas - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3592 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 605-612 - best focus image product
		3592MH000265001300614S00	614	target Piabas - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3592 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 605-612 - range map product
		3592MH000265001300615R00	615	target Piabas - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3592 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 595-602 - best focus image product
		3592MH000265001300616S00	616	target Piabas - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3592 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 595-602 - range map product

updated: 17_October_2022

Sol 3594 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	04-Sep-2016/2016
camera position	6
total parent images	53
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	63

MAHLI imaged the targets Tiger_Pond and La_Mata. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Tiger_Pond ~24 cm standoff	3594MH000190001300617000	617	autofocus sub-frame for target Tiger_Pond - standoff near 24 cm
		3594MH000190001300618000	618	target Tiger_Pond - standoff near 24 cm
mN00673	Tiger_Pond stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3594MH000673001300619000	619	autofocus sub-frame for target Tiger_Pond - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3594MH000673001300620000	620	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3594MH000673001300621000	621	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000673001300622000	622	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000673001300623000	623	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000673001300624000	624	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000673001300625000	625	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000673001300626000	626	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000673001300627000	627	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000673001300628000	628	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00673	Tiger_Pond stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3594MH000673001300629000	629	autofocus sub-frame for target Tiger_Pond - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3594MH000673001300630000	630	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3594MH000673001300631000	631	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000673001300632000	632	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000673001300633000	633	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000673001300634000	634	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000673001300635000	635	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000673001300636000	636	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000673001300637000	637	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000673001300638000	638	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00291	La_Mata ~9 cm standoff	3594MH000291001300639000	639	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Mata - standoff near 9 cm
		3594MH000291001300640000	640	target La_Mata - standoff near 9 cm
		3594MH000291001300641000	641	target La_Mata - standoff near 9 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000291001300642000	642	target La_Mata - standoff near 9 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000291001300643000	643	target La_Mata - standoff near 9 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000291001300644000	644	target La_Mata - standoff near 9 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000291001300645000	645	target La_Mata - standoff near 9 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000291001300646000	646	target La_Mata - standoff near 9 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000291001300647000	647	target La_Mata - standoff near 9 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000291001300648000	648	target La_Mata - standoff near 9 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00358	La_Mata stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3594MH000358001300649000	649	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Mata - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3594MH000358001300650000	650	target La_Mata - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3594MH000358001300651000	651	target La_Mata - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000358001300652000	652	target La_Mata - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000358001300653000	653	target La_Mata - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000358001300654000	654	target La_Mata - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000358001300655000	655	target La_Mata - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000358001300656000	656	target La_Mata - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000358001300657000	657	target La_Mata - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000358001300658000	658	target La_Mata - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00358	La_Mata stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3594MH000358001300659000	659	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Mata - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3594MH000358001300660000	660	target La_Mata - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3594MH000358001300661000	661	target La_Mata - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000358001300662000	662	target La_Mata - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000358001300663000	663	target La_Mata - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000358001300664000	664	target La_Mata - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000358001300665000	665	target La_Mata - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000358001300666000	666	target La_Mata - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000358001300667000	667	target La_Mata - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3594MH000358001300668000	668	target La_Mata - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00227	Focus Merges	3594MH000227001300669000	669	target La_Mata - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3594 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 661-668 - best focus image product
		3594MH000227001300670000	670	target La_Mata - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3594 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 661-668 - range map product
		3594MH000227001300671000	671	target La_Mata - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3594 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 651-658 - best focus image product
		3594MH000227001300672000	672	target La_Mata - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3594 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 651-658 - range map product
		3594MH000227001300673000	673	target La_Mata - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3594 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 641-648 - best focus image product
		3594MH000227001300674000	674	target La_Mata - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3594 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 641-648 - range map product
		3594MH000227001300675000	675	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3594 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 631-638 - best focus image product
		3594MH000227001300676000	676	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3594 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 631-638 - range map product
		3594MH000227001300677000	677	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3594 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 621-628 - best focus image product
		3594MH000227001300678000	678	target Tiger_Pond - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3594 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 621-628 - range map product

Sol 3596 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	18-Sep-22
camera position	48
total parent images	75
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	13
total parent images + focus merge products	84

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed targets Marshall_Falls and Corona_Falls and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Marshall_Falls before DRT ~24 cm standoff	3596MH001900001300679C00	679	autofocus sub-frame for target Marshall_Falls - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		3596MH00190001300680C00	680	target Marshall_Falls - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00212	Marshall_Falls before DRT ~5 cm standoff	3596MH00122001300681C00	681	autofocus sub-frame for target Marshall_Falls - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm
		3596MH00122001300682C00	682	target Marshall_Falls - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm
mN00190	Corona_Falls after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3596MH001900001300683C00	683	autofocus sub-frame for target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3596MH00190001300684C00	684	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00224	Corona_Falls after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3596MH00224001300685C00	685	autofocus sub-frame for target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3596MH00224001300686C00	686	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3596MH00224001300687C00	687	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00224001300688C00	688	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00224001300689C00	689	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00224001300690C00	690	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00224001300691C00	691	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00224001300692C00	692	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00224001300693C00	693	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00224001300694C00	694	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	Corona_Falls after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3596MH00224001300695C00	695	autofocus sub-frame for target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3596MH00224001300696C00	696	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3596MH00224001300697C00	697	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00224001300698C00	698	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00224001300699C00	699	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00224001300700C00	700	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00224001300701C00	701	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00224001300702C00	702	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00224001300703C00	703	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00224001300704C00	704	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00307	Corona_Falls after DRT ~2 cm standoff	3596MH00307001300705C00	705	autofocus sub-frame for target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3596MH00307001300706C00	706	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3596MH00307001300707C00	707	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00307001300708C00	708	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00307001300709C00	709	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00307001300710C00	710	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00307001300711C00	711	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00307001300712C00	712	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00307001300713C00	713	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00307001300714C00	714	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00706	Marshall_Falls after DRT ~24 cm standoff	3596MH007060001300715C00	715	autofocus sub-frame for target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		3596MH00706001300716C00	716	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		3596MH00706001300717C00	717	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00699	Marshall_Falls after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3596MH00699001300718C00	718	autofocus sub-frame for target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3596MH00699001300719C00	719	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3596MH00699001300720C00	720	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3596MH00699001300721C00	721	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00699001300722C00	722	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00699001300723C00	723	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00699001300724C00	724	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00699001300725C00	725	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00699001300726C00	726	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00699001300727C00	727	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00699	Marshall_Falls after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3596MH00699001300728C00	728	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00699001300729C00	729	autofocus sub-frame for target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3596MH00699001300730C00	730	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3596MH00699001300731C00	731	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3596MH00699001300732C00	732	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00699001300733C00	733	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00699001300734C00	734	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00699001300735C00	735	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00699001300736C00	736	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00699001300737C00	737	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00699001300738C00	738	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH00699001300739C00	739	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

mH000823	Marshall Falls after DRT -1 cm standoff	3596MH000823001300740C00	740	autofocus sub-frame for target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3596MH000823001300741C00	741	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3596MH000823001300742C00	742	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3596MH000823001300743C00	743	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH000823001300744C00	744	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH000823001300745C00	745	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH000823001300746C00	746	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH000823001300747C00	747	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH000823001300748C00	748	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3596MH000823001300749C00	749	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3596MH000823001300750C00	750	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00163	Focus Merges	3596MH001630001300751R00	751	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3596 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 743-750 - best focus image product
		3596MH001630001300752R00	752	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3596 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 743-750 - range map product
		3596MH001630001300753R00	753	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3596 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 732-739 - best focus image product
		3596MH001630001300754R00	754	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3596 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 732-739 - range map product
		3596MH001630001300755R00	755	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3596 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 721-728 - best focus image product
		3596MH001630001300756R00	756	target Marshall_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3596 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 721-728 - range map product
		3596MH001630001300757R00	757	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3596 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 707-714 - best focus image product
		3596MH001630001300758R00	758	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3596 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 707-714 - range map product
		3596MH001630001300759R00	759	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3596 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 697-704 - best focus image product
		3596MH001630001300760R00	760	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3596 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 697-704 - range map product
3596MH001630001300761R00	761	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3596 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 687-694 - best focus image product		
3596MH001630001300762R00	762	target Corona_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3596 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 687-694 - range map product		

updated: 19_October_2022

Sol 3599 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	21-Sep-22
camera position	41
total parent images	95
focus merges performed	9
total focus merge products	18
total parent images + focus merge products	112

MAHLI imaged the targets El_Triunfo, Nova_Cintra and Pirara. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00855	El_Triunfo ~24 cm standoff	3599MH00855001300763C00	763	autofocus sub-frame for target El_Triunfo - standoff near 24 cm
		3599MH00855001300764C00	764	target El_Triunfo - standoff near 24 cm
		3599MH00855001300765C00	765	target El_Triunfo - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00855001300766C00	766	target El_Triunfo - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00855001300767C00	767	target El_Triunfo - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00855001300768C00	768	target El_Triunfo - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00855001300769C00	769	target El_Triunfo - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00855001300770C00	770	target El_Triunfo - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00855001300771C00	771	target El_Triunfo - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00855001300772C00	772	target El_Triunfo - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00291	El_Triunfo stereo-1 ~9 cm standoff	3599MH00291001300773C00	773	autofocus sub-frame for target El_Triunfo - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm
		3599MH00291001300774C00	774	target El_Triunfo - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm
		3599MH00291001300775C00	775	target El_Triunfo - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00291001300776C00	776	target El_Triunfo - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00291001300777C00	777	target El_Triunfo - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00291001300778C00	778	target El_Triunfo - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00291001300779C00	779	target El_Triunfo - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00291001300780C00	780	target El_Triunfo - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00291001300781C00	781	target El_Triunfo - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00291001300782C00	782	target El_Triunfo - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00291	El_Triunfo stereo-2 ~9 cm standoff	3599MH00291001300783C00	783	autofocus sub-frame for target El_Triunfo - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm
		3599MH00291001300784C00	784	target El_Triunfo - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm
		3599MH00291001300785C00	785	target El_Triunfo - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00291001300786C00	786	target El_Triunfo - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00291001300787C00	787	target El_Triunfo - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00291001300788C00	788	target El_Triunfo - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00291001300789C00	789	target El_Triunfo - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00291001300790C00	790	target El_Triunfo - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00291001300791C00	791	target El_Triunfo - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00291001300792C00	792	target El_Triunfo - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Nova_Cintra ~25 cm standoff	3599MH00190001300793C00	793	autofocus sub-frame for target Nova_Cintra - standoff near 25 cm
		3599MH00190001300794C00	794	target Nova_Cintra - standoff near 25 cm
mN00173	Nova_Cintra stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3599MH00173001300795C00	795	autofocus sub-frame for target Nova_Cintra - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3599MH00173001300796C00	796	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3599MH00173001300797C00	797	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00173001300798C00	798	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00173001300799C00	799	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00173001300800C00	800	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00173001300801C00	801	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00173001300802C00	802	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00173001300803C00	803	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00173001300804C00	804	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Nova_Cintra stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3599MH00173001300805C00	805	autofocus sub-frame for target Nova_Cintra - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3599MH00173001300806C00	806	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3599MH00173001300807C00	807	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00173001300808C00	808	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00173001300809C00	809	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00173001300810C00	810	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00173001300811C00	811	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00173001300812C00	812	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00173001300813C00	813	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00173001300814C00	814	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00317	Nova_Cintra ~2 cm standoff	3599MH00317001300815C00	815	autofocus sub-frame for target Nova_Cintra - standoff near 2 cm
		3599MH00317001300816C00	816	target Nova_Cintra - standoff near 2 cm
		3599MH00317001300817C00	817	target Nova_Cintra - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00317001300818C00	818	target Nova_Cintra - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00317001300819C00	819	target Nova_Cintra - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00317001300820C00	820	target Nova_Cintra - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00317001300821C00	821	target Nova_Cintra - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00317001300822C00	822	target Nova_Cintra - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Pirara ~26 cm standoff	3599MH00190001300823C00	823	target Nova_Cintra - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH00317001300824C00	824	target Nova_Cintra - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Pirara ~26 cm standoff	3599MH00190001300825C00	825	autofocus sub-frame for target Pirara - standoff near 26 cm
		3599MH00190001300826C00	826	target Pirara - standoff near 26 cm

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mH00299	Pirara stereo-1 ~6 cm standoff	3599MH0029900130082700	827	autofocus sub-frame for target Pirara - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm
		3599MH0029900130082800	828	target Pirara - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm
		3599MH0029900130082900	829	target Pirara - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0029900130083000	830	target Pirara - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0029900130083100	831	target Pirara - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0029900130083200	832	target Pirara - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0029900130083300	833	target Pirara - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0029900130083400	834	target Pirara - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0029900130083500	835	target Pirara - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0029900130083600	836	target Pirara - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mH00299	Pirara stereo-2 ~6 cm standoff	3599MH0029900130083700	837	autofocus sub-frame for target Pirara - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm
		3599MH0029900130083800	838	target Pirara - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm
		3599MH0029900130083900	839	target Pirara - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0029900130084000	840	target Pirara - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0029900130084100	841	target Pirara - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0029900130084200	842	target Pirara - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0029900130084300	843	target Pirara - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0029900130084400	844	target Pirara - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0029900130084500	845	target Pirara - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0029900130084600	846	target Pirara - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mH00337	Pirara ~3 cm standoff	3599MH0033700130084700	847	autofocus sub-frame for target Pirara - standoff near 3 cm
		3599MH0033700130084800	848	target Pirara - standoff near 3 cm
		3599MH0033700130084900	849	target Pirara - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0033700130085000	850	target Pirara - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0033700130085100	851	target Pirara - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0033700130085200	852	target Pirara - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0033700130085300	853	target Pirara - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0033700130085400	854	target Pirara - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0033700130085500	855	target Pirara - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3599MH0033700130085600	856	target Pirara - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mH00536	Focus Merges	3599MH0053600130085700	857	target Pirara - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3599 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 849-856 - best focus image product
		3599MH0053600130085800	858	target Pirara - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3599 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 849-856 - range map product
		3599MH0053600130085900	859	target Pirara - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3599 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 839-846 - best focus image product
		3599MH0053600130086000	860	target Pirara - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3599 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 839-846 - range map product
		3599MH0053600130086100	861	target Pirara - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3599 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 829-836 - best focus image product
		3599MH0053600130086200	862	target Pirara - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3599 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 829-836 - range map product
		3599MH0053600130086300	863	target Nova_Cintra - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3599 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 817-824 - best focus image product
		3599MH0053600130086400	864	target Nova_Cintra - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3599 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 817-824 - range map product
		3599MH0053600130086500	865	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3599 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 807-814 - best focus image product
		3599MH0053600130086600	866	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3599 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 807-814 - range map product
		3599MH0053600130086700	867	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3599 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 797-804 - best focus image product
		3599MH0053600130086800	868	target Nova_Cintra - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3599 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 797-804 - range map product
		3599MH0053600130086900	869	target El_Triunfo - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3599 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 785-792 - best focus image product
		3599MH0053600130087000	870	target El_Triunfo - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3599 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 785-792 - range map product
		3599MH0053600130087100	871	target El_Triunfo - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3599 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 775-782 - best focus image product
		3599MH0053600130087200	872	target El_Triunfo - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3599 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 775-782 - range map product
		3599MH0053600130087300	873	target El_Triunfo - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3599 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 765-772 - best focus image product
		3599MH0053600130087400	874	target El_Triunfo - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3599 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 765-772 - range map product

updated: 24_October_2022

Sol 3601 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)		23-Sep-21
		Camera position	4	Image ID:
		total parent images	33	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	3	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	39	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT (brushed target) Cauarane and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Cauarane after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3601MH00190001300875C0	875	autofocus sub-frame for target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3601MH00190001300876C0	876	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Cauarane after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3601MH00182001300877C0	877	autofocus sub-frame for target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3601MH00182001300878C0	878	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3601MH00182001300879C0	879	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH00182001300880C0	880	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH00182001300881C0	881	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH00182001300882C0	882	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH00182001300883C0	883	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH00182001300884C0	884	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH00182001300885C0	885	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH00182001300886C0	886	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Cauarane after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3601MH00182001300897C0	887	autofocus sub-frame for target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3601MH00182001300898C0	888	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3601MH00182001300899C0	889	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH00182001300900C0	890	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH00182001300901C0	891	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH00182001300902C0	892	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH00182001300903C0	893	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH00182001300904C0	894	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH00182001300905C0	895	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH00182001300906C0	896	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00838	Cauarane after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3601MH000838001300977C0	897	autofocus sub-frame for target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3601MH000838001300988C0	898	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3601MH000838001300999C0	899	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH000838001300990C0	900	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH000838001300991C0	901	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH000838001300992C0	902	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH000838001300993C0	903	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH000838001300994C0	904	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH000838001300995C0	905	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3601MH000838001300996C0	906	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00289	Focus Merges	3601MH0019300130090700	907	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3601 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 899-906 - best focus image product
		3601MH0019300130090800	908	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3601 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 899-906 - range map product
		3601MH0019300130090900	909	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3601 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 899-896 - best focus image product
		3601MH0019300130091000	910	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3601 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 899-896 - range map product
		3601MH0019300130091100	911	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3601 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 879-886 - best focus image product
		3601MH0019300130091200	912	target Cauarane - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3601 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 879-886 - range map product

Sol 3603 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	25-Sep-22
camera position	65
total parent images	65
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	78

MAHLI imaged the targets Tapirapeco, Lagoa_do_Velame and Lagoa_do_Macaco. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00290	Tapirapeco ~24 cm standoff	3603MH0019000130091300	913	autofocus sub-frame for target Tapirapeco - standoff near 24 cm
		3603MH0019000130091400	914	target Tapirapeco - standoff near 24 cm
mN00224	Tapirapeco stereo-1 ~35 mm standoff	3603MH002400130091500	915	autofocus sub-frame for target Tapirapeco - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3603MH002400130091600	916	target Tapirapeco - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3603MH002400130091700	917	target Tapirapeco - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH002400130091800	918	target Tapirapeco - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH002400130091900	919	target Tapirapeco - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH002400130092000	920	target Tapirapeco - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH002400130092100	921	target Tapirapeco - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH002400130092200	922	target Tapirapeco - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH002400130092300	923	target Tapirapeco - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH002400130092400	924	target Tapirapeco - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	Tapirapeco stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff	3603MH002400130092500	925	autofocus sub-frame for target Tapirapeco - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3603MH002400130092600	926	target Tapirapeco - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3603MH002400130092700	927	target Tapirapeco - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH002400130092800	928	target Tapirapeco - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH002400130092900	929	target Tapirapeco - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH002400130093000	930	target Tapirapeco - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH002400130093100	931	target Tapirapeco - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH002400130093200	932	target Tapirapeco - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH002400130093300	933	target Tapirapeco - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH002400130093400	934	target Tapirapeco - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00290	Lagoa_do_Velame ~24 cm standoff	3603MH0016800130093500	935	autofocus sub-frame for target Lagoa_do_Velame - standoff near 24 cm
		3603MH0016800130093600	936	target Lagoa_do_Velame - standoff near 24 cm
mN00268	Lagoa_do_Velame stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3603MH0016800130093700	937	autofocus sub-frame for target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3603MH0016800130093800	938	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3603MH0016800130093900	939	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130094000	940	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130094100	941	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130094200	942	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130094300	943	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130094400	944	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130094500	945	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130094600	946	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00268	Lagoa_do_Velame stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3603MH0016800130094700	947	autofocus sub-frame for target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3603MH0016800130094800	948	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3603MH0016800130094900	949	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130095000	950	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130095100	951	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130095200	952	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130095300	953	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130095400	954	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130095500	955	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130095600	956	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00290	Lagoa_do_Macaco ~24 cm standoff	3603MH0019000130095700	957	autofocus sub-frame for target Lagoa_do_Macaco - standoff near 24 cm
		3603MH0019000130095800	958	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - standoff near 24 cm
mN00268	Lagoa_do_Macaco stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3603MH0016800130095900	959	autofocus sub-frame for target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3603MH0016800130096000	960	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3603MH0016800130096100	961	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130096200	962	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130096300	963	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130096400	964	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130096500	965	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130096600	966	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130096700	967	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130096800	968	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00268	Lagoa_do_Macaco stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3603MH0016800130096900	969	autofocus sub-frame for target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3603MH0016800130097000	970	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3603MH0016800130097100	971	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130097200	972	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130097300	973	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130097400	974	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130097500	975	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130097600	976	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130097700	977	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3603MH0016800130097800	978	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

Continued on Next Page...

m000163	Focus Merge	3603MH00163000130097900	979	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3603 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 971-978 - best focus image product
		3603MH001630001300980500	980	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3603 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 971-978 - range map product
		3603MH001630001300981800	981	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3603 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 961-968 - best focus image product
		3603MH001630001300982500	982	target Lagoa_do_Macaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3603 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 961-968 - range map product
		3603MH001630001300983800	983	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3603 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 949-956 - best focus image product
		3603MH001630001300984500	984	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3603 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 949-956 - range map product
		3603MH001630001300985800	985	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3603 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 939-946 - best focus image product
		3603MH001630001300986500	986	target Lagoa_do_Velame - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3603 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 939-946 - range map product
		3603MH001630001300987800	987	target Tapirapeco - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3603 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 927-934 - best focus image product
		3603MH001630001300988500	988	target Tapirapeco - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3603 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 927-934 - range map product
		3603MH001630001300989800	989	target Tapirapeco - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3603 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 917-924 - best focus image product
		3603MH001630001300990500	990	target Tapirapeco - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3603 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 917-924 - range map product

mNH00163	Focus Merge	3605MH001630001301051800	1051	target Tapirapeco - mosaic position 6 of 6 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3605 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1043-1050 - best focus image product
		3605MH001630001301052500	1052	target Tapirapeco - mosaic position 6 of 6 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3605 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1043-1050 - range map product
		3605MH001630001301053800	1053	target Tapirapeco - mosaic position 5 of 6 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3605 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1033-1040 - best focus image product
		3605MH001630001301054500	1054	target Tapirapeco - mosaic position 5 of 6 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3605 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1033-1040 - range map product
		3605MH001630001301055800	1055	target Tapirapeco - mosaic position 4 of 6 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3605 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1023-1030 - best focus image product
		3605MH001630001301056500	1056	target Tapirapeco - mosaic position 4 of 6 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3605 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1023-1030 - range map product
		3605MH001630001301057800	1057	target Tapirapeco - mosaic position 3 of 6 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3605 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1013-1020 - best focus image product
		3605MH001630001301058500	1058	target Tapirapeco - mosaic position 3 of 6 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3605 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1013-1020 - range map product
		3605MH001630001301059800	1059	target Tapirapeco - mosaic position 2 of 6 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3605 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1003-1010 - best focus image product
		3605MH001630001301060500	1060	target Tapirapeco - mosaic position 2 of 6 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3605 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1003-1010 - range map product
		3605MH001630001301061800	1061	target Tapirapeco - mosaic position 1 of 6 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3605 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 993-1000 - best focus image product
		3605MH001630001301062500	1062	target Tapirapeco - mosaic position 1 of 6 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3605 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 993-1000 - range map product

updated: 24_October_2022

Sol 3607 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	28-Sep-22
camera positions	6
total parent images	12
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	12

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the targets El_Pao_De_La_Fortuna and Espirito_Santo.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00290	El_Pao_De_La_Fortuna ~24 cm standoff	3607MH00190001301063C00	1063	autofocus sub-frame for target El_Pao_De_La_Fortuna - standoff near 24 cm
		3607MH00190001301064C00	1064	target El_Pao_De_La_Fortuna - standoff near 24 cm
mN00248	El_Pao_De_La_Fortuna stereo-1 ~9 cm standoff	3607MH00148001301065C00	1065	autofocus sub-frame for target El_Pao_De_La_Fortuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm
		3607MH00148001301066C00	1066	target El_Pao_De_La_Fortuna - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm
mN00248	El_Pao_De_La_Fortuna stereo-2 ~9 cm standoff	3607MH00148001301067C00	1067	autofocus sub-frame for target El_Pao_De_La_Fortuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm
		3607MH00148001301068C00	1068	target El_Pao_De_La_Fortuna - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm
mN00290	Espirito_Santo ~24 cm standoff	3607MH00190001301069C00	1069	autofocus sub-frame for target Espirito_Santo - standoff near 24 cm
		3607MH00190001301070C00	1070	target Espirito_Santo - standoff near 24 cm
mN00248	Espirito_Santo stereo-1 ~9 cm standoff	3607MH00148001301071C00	1071	autofocus sub-frame for target Espirito_Santo - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm
		3607MH00148001301072C00	1072	target Espirito_Santo - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm
mN00248	Espirito_Santo stereo-2 ~9 cm standoff	3607MH00148001301073C00	1073	autofocus sub-frame for target Espirito_Santo - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm
		3607MH00148001301074C00	1074	target Espirito_Santo - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm

updated: 08_June_2023

Sol 3609 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	1-Oct-22
camera position	6
total parent images	48
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	56

MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Canaima before and after DRT, and after a drill bit preload test, then the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Canaima before DRT ~25 cm standoff	3609MH0001900013010750C0	1075	autofocus sub-frame for intended Canaima drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3609MH0001900013010760C0	1076	intended Canaima drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00122	Canaima before DRT APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	3609MH0001220013010770C0	1077	autofocus sub-frame for intended Canaima drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3609MH0001220013010780C0	1078	intended Canaima drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00190	Canaima after DRT ~24 cm standoff	3609MH0001900013010790C0	1079	autofocus sub-frame for intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 24 cm
		3609MH0001900013010800C0	1080	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 24 cm
mN00173	Canaima after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3609MH0001730013010810C0	1081	autofocus sub-frame for intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3609MH0001730013010820C0	1082	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3609MH0001730013010830C0	1083	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013010840C0	1084	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013010850C0	1085	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013010860C0	1086	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013010870C0	1087	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013010880C0	1088	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013010890C0	1089	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013010900C0	1090	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Canaima after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3609MH0001730013010910C0	1091	autofocus sub-frame for intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3609MH0001730013010920C0	1092	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3609MH0001730013010930C0	1093	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013010940C0	1094	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013010950C0	1095	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013010960C0	1096	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013010970C0	1097	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013010980C0	1098	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013010990C0	1099	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013011000C0	1100	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00649	Canaima after DRT APXS spot 2 ~1 cm standoff	3609MH0006490013011010C0	1101	autofocus sub-frame for intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3609MH0006490013011020C0	1102	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3609MH0006490013011030C0	1103	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0006490013011040C0	1104	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0006490013011050C0	1105	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0006490013011060C0	1106	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0006490013011070C0	1107	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0006490013011080C0	1108	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0006490013011090C0	1109	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0006490013011100C0	1110	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Canaima after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3609MH0001730013011110C0	1111	autofocus sub-frame for intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3609MH0001730013011120C0	1112	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3609MH0001730013011130C0	1113	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013011140C0	1114	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013011150C0	1115	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013011160C0	1116	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013011170C0	1117	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013011180C0	1118	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013011190C0	1119	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3609MH0001730013011200C0	1120	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00465	Canaima after DRT after drill bit preload test ~35 cm standoff	3609MH0004650013011210C0	1121	autofocus sub-frame for intended Canaima drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 3609 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
		3609MH0004650013011220C0	1122	intended Canaima drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 3609 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
mN00153	Focus Merges	3609MH000153001301123000	1123	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3609 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1113-1120 - best focus image product
		3609MH000153001301124000	1124	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3609 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1113-1120 - range map product
		3609MH000153001301125000	1125	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3609 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1103-1110 - best focus image product
		3609MH000153001301126000	1126	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3609 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1103-1110 - range map product
		3609MH000153001301127000	1127	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3609 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1093-1100 - best focus image product
		3609MH000153001301128000	1128	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3609 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1093-1100 - range map product
		3609MH000153001301129000	1129	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3609 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1083-1090 - best focus image product
		3609MH000153001301130000	1130	intended Canaima drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3609 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1083-1090 - range map product

updated: 24_October_2022

Sol 3612 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	4-Oct-22			
camera positions	3	Image ID:		
total parent images	2	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
focus merges performed	0	CCPFD:		
total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
total parent images + focus merge products	2			
summary of MAHLI activities: Drill preparation activities at the planned Canaima sample extraction site. MAHLI imaged the intended site for the Canaima sample discard pile.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CCPFD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Intended Canaima Drill Sample Discard Site Before Discard ~25 cm standoff	3612MH00190001301131C00	1131	autofocus sub-frame for intended Canaima drill sample discard site - before drill attempt and before discard - standoff near 25 cm
		3612MH00190001301132C00	1132	intended Canaima drill sample discard site - before drill attempt and before discard - standoff near 25 cm

updated: 24_October_2022

Sol 3624 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)		in-image/stack	
camera positions:	2	image ID:	
total parent images:	15	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received	
focus merges performed:	1	CDPID:	
total focus merge products:	2	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	
total parent images + focus merge products:	16		

summary of MAHLI activities			
MAHLI imaged the Canaima drill hole and cuttings. The focus stack images were also merged.			
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID
Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)			
mN00187	Canaima drill hole drilled on Sol 3612 ~24 cm standoff	3624MH0019700013011230C0	1133
		3624MH001970011301134C0	1134
mN00774	Canaima drill hole drilled on Sol 3612 ~9 cm standoff	3624MH00077400013011235C0	1125
		3624MH0007740011301136C0	1136
mN00152	Canaima drill cuttings ~35 mm standoff	3624MH001520001301137C0	1137
		3624MH001520011301138C0	1138
		3624MH001520021301139C0	1139
		3624MH001520031301140C0	1140
		3624MH001520041301141C0	1141
		3624MH001520051301142C0	1142
		3624MH001520061301143C0	1143
		3624MH001520071301144C0	1144
		3624MH001520081301145C0	1145
		3624MH001520091301146C0	1146
mN00258	Focus Merge	3624MH002580001301147R0	1147
		3624MH00258001301148S0	1148

updated: 24_October_2022

Sol 3626 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	18-Oct-22
camera positions	4
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the target Bacabal and the Canaima drill cuttings. The focus stack images were also merged.
Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Bacabal ~24 cm standoff	3626MH00190001301149000	1149	autofocus sub-frame for target Bacabal - standoff near 24 cm
		3626MH00190001301150000	1150	target Bacabal - standoff near 24 cm
mN00173	Bacabal stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	3626MH00173001301151000	1151	autofocus sub-frame for target Bacabal - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3626MH00173001301152000	1152	target Bacabal - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3626MH00173001301153000	1153	target Bacabal - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3626MH00173001301154000	1154	target Bacabal - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3626MH00173001301155000	1155	target Bacabal - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3626MH00173001301156000	1156	target Bacabal - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3626MH00173001301157000	1157	target Bacabal - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3626MH00173001301158000	1158	target Bacabal - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3626MH00173001301159000	1159	target Bacabal - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3626MH00173001301160000	1160	target Bacabal - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Bacabal stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3626MH00173001301161000	1161	autofocus sub-frame for target Bacabal - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3626MH00173001301162000	1162	target Bacabal - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3626MH00173001301163000	1163	target Bacabal - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3626MH00173001301164000	1164	target Bacabal - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3626MH00173001301165000	1165	target Bacabal - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3626MH00173001301166000	1166	target Bacabal - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3626MH00173001301167000	1167	target Bacabal - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3626MH00173001301168000	1168	target Bacabal - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00122	Canaima drill cuttings ~55 mm standoff	3626MH00122001301171000	1171	autofocus sub-frame for Canaima drill cuttings - standoff near 55 mm
		3626MH00122001301172000	1172	Canaima drill cuttings - standoff near 55 mm
mN00265	Focus Merges	3626MH00265000130117300	1173	target Bacabal - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3626 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1163-1170 - best focus image product
		3626MH00265000130117400	1174	target Bacabal - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3626 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1163-1170 - range map product
		3626MH00265000130117500	1175	target Bacabal - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3626 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1153-1160 - best focus image product
		3626MH00265000130117600	1176	target Bacabal - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3626 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1153-1160 - range map product

updated: 28_November_2022

Sol 3628 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	01-Nov-2022/01-Nov-2022
camera positions	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the target Pacu and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Pacu ~25 cm standoff	3628MH00190001301177C0D	1177	autofocus sub-frame for target Pacu - standoff near 25 cm
		3628MH00190001301178C0D	1178	target Pacu - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Pacu stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3628MH00168001301179C0D	1179	autofocus sub-frame for target Pacu - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3628MH00168001301180C0D	1180	target Pacu - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3628MH00168001301181C0D	1181	target Pacu - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00168001301182C0D	1182	target Pacu - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00168001301183C0D	1183	target Pacu - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00168001301184C0D	1184	target Pacu - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00168001301185C0D	1185	target Pacu - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00168001301186C0D	1186	target Pacu - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00168001301187C0D	1187	target Pacu - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00168001301188C0D	1188	target Pacu - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Pacu stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3628MH00168001301189C0D	1189	autofocus sub-frame for target Pacu - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3628MH00168001301190C0D	1190	target Pacu - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3628MH00168001301191C0D	1191	target Pacu - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00168001301192C0D	1192	target Pacu - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00168001301193C0D	1193	target Pacu - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00168001301194C0D	1194	target Pacu - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00168001301195C0D	1195	target Pacu - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00168001301196C0D	1196	target Pacu - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00168001301197C0D	1197	target Pacu - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00168001301198C0D	1198	target Pacu - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00386	Pacu ~1 cm standoff	3628MH00386001301199C0D	1199	autofocus sub-frame for target Pacu - standoff near 1 cm
		3628MH00386001301200C0D	1200	target Pacu - standoff near 1 cm
		3628MH00386001301201C0D	1201	target Pacu - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00386001301202C0D	1202	target Pacu - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00386001301203C0D	1203	target Pacu - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00386001301204C0D	1204	target Pacu - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00386001301205C0D	1205	target Pacu - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00386001301206C0D	1206	target Pacu - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00386001301207C0D	1207	target Pacu - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3628MH00386001301208C0D	1208	target Pacu - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	3628MH0019300130120900D	1209	target Pacu - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3628 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1201-1208 - best focus image product
		3628MH0019300130121050D	1210	target Pacu - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3628 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1201-1208 - range map product
		3628MH0019300130121190D	1211	target Pacu - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3628 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1191-1198 - best focus image product
		3628MH0019300130121250D	1212	target Pacu - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3628 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1191-1198 - range map product
		3628MH0019300130121390D	1213	target Pacu - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3628 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1181-1188 - best focus image product
3628MH0019300130121450D	1214	target Pacu - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3628 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1181-1188 - range map product		

updated: 28_November_2022

Sol 3630 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	23-Oct-22
camera position	4
total parent images	44
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	44

MAHLI images that correspond to CPOIDs 3314 through 4854 (data from Sols 3482-3560) were deleted from the MAHLI OEA non-volatile memory storage. MAHLI imaged the targets Vista_Alegre and Santa_Silvia.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPOID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Vista_Alegre ~25 cm standoff	3630MH0019000130121500	1215	autofocus sub-frame for target Vista_Alegre - standoff near 25 cm
		3630MH0019000130121600	1216	target Vista_Alegre - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Vista_Alegre stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3630MH0018200130121700	1217	autofocus sub-frame for target Vista_Alegre - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3630MH0018200130121800	1218	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3630MH0018200130121900	1219	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130122000	1220	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130122100	1221	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130122200	1222	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130122300	1223	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130122400	1224	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130122500	1225	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130122600	1226	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Vista_Alegre stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3630MH0018200130122700	1227	autofocus sub-frame for target Vista_Alegre - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3630MH0018200130122800	1228	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3630MH0018200130122900	1229	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130123000	1230	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130123100	1231	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130123200	1232	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130123300	1233	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130123400	1234	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130123500	1235	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130123600	1236	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Santa_Silvia ~25 cm standoff	3630MH0019000130123700	1237	autofocus sub-frame for target Santa_Silvia - standoff near 25 cm
		3630MH0019000130123800	1238	target Santa_Silvia - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Santa_Silvia stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3630MH0018200130123900	1239	autofocus sub-frame for target Santa_Silvia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3630MH0018200130124000	1240	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3630MH0018200130124100	1241	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130124200	1242	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130124300	1243	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130124400	1244	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130124500	1245	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130124600	1246	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130124700	1247	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130124800	1248	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Santa_Silvia stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3630MH0018200130124900	1249	autofocus sub-frame for target Santa_Silvia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3630MH0018200130125000	1250	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3630MH0018200130125100	1251	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130125200	1252	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130125300	1253	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130125400	1254	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130125500	1255	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130125600	1256	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130125700	1257	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3630MH0018200130125800	1258	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 25_May_2023

Sol 3631 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	25-Oct-22
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	4
total focus merge products:	8
total parent images + focus merge products:	8

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3630 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N0013	Focus Merges	3631MH001530001301239900	1259	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3630 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1251-1258 - best focus image product
		3631MH001530001301260500	1260	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3630 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1251-1258 - range map product
		3631MH001530001301261800	1261	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3630 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1241-1248 - best focus image product
		3631MH001530001301262500	1262	target Santa_Silvia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3630 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1241-1248 - range map product
		3631MH001530001301263800	1263	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3630 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1229-1236 - best focus image product
		3631MH001530001301264500	1264	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3630 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1229-1236 - range map product
		3631MH001530001301265800	1265	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3630 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1219-1226 - best focus image product
		3631MH001530001301266500	1266	target Vista_Alegre - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3630 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1219-1226 - range map product

updated: 01_December_2022

Sol 3633 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26-Oct-22
camera position	4
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the target Balata and the focus stack images were merged. The REMS UV sensor was imaged as well.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Balata ~25 cm standoff	3633MH00190001301267C0D	1267	autofocus sub-frame for target Balata - standoff near 25 cm
		3633MH00190001301268C0D	1268	target Balata - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Balata stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3633MH00168001301269C0D	1269	autofocus sub-frame for target Balata - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3633MH00168001301270C0D	1270	target Balata - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3633MH00168001301271C0D	1271	target Balata - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3633MH00168001301272C0D	1272	target Balata - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3633MH00168001301273C0D	1273	target Balata - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3633MH00168001301274C0D	1274	target Balata - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3633MH00168001301275C0D	1275	target Balata - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3633MH00168001301276C0D	1276	target Balata - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3633MH00168001301277C0D	1277	target Balata - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3633MH00168001301278C0D	1278	target Balata - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Balata stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3633MH00168001301279C0D	1279	autofocus sub-frame for target Balata - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3633MH00168001301280C0D	1280	target Balata - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3633MH00168001301281C0D	1281	target Balata - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3633MH00168001301282C0D	1282	target Balata - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3633MH00168001301283C0D	1283	target Balata - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3633MH00168001301284C0D	1284	target Balata - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3633MH00168001301285C0D	1285	target Balata - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3633MH00168001301286C0D	1286	target Balata - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3633MH00168001301287C0D	1287	target Balata - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3633MH00168001301288C0D	1288	target Balata - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00205	Focus Merges	3633MH00205001301289N0D	1289	target Balata - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3633 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1281-1288 - best focus image product
		3633MH00205001301290S0D	1290	target Balata - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3633 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1281-1288 - range map product
		3633MH00205001301291N0D	1291	target Balata - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3633 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1271-1278 - best focus image product
		3633MH00205001301292S0D	1292	target Balata - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3633 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1271-1278 - range map product
mN00095	REMS UV sensor ~15 cm standoff	3633MH00095001301293C0D	1293	autofocus sub-frame for REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
		3633MH00095001301294C0D	1294	REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation

updated: 28_November_2022

Sol 3635 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	28-Oct-22
camera positions	6
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	41

MAHLI imaged the targets Mau and Univini and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Mau ~25 cm standoff	3635MH00190001301295CD	1295	autofocus sub-frame for target Mau - standoff near 25 cm
		3635MH00190001301296CD	1296	target Mau - standoff near 25 cm
mN00299	Mau stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3635MH00299001301297CD	1297	autofocus sub-frame for target Mau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3635MH00299001301298CD	1298	target Mau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3635MH00299001301299CD	1299	target Mau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00299001301300CD	1300	target Mau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00299001301301CD	1301	target Mau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00299001301302CD	1302	target Mau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00299001301303CD	1303	target Mau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00299001301304CD	1304	target Mau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00299001301305CD	1305	target Mau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00299001301306CD	1306	target Mau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00299	Mau stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3635MH00299001301307CD	1307	autofocus sub-frame for target Mau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3635MH00299001301308CD	1308	target Mau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3635MH00299001301309CD	1309	target Mau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00299001301310CD	1310	target Mau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00299001301311CD	1311	target Mau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00299001301312CD	1312	target Mau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00299001301313CD	1313	target Mau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00299001301314CD	1314	target Mau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00299001301315CD	1315	target Mau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00299001301316CD	1316	target Mau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00814	Univini ~14 cm standoff	3635MH00814001301317CD	1317	autofocus sub-frame for target Univini - standoff near 14 cm
		3635MH00814001301318CD	1318	target Univini - standoff near 14 cm
		3635MH00814001301319CD	1319	target Univini - standoff near 14 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00699	Univini ~45 mm standoff	3635MH00699001301320CD	1320	autofocus sub-frame for target Univini - standoff near 45 mm
		3635MH00699001301321CD	1321	target Univini - standoff near 45 mm
		3635MH00699001301322CD	1322	target Univini - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3635MH00699001301323CD	1323	target Univini - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00699001301324CD	1324	target Univini - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00699001301325CD	1325	target Univini - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00699001301326CD	1326	target Univini - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00699001301327CD	1327	target Univini - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00699001301328CD	1328	target Univini - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3635MH00699001301329CD	1329	target Univini - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	3635MH00193001301330CD	1331	target Univini - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3635 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1323-1330 - best focus image product
		3635MH00193001301332CD	1332	target Univini - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3635 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1323-1330 - range map product
		3635MH00193001301333CD	1333	target Mau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3635 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1309-1316 - best focus image product
		3635MH00193001301334CD	1334	target Mau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3635 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1309-1316 - range map product
		3635MH00193001301335CD	1335	target Mau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3635 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1299-1306 - best focus image product
3635MH00193001301336CD	1336	target Mau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3635 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1299-1306 - range map product		

Sol 3637 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	30-Oct-22
camera position	2
total parent images	57
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	67

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Catrimani and the target Marari. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00190	Catrimani after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3637MH0001900013013370C0	1337	autofocus sub-frame for target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3637MH0001900013013380C0	1338	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mNI00173	Catrimani after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3637MH0001730013013390C0	1339	autofocus sub-frame for target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3637MH0001730013013400C0	1340	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3637MH0001730013013410C0	1341	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0001730013013420C0	1342	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0001730013013430C0	1343	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0001730013013440C0	1344	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0001730013013450C0	1345	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0001730013013460C0	1346	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0001730013013470C0	1347	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0001730013013480C0	1348	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00173	Catrimani after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3637MH0001730013013490C0	1349	autofocus sub-frame for target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3637MH0001730013013500C0	1350	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3637MH0001730013013510C0	1351	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0001730013013520C0	1352	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0001730013013530C0	1353	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0001730013013540C0	1354	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0001730013013550C0	1355	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0001730013013560C0	1356	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0001730013013570C0	1357	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0001730013013580C0	1358	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00176	Catrimani after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3637MH0007600013013590C0	1359	autofocus sub-frame for target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3637MH0007600013013600C0	1360	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3637MH0007600013013610C0	1361	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0007600013013620C0	1362	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0007600013013630C0	1363	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0007600013013640C0	1364	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0007600013013650C0	1365	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0007600013013660C0	1366	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0007600013013670C0	1367	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH0007600013013680C0	1368	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00706	Marari ~23 cm standoff	3637MH00070600013013690C0	1369	autofocus sub-frame for target Marari - standoff near 23 cm
		3637MH00070600013013700C0	1370	target Marari - standoff near 23 cm
		3637MH00070600013013710C0	1371	target Marari - standoff near 23 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00721	Marari stereo-1 ~3 cm standoff	3637MH00072100013013720C0	1372	autofocus sub-frame for target Marari - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm
		3637MH00072100013013730C0	1373	target Marari - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm
		3637MH00072100013013740C0	1374	target Marari - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3637MH00072100013013750C0	1375	target Marari - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH00072100013013760C0	1376	target Marari - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH00072100013013770C0	1377	target Marari - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH00072100013013780C0	1378	target Marari - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH00072100013013790C0	1379	target Marari - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH00072100013013800C0	1380	target Marari - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH00072100013013810C0	1381	target Marari - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3637MH00072100013013820C0	1382	target Marari - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00721	Marari stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff	3637MH00072100013013830C0	1383	autofocus sub-frame for target Marari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3637MH00072100013013840C0	1384	target Marari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3637MH00072100013013850C0	1385	target Marari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3637MH00072100013013860C0	1386	target Marari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH00072100013013870C0	1387	target Marari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH00072100013013880C0	1388	target Marari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH00072100013013890C0	1389	target Marari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH00072100013013900C0	1390	target Marari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH00072100013013910C0	1391	target Marari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3637MH00072100013013920C0	1392	target Marari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3637MH00072100013013930C0	1393	target Marari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00227	Focus Merges	3637MH000227000130139400C0	1394	target Marari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3637 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1386-1393 - best focus image product
		3637MH0002270001301395500C0	1395	target Marari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3637 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1386-1393 - range map product
		3637MH0002270001301396000C0	1396	target Marari - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3637 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1375-1382 - best focus image product
		3637MH0002270001301397500C0	1397	target Marari - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3637 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1375-1382 - range map product
		3637MH0002270001301398000C0	1398	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3637 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1361-1368 - best focus image product
		3637MH0002270001301399500C0	1399	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3637 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1361-1368 - range map product
		3637MH0002270001301400000C0	1400	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3637 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1351-1358 - best focus image product
		3637MH0002270001301401500C0	1401	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3637 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1351-1358 - range map product
		3637MH0002270001301402000C0	1402	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3637 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1341-1348 - best focus image product
		3637MH0002270001301402500C0	1403	target Catrimani - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3637 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1341-1348 - range map product

updated: 25_May_2023

Sol 3642 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	4 Nov 22
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	10

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3641 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N0389	Focus Merges	3642MH00369000130150800	1550	target Iracema - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1542-1549 - best focus image product
		3642MH00369000130151500	1551	target Iracema - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1542-1549 - range map product
		3642MH00369000130152000	1552	target Iracema - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1532-1539 - best focus image product
		3642MH00369000130153500	1553	target Iracema - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1532-1539 - range map product
		3642MH00369000130154000	1554	target Iracema - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1522-1529 - best focus image product
		3642MH00369000130155500	1555	target Iracema - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1522-1529 - range map product
		3642MH00369000130156000	1556	target Iracema - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1512-1519 - best focus image product
		3642MH00369000130157500	1557	target Iracema - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1512-1519 - range map product
		3642MH00369000130158000	1558	target Mamupi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1502-1509 - best focus image product
		3642MH00369000130159500	1559	target Mamupi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1502-1509 - range map product
		3642MH00369000130156000	1560	target Mamupi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1492-1499 - best focus image product
		3642MH003690001301561500	1561	target Mamupi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1492-1499 - range map product
		3642MH003690001301562000	1562	target Mamupi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1482-1489 - best focus image product
		3642MH003690001301563500	1563	target Mamupi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1482-1489 - range map product
		3642MH003690001301564000	1564	target Mel - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1470-1477 - best focus image product
		3642MH003690001301565500	1565	target Mel - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1470-1477 - range map product
		3642MH003690001301566000	1566	target Mel - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1460-1467 - best focus image product
		3642MH003690001301567500	1567	target Mel - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1460-1467 - range map product
		3642MH003690001301568000	1568	target Mel - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1450-1457 - best focus image product
		3642MH003690001301569500	1569	target Mel - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3641 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1450-1457 - range map product

7 Definitions, conventions, and acronyms

7.1 Definitions and conventions

absolute focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a commanded (manual) focus setting. The starting focus position (a stepper motor count), and the incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack, are specified by instrument commanding.

best focus image product

A *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *best focus image product* is a color JPEG that combines the in-focus (or closest to in-focus) elements of the up to 8 *parent images* into a single image. The onboard focus merge software also creates a *range map product*.

focus merge product

Using the methods described by Edgett *et al.* (2012), *focus merge products* are created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. Two products are created, a *best focus image product* and a *range map product*.

MAHLI toolframe +X distance

Same as *standoff distance*. See *standoff distance*.

parent and child images

Every MAHLI image has a *parent image*, the picture originally commanded to be acquired. Upon command, the parent image can spawn children (each a *child image*) onboard the instrument. Examples of children include *thumbnail images*, focus merge products, and any version of the image that is compressed differently than the parent (Edgett *et al.* 2012). While a parent can be an image that was compressed during image acquisition, our best practice since landing on Mars has been to acquire and store (onboard the instrument) most MAHLI images in uncompressed 8-bit form. An uncompressed 8-bit parent image can be commanded for compression some time after acquisition and storage, whereas a parent that was compressed at the time of acquisition cannot be further compressed onboard the instrument. When a parent is stored onboard in uncompressed form, it can be used to create multiple versions of the image, each time with a different compression scheme, for downlink to Earth. Thus, if the image received is over-compressed, we have the option to retrieve it again (as many times as necessary) in a less compressed form. Indeed, the majority of MAHLI images received from Mars have been losslessly compressed children of an uncompressed, 8-bit parent.

range

Used here in the context of describing a focus merge range map product, this term refers to the distance between the front lens element and in-focus elements of the imaged subject in a given MAHLI focus merge product. As each MAHLI focus stack is acquired at a fixed *working distance*, the range denotes the distance between the camera and the relief elements of the target (*i.e.*, subject), as indicated by grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) in the range map product.

range map product

A grayscale JPEG image *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *range map product* accompanies a *best focus image product*. The grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) can be correlated with knowledge of instrument focus, *working distance*, *range*, and pixel scale.

RATIONALE_DESC

The term, RATIONALE_DESC, comes from the NASA PDS archivists. The RATIONALE_DESC for a given MAHLI image is a text description of the rationale or purpose behind the acquisition of a given MAHLI parent image or onboard focus merge product. Each parent image RATIONALE_DESC provides information that the MAHLI team desired to communicate to data users, such as the intended image target, intended working or standoff distance, intended purpose of the image (e.g., stereo, mosaic, autofocus sub-frame, range-finding), image position in a focus stack, as well as information regarding how the image supports observations made by other MSL science instruments, especially APXS and ChemCam. The RATIONALE_DESC for a focus merge product tells the user which images were merged (on what sol they were acquired and images of which CDPIDs were merged), as well as the focus merge product type (best focus or range map product).

relative focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a starting focus position determined by a preceding instrument command. Usually, this is a focus setting based upon a focus position determined by a preceding autofocus command. The incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack is specified by instrument commanding.

RP distance

RP refers to Rover Planners, the personnel who drive the Curiosity rover and operate its robotic arm. RP distance is equivalent to *standoff distance*. See definition of *standoff distance*.

sol

A Martian day; duration of ~1.027 Earth days.

Sol

A specific Martian sol during the MSL Curiosity mission. Because it landed during local afternoon, the sol that Curiosity arrived on Mars was designated Sol 0 and the first full sol after landing was Sol 1.

standoff distance

Also known as the MAHLI *toolframe distance* and *RP distance*, this is range between the subject photographed and the Y, Z plane defined by the two MAHLI contact sensor probe tips when they are not in contact with a surface. In the MAHLI toolframe, the X axis is equivalent to the instrument's optic (z) axis; the distance between the Y, Z plane and the subject is +X; the – X-axis goes from the Y, Z plane into the camera. *Standoff distance* and *RP distance* are equivalent to the +X MAHLI toolframe distance. MAHLI *standoff distance* is 1.9 cm less than *working distance*.

thumbnail images

Reduced-size versions of MAHLI *parent images* and *focus merge products*, approximately 1/8th size in terms of pixel dimensions. Under most circumstances, a *thumbnail image* is returned to Earth for every *parent image* acquired or *focus merge product* created, whether a full-size version of the *parent image* (or a *child image*) or *focus merge product* is returned or not.

working distance

A photography term that refers to the range between the front lens element of a camera and the subject imaged. MAHLI working distance is 1.9 cm greater than the toolframe (also known as standoff or RP) distance.

7.2 Acronyms

APXS

Alpha Particle X-ray Spectrometer (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CDPID or MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID

Each MAHLI parent image acquired or onboard focus merge product created and stored in the instrument's DEA flash memory is assigned a Camera Data Product ID (CDPID). This identifier, plus the time at which (or sol on which) the data were acquired, uniquely identify each image. The CDPID and sol are incorporated into the image ID. Data acquired by the camera but not stored in the DEA have less unique CDPIDs; these acquisitions have generally been rare and easy for the operations team to track (*i.e.*, 12 such images were obtained during Interplanetary Cruise, only one such image was obtained during the first 1000 sols of operations on Mars).

ChemCam

Chemistry Camera; Laser Induced Breakdown Spectrometer (LIBS) and Remote Microscopic Imager (RMI) (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CheMin

Chemistry and Mineralogy x-ray diffraction (XRD) and x-ray fluorescence (XRF) sample analysis investigation (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CHIMRA

Collection and Handling for Interior Martian Rock Analysis (sample handling and processing subsystem on Curiosity's robotic arm)

DEA

Digital Electronics Assembly, the MAHLI electronics housed inside Curiosity's rover body.

DN

data number (image pixel value)

DOF

image depth of field

DRT

Dust Removal Tool (wire brush tool on Curiosity's robotic arm)

EDR

Experiment Data Record

Hazcam(s)

Hazard cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

ID or image ID

Image identifier (NASA PDS image identifier for MAHLI images and focus merge products).

JPL-Caltech

Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, California, USA

MAHLI

Mars Hand Lens Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MARDI

Mars Descent Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-34 (also M-34 and M34)

34 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-100 (also M-100 and M100)

100 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MSL

Mars Science Laboratory

MSSS

Malin Space Science Systems, San Diego, California, USA

NASA

National Aeronautics and Space Administration (USA space agency)

Navcam(s)

Navigation cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

PDS

Planetary Data System (NASA planetary science data archives)

QMS

Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

RDR

Reduced Data Record

REMS

Rover Environment and Monitoring Station (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

SAM

Sample Analysis at Mars (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

TLS

Tunable Laser Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

USA

United States of America

UTC

Coordinated Universal Time

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References

- Anderson, R. C., L. W. Beegle, J. Hurowitz, C. Hanson, W. Abbey, C. Seybold, D. Limonadi, S. Kuhn, L. Jandura, K. Brown, G. Peters, C. Roumeliotis, M. Robinson, K. Edgett, M. Minitti, J. Grotzinger (2015) The Mars Science Laboratory scooping campaign at Rocknest, *Icarus* 256, 66–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icarus.2015.03.033>
- Edgett, K. S., R. A. Yingst, M. A. Ravine, M. A. Caplinger, J. N. Maki, F. T. Ghaemi, J. A. Schaffner, J. F. Bell III, L. J. Edwards, K. E. Herkenhoff, E. Heydari, L. C. Kah, M. T. Lemmon, M. E. Minitti, T. S. Olson, T. J. Parker, S. K. Rowland, J. Schieber, R. J. Sullivan, D. Y. Sumner, P. C. Thomas, E. H. Jensen, J. J. Simmonds, A. J. Sengstacken, R. G. Willson, and W. Goetz (2012) Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) investigation, *Space Sci. Rev.* 170, 259–317. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-012-9910-4>
- Edgett, K. S., R. A. Yingst, and the MSL Science Team (2013) Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI): Sol 0–179 activities, observations, range and scale characterization, *European Planetary Science Congress 2013*, vol. 8, Abstract EPSC2013-246. (8–13 September 2013, London, United Kingdom)
- Edgett, K. S., M. A. Caplinger, J. N. Maki, M. A. Ravine, F. T. Ghaemi, S. McNair, K. E. Herkenhoff, B. M. Duston, R. G. Willson, R. A. Yingst, M. R. Kennedy, M. E. Minitti, A. J. Sengstacken, K. D. Supulver, L. J. Lipkaman, G. M. Krezoski, M. J. McBride, T. L. Jones, B. E. Nixon, J. K. Van Beek, D. J. Krysak, and R. L. Kirk (2015) Curiosity's robotic arm-mounted Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI): Characterization and calibration status, *MSL MAHLI Technical Report 0001* (version 1: 19 June 2015; version 2: 05 October 2015). <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>
- Garvin, J. B., K. S. Edgett, R. Dotson, D. M. Fey, K. E. Herkenhoff, B. J. Hallet, M. R. Kennedy (2017) Quantitative relief models of rock surfaces on Mars at sub-millimeter scales from Mars Curiosity rover Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) observations: Geologic implications, *Microscopy and Microanalysis* 23(S1), 2146–2147. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1431927617011394>
- Malin, M., Edgett, K., Jensen, E., Lipkaman, L. (2013) Mast Camera (Mastcam), Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI), and Mars Descent Imager (MARDI) Experiment Data Record (EDR) and Reduced Data Record (RDR) PDS data products, version 1.2, *Mars Science Laboratory Project Software Interface Specification (SIS)*, JPL D-75410, SIS-

SCI0135-MSL, file MSL_MMM_EDR_RDR_DPSIS.PDF archived by the NASA Planetary Data System, 29 October 2013.

- Minitti, M. E., L. C. Kah, R. A. Yingst, K. S. Edgett, R. C. Anderson, L. W. Beegle, J. L. Carsten, R. G. Deen, W. Goetz, C. Hardgrove, D. E. Harker, K. E. Herkenhoff, J. A. Hurowitz, L. Jandura, M. R. Kennedy, G. Kocurek, G. M. Krezoski, S. R. Kuhn, D. Limonadi, L. Lipkaman, M. B. Madsen, T. S. Olson, M. L. Robinson, S. K. Rowland, D. M. Rubin, C. Seybold, J. Schieber, M. Schmidt, D. Y. Sumner, V. V. Tompkins, J. K. Van Beek, T. Van Beek (2013) MAHLI at the Rocknest sand shadow: Science and science-enabling activities, *J. Geophys. Res.* 118(11), 2338–2360. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2013JE004426>
- Vasavada, A. R., J. P. Grotzinger, R. E. Arvidson, F. J. Calef, J. A. Crisp, S. Gupta, J. Hurowitz, N. Mangold, S. Maurice, M. E. Schmidt, R. C. Wiens, R. M. E. Williams, and R. A. Yingst (2014) Overview of the Mars Science Laboratory mission: Bradbury Landing to Yellowknife Bay and beyond, *J. Geophys. Res.* 119, 1134–1161. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014JE004622>
- Yingst, R. A., K. S. Edgett, M. R. Kennedy, G. M. Krezoski, M. J. McBride, M. E. Minitti, M. A. Ravine, R. M. E. Williams (2016) MAHLI on Mars: Lessons learned operating a geoscience camera on a landed payload robotic arm, *Geoscientific Instrumentation, Methods and Data Systems* 5, 205–217. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gi-5-205-2016>

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